

Coherent & Cross-compliant Ocean Governance for Delivering the EU Green Deal for European Seas

Deliverable 3.6

Cross-Compliance in integrative planning

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Abstract	This Deliverable D3.6 presents the results of CrossGov's Task 3.2, which investigates the coherence among planning systems established under three EU Directives: the Water Framework Directive (WFD), the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD). The analysis is based on four case studies located in the Finnish Archipelago, the North Adriatic Sea, the French Mediterranean Sea, and the Oslo Fjord. The study

	<p>explores whether planning processes under these directives operate in cross-compliance to support the European Green Deal (EGD) objectives on zero pollution and marine biodiversity. Two analytical frameworks guided the research: the Policy Coherence Framework and the Science-Policy-Society Interface assessment framework. Findings highlight mechanisms and practices used by national and local authorities to enhance policy coherence, particularly horizontal coherence across the three planning systems. The case studies also identify areas of incoherence and suggestions or transferable lessons, especially where operational solutions already exist area also offered. These insights may be relevant to other EU contexts aiming to strengthen integrated marine and water governance in support of EGD goals.</p>
Keywords	Coherence; WFD; MSFD; MSP; Planning processes; Eutrophication; Marine-based activities; Land-based pollution; Marine planning; Synergies ; Challenges; Local level; Misalignment; Authorities; Cross-compliance; European Green Deal

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Acronyms

Table 1: Acronyms used through the text reporting on the case study work. To note that for reasons of uniformity with pre-existing literature on the topic, all acronyms related to the French Mediterranean case study have been left in French in the text.

ACCOMBAS	Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and contiguous Atlantic area
ARPA	Regional Agency for the Protection of the Environment
AZA	Allocated Zone for Aquaculture
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CFP	Common Fishery Policy
CITES	Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora
DM	Decree of the Ministry
DPCM	Decree of the Prime Minister
DSF	Document Stratégique de Façade (Façade Strategic Document - transposes the MSFD and MSPD)
EFH	Essential Fish Habitat
EGD	European Green Deal
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EMFAF	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
ELY	Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (Elinkeino-, liikenne- ja ympäristökeskus)
FRA	Fisheries Restricted Area
GES	Good Environmental Status
GFCM	General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean
GSA	Geographic Sub Area
H&BDs	Habitat and Birds Directives
ISPRA	Institute for Environmental Protection and Research
IOMP	Integrated Ocean Management Plans (Norwegian parallel to EU's Marine Strategies)
IUU fishing	Illegal, unreported, and unregulated fishing
LSI	Land-sea Interactions
MaS	Marine Strategy
MASAF	Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty, and Forestry
MASE	Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security
MIT	Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSPD	Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
MSP	Maritime Spatial Plans
N	Nitrogen
nm	Nautical mile
NIS	Non-indigenous Species
OECM	Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures
P	Phosphorus
PADDUC	Plan d'aménagement et de développement durable de la Corse (Corsica's sustainable development plan - land management plan for Corsica)
PBA	Plan and Building Act
PoM	Programmes of Measures
RBMP	River Basin Management Plan

SDAGE (RBMP)	Schéma directeur d'aménagement et de gestion des eaux (River Based Management Plan for the French Hydrographic basins)
SEA	Strategic Environmental Assessment
SMVM	Schema de mise en valeur de la mer (Coastal municipalities' a sea development schemes previous to the MSP and still ongoing)
SNML	Stratégie Nationale de la mer et du littoral (France's national strategy for the sea and coastline)
SRADDET	Schéma régional d'aménagement, de développement durable et d'égalité des territoires (Regional plan for spatial planning, sustainable development and territorial equality - land-management plan for the Provence-Alpes-Côte-D'Azur Region)
STERE	Schémas territorial de restauration écologique (Territorial ecological restoration schemes supported in the framework of the Façade Strategic Document program of measure and supported by the Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea and the Water Agency)
WFD	Water Framework Directive
UWWT	Urban wastewater treatment

Executive Summary

The Horizon Europe CrossGov projects aims at enhancing knowledge on how coherence and cross-compliance of European marine related policies affect the ability to realize the European Green Deal (EGD) objectives related to protection of marine biodiversity, climate resilience, and zero pollution. Work Package 3 explores, by means of case study approach, the reality of implementing several legal and policy frameworks simultaneously. Two tasks are part of WP3: **Task 3.2** studies the coherence of the three sets of planning systems from the three EU framework Directives: Water Framework Directive (WFD), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), and Marine Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD). The task also explored whether the planning processes associated with the MSFD, WFD, and MSPD operate in cross-compliance to support the delivery of the EGD of zero pollution and marine biodiversity objective. **Task 3.3** explores how selected sectors (agriculture, fisheries, aquaculture, and offshore wind energy) internalise the environmental requirements from the three framework Directives through policy instruments (i.e. impact assessments, funding conditionalities, environmental assessments or authorisations processes), and also, how the three EGD objectives of focus (marine biodiversity, climate resilience, and zero pollution) are, or can be internalized (mainstreamed) into these sectoral policies.

The current Deliverable 3.6 documents the results of the Task 3.2 work. The four case studies explored in Task 3.2 are located in the Finnish Archipelago, the North Adriatic Sea, the French Mediterranean Sea and the Oslo Fjord. Deliverable 3.7, documenting the results of Task 3.3 should be seen as a sibling report to the current D3.6 Deliverable.

Findings from the case studies illustrate aspects and mechanisms applied by national and local authorities that would contribute to advancing policy coherence across the three planning systems. As reflected in the analysed data, strengthening this horizontal coherence would also support the achievement of the of the EGD objectives on zero pollution and marine biodiversity. Among these aspect and mechanisms, structured according to the coherence attributes and explanatory variables are:

- **Policy objectives** (coherence attribute). For example, mandatory alignment between MSFD measures and RBMP objectives; linking RBMP and MaS to address marine nutrient reduction; and integrating WFD and MSFD objectives within the MSP framework.
- **Instruments** (coherence attribute). For example, a unified strategic framework aligning MSFD and MSP requirements; coordinated monitoring activities across WFD, MSFD, and MSP; measures designed with consideration for environmental and economic interactions; coordination between MSP and terrestrial planning instruments; and a cross-sectoral action plan layered into existing planning instruments.
- **Governmental structures** (explanatory variable). For example, the presence of coordinating agencies facilitating integration of MSFD, WFD, and MSP governance; and the availability of multidisciplinary expertise in both freshwater and marine domains among civil servants in freshwater agencies.
- **Science-policy-society interfaces** (explanatory variable). For example, environmental agencies collaborating with universities and research institutions not only as knowledge providers and policy advisors, but also as knowledge brokers and boundary organizations; and the presence of a consultative council that ensures representation across sectors and governance levels.

Regarding **stakeholder engagement**, another explanatory variable, no positive learning experiences were identified in the case studies. Stakeholder involvement related to the WFD, MSFD, and MSP continues to occur in silos, with each policy maintaining separate engagement processes. Public consultations are conducted independently for each policy and are sometimes criticised for lacking sufficient participatory depth.

Findings from the case studies not only highlighted areas in need of improvement (areas of incoherence) but also revealed situations that may be relevant to other contexts across the EU. For each identified area, we present suggestions that emerged during co-creation processes, and/or opportunities for lesson extraction, particularly where solutions are already operational in one or more case studies. The following are the areas for which we offer suggestions or transferable lessons (see Chapter 4 for details):

- Exploit the role of MSP in the integration of environmental objectives into spatial decision-making for marine areas
- Strengthen the explicit links from the RBMP to MSP
- Strengthen a structured coordination across all governance levels
- Progressively develop an integrated land-sea stakeholder engagement process
- Strengthen local technical competence and implementation capacity
- Strengthen the science-policy interactions between terrestrial, coastal and marine water governance

Chapter 2 provides a description of the research design, including the research questions and analytical frameworks. Chapter 3 is structured around the four case studies conducted under Task 3.2. Each case study begins with concise contextual information outlining the geographic scope and the specific challenges addressed. This is followed by a description of the methodology applied, including a list of key documents and actors involved. Subsequent subsections present the results of the analysis on horizontal and vertical coherence, along with brief information on how the three Directives are implemented in the respective countries. Key elements emphasized in these sections include: (i) factors supporting horizontal and vertical coherence, and (ii) potential strategies to enhance coherence—both in relation to the specific challenge addressed and in contributing to the delivery of the European Green Deal (EGD) objectives. Finally, Chapter 4 succinctly presents the findings from the case studies, illustrating the mechanisms and practices applied by national and local authorities, as well as the areas for which we offer suggestions or transferable lessons, as previously described.

1. Introduction

The Horizon Europe CrossGov project aims at enhancing knowledge on how coherence and cross-compliance of European marine related policies affect the ability to realize the European Green Deal (EGD). In specific, assesses to what extent and in which manner policy coherence (in policy design and implementation) affects or facilitates cross-compliance with the EGD objectives related to protection of marine biodiversity, climate resilience, and zero pollution¹.

Box 1 brings the key concepts to be understood by the readers of this document.

Box 1: Key concepts and definitions part of the CrossGov project

(Source: [D1.2 \(2023\) Policy Brief on coherent and cross-compliant Ocean Governance](#); [D1.3 \(2024\) Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework](#); [D4.2 \(2025\) Handbook on Policy Coherence](#))

Policy: Refers to a set of objectives, rules and measures that provide guidance for solving a particular societal issue. Within the CrossGov project, a *policy* can encompass substantive documents such as white papers and strategies as well as specific laws and regulations, or directives.

Policy area: Refers to a substantive group of policies that has formed around societal or sectoral interests. Examples of policy areas are environmental protection, trade, transport, waste, or renewable energy.

Policy coherence refers to how well different *policies* work together. It concerns the alignment and coordination of policies across different *policy areas* and governance levels to achieve mutually reinforcing outcomes and avoid that policy interventions contradict or undermine each other. Coherence can be defined as the extent to which policies strengthen each other by promoting synergies or reducing conflicts between objectives and measures both in design and implementation. Policy Coherence can be observed along two major axes: Horizontal and Vertical.

Horizontal coherence: refers to how well policies at the **same governance level** work together. It concerns the coherence between policies within the same *policy area* (e.g. between different EU water and wastewater policies), but also across different *policy areas* (e.g. between renewable energy and biodiversity policies). Horizontal coherence also describes policies that are cross-cutting though institutional and sectoral boundaries.

Vertical coherence: refers to how well policies are aligned **between different governance levels**. It concerns the alignment of policy interventions and plans across governance levels.

Cross-compliance specifically explores the cross-sectoral outcomes and impacts towards the EGD, the compliance with multiple strategies, objectives, goals, and targets in concert (progress towards one strategy does not negatively affect progress towards the objectives of other strategies, or even better, that actions support several strategies simultaneously). That is, effective design and implementation of policy instruments are required to deliver not only the individual policies' specified goals and targets, but also to support the achievement of other objectives under the EGD. Focus is on a subset of EGD objectives related to protection of marine biodiversity, climate resilience, and zero pollution. CrossGov works on the assumption that both horizontal and vertical coherence are important factors contributing to cross-compliance.

Ocean governance within CrossGov covers the entire policy landscape and its implementation that affects marine ecosystems, coupling marine with land-based policy and regulatory frameworks. It also refers to the formal and informal processes of collective decision-making, planning, deliberating, and capacity building by governmental, market, and civil society actors.

¹ This is just a “shorthand” that aims to cover -within those three areas, the several objectives which are relevant to the ocean (see [D1.1 \(2023\) Green Deal Objectives and Scenarios](#))

Work Package 3 (WP3) explores, by means of case study approach (D3.1²), the reality of implementing several legal and policy frameworks simultaneously.

Two tasks are part of WP3: **Task 3.2** explores the coherence of the three sets of planning systems from the three EU framework Directives: Water Framework Directive (WFD), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), and Marine Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD). The task also explored whether the planning processes associated with the MSFD, WFD, and MSPD operate in cross-compliance to support the delivery of the EGD of zero pollution and marine biodiversity objective. **Task 3.3** explores how selected sectors (agriculture, fisheries, aquaculture, and offshore wind energy) internalise the environmental requirements from the three framework Directives through policy instruments (i.e. impact assessments, funding conditionalities, environmental assessments or authorisations processes), and also, how the three EGD objectives of focus (marine biodiversity, climate resilience, and zero pollution) are, or can be internalized (mainstreamed) into these sectoral policies³.

Table 2 presents the questions for WP3 as presented in the Description of Action (DoA) (left column) and how these questions have been operationalized with a Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 lens (middle and right columns). The key research questions that WP3 aims to address have been fine-tuned along the development of the project. Also, and as it will be presented in Chapter 3, more specific questions have been defined within each of the case studies.

Table 2: Evolution of CrossGov’s WP3 questions through a Task 3.2 and a Task 3.3 lens.

Key research questions that WP3 aims to address (as stated in the DoA)	Explanations of the questions with a Task 3.2 lens	Explanations of the questions with a Task 3.3 lens
How do the plans and planning processes that implement marine related legal and policy frameworks support or impede progress towards the GD objectives?	Addresses both: Horizontal coherence (e.g., “how do the interlinkages between national and local plans developed under the WFD, MSFD, MSP provide an integrated approach to govern and protect the marine environment?”), and	Addresses both: Do policy instruments [delivery mechanisms] set for the implementation of sectoral policies adequately internalize key-requirements of EU policies established to deliver healthy marine ecosystems (MSFD/WFD/MSPD)?, and
What explains the degree of vertical coherence towards the GD objectives?	Vertical coherence (e.g., “to what extent does the resulting interplay between these three Directives’ national and local plans assists the reaching of the three EGD objectives of focus in CrossGov?”).	Do policy instruments set for the implementation of sectoral policies adequately internalize the three EGD objectives of focus in CrossGov?
What can be learnt from impediments and best practices, as reported in the first two questions, to facilitate the realisation of the key GD objectives?	Addressed by analysing the findings from the first two questions: For example: What is the takeaway? What needs to be done to facilitate the realisation of the three EGD objectives of focus? Which lessons can be distilled that can assist the coherence and cross-compliance of marine policies both for their own intended objectives, as well as for the three EGD objectives of focus?	What can be learnt from impediments and best practices to facilitate the internalization of the key GD objectives into sectoral policies?

² D3.1 (2023) (A framework for implementing case studies in CrossGov – internal report), is meant for case study leaders in the CrossGov project as a tool to refer to when carrying out the different stages of implementation of the case study work.

³ See Deliverable 3.7 which is a sibling report to the current D3.6 Deliverable

Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 complement each other. Together, they help understand what the status of coherence across environmental and sectoral policies is, and the interlinkages between those policies (when implemented) towards the cross-compliance with the three EGD objectives of focus. At the same time, the work developed as part of WP3 is linked to other Tasks and WP in the project (*Table 3*).

Table 3: Linkages between WP3 and other Tasks and WP as part of the CrossGov project.

Linkages with WP1	Methodologies for the assessment of Policy Coherence (D1.3, rev Feb 2024) and for the assessment of Science-Policy-Society Interfaces in function of Coherence and Cross-compliance (D1.4, 2023) were drafted and put to test with the case study work carried out in WP3. Both sets of methodologies were fine-tuned based on the experiences of implementing them as part of the WP3 work. The final version can be found respectively in D4.2 (2025) Handbook on Policy Coherence , and D4.3 (2025) Blueprint for SPS .
Linkages with WP2	WP2 analysed and evaluates the multi-level policy landscape (EU, international, national) relevant to the Green Deal in the marine domain. Tasks 2.1 mapped the EU and international policy landscape (D2.1 (2024) EU and international policy landscape). Task 2.2 analysed the horizontal coherence in selected areas of the EU policy landscape (D2.2 (2024) Horizontal coherence in EU law and policy). Task 2.3 analysed the vertical coherence by focusing on the transposition into national policies in Norway, the Netherlands, Germany, and Finland (D2.3 (2024) Vertical coherence in EU and national policies). Figure 1 brings a graphical representation of the connections between WP2 and WP3.
Linkages with WP4	Drawing on the information and experiences gathered in WP2 and WP3, three Roadmaps addressing offshore wind energy , agriculture pollution , and fisheries were co-created in collaboration with key stakeholders from each sector (D4.1 (2025) Policy coherence roadmaps).
Linkages with WP5	WP3 case study results, as part of the products from WP4, are shared with all interested parties (decision-makers, stakeholders, students and young professionals) through the means of communicating synthesis, workshops, webinars (see for example News and Events) and the CrossGov MOOC .

Coherence in Policy Design

WP 2

- EU policy landscape
- Horizontal coherence in policy clusters
- Vertical coherence MS-EU (transposition of selected policies)

Coherence in Policy Implementation

WP 3

- Policy coherence at case study level
- Horizontal coherence in policy clusters

Case level

Figure 1: Graphical representation of the connections between WP2 and WP3 as part of the CrossGov project.

The four case studies explored in **Task 3.2** are located in the Finnish Archipelago, the North Adriatic Sea, the French Mediterranean Sea and the Oslo Fjord. It considers to what extent coordination mechanisms between the three planning systems are developed -or not (horizontal

coherence). It also considers the coherence of these three sets of planning systems towards cross-compliance with the three EGD of focus in CrossGov (vertical coherence). **Box 2** offers an overview of key aspects of the three directives.

Box 2: WFD, MSFD, and MSPD: Providing structure and coordination

Adapted from EC, n.d1; EC, n.d2; EC, n.d3; EC, n.d4; CrossGov MOOC Module 3 (2025)

The WFD and MSFD were designed to provide a structure, a framework, within which the wide variety of existing sectoral policies could be implemented in a more holistic and coordinated manner. Rather than imposing direct regulation on specific sectors, many of which are already governed (e.g. fisheries-CFP, agriculture-CAP), the framework directives aim to integrate and align such policies under a unified approach. The MSPD provides a structured platform for aligning different sectoral interests, enabling diverse marine activities to coexist within the same maritime space (Refer to *Table 4* for a concise overview of the key elements of the three framework directives).

At the national and local scale, the instruments used to operationalize these directives (i.e River Basin Management Plans, Marine Strategies, Maritime Spatial Plans) set objectives and guide management efforts, including the development of national strategies, management plans, and monitoring programs. In addition to these instruments, other relevant EU and national legislation, such as the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive, Nitrates Directive, Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive, Common Agricultural Policy, Drinking Water Directive, and Bathing Water Directive also contribute to addressing the various factors impacting inland and marine waters by providing specific measures for pollution control and water quality standards.

Table 4: Key elements from the three framework Directives.

Water Framework Directive (WFD) Directive 2000/60/EC	Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) Directive 2008/56/EC	Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD) Directive 2014/89/EU
<p>Aims to ensure the good qualitative and quantitative status of all inland, transitional, coastal surface waters, and groundwaters.</p> <p>Requires EU Member States to develop River Basin Management Plans (RBMP) and Programmes of Measures (PoM) to protect and restore water bodies, prevent their deterioration, and achieve good chemical and ecological status.</p> <p>While the term "sectors" is not explicitly used in the Directive, implicit cross-sectoral coordination is reflected in, for example, Art 1 (obligation to address all water uses, functions, and values); Art 3(4) (ensure that the requirements of the Directive are coordinated for the whole of the river basin district); and Art 14 (requiring public participation and stakeholder consultation during the development of the RBMP).</p>	<p>Has the overarching goal of achieving and maintaining Good Environmental Status (GES) in European marine waters.</p> <p>Requires EU Member States to develop and implement a Marine strategy (MaS) for each marine region or subregion within their waters.</p> <p>MaS are overarching, cyclical plans that include several key elements: Initial assessment of the marine environment; determination of Good Environmental Status (GES); establishment of environmental targets and indicators; monitoring programmes; and programmes of measures (PoMs) to achieve or maintain GES.</p>	<p>Aims to promote the sustainable development of maritime economies, the sustainable use of marine resources, and the protection of marine environments by coordinating the spatial and temporal distribution of human activities at sea.</p> <p>Requires coastal Member States to develop and implement Maritime Spatial Plans (MSP) for their marine waters.</p>

WFD and MSFD: designed to be complementary

Both directives are meant to work in synergy, and specific coordination is required in transitional and coastal waters where the directives' scopes intersect according to national implementation. That is, emphasis of the WFD's RBMP and the MSFD's PoMs should be on coordination, rather than on alignment.

Some of the elements that assist this coordination are:

The general objective of both the WFD and MSFD in achieving good status of waters

- The WFD targets Good Ecological and Chemical Status for inland surface waters, transitional waters, groundwater, and coastal waters extending up to one nautical mile (nm) from the baseline.
- The MSFD aims for Good Environmental Status in marine waters from the baseline seaward to the outermost reach of the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) or to the outer limits of Member States' jurisdiction. The MSFD covers additional aspects such as biodiversity, marine mammals, seabirds, marine litter, and underwater noise, and is designed to complement the WFD by explicitly avoiding duplication of efforts in coastal waters, instead focusing on pressures and descriptors more relevant to the wider environment.

The complementarity of eutrophication and contaminants measures under the WFD and MSFD:

- The MSFD builds on the WFD framework, extending and adapting it for the marine environment, particularly from the baseline seawards.
- For eutrophication (D5), the MSFD requires that assessments in marine waters take into account the WFD assessments for coastal and transitional waters. The WFD's "Good Ecological Status" for these waters is linked to the MSFD's "Good Environmental status".
- For contaminants (D8), the MSFD is closely related to WFD activities, such as monitoring and assessment of chemical pollutants, implementation of RBMPs to reduce land-based pollution, and reduction or phase-out of priority hazardous substances. Both directives use Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for certain priority substances. The MSFD may include additional contaminants and threshold values not covered by the WFD (i.e. marine-specific pollutants, offshore areas).

The implementation of an ecosystem-based approach as an element that assists the alignment between the three Directives

- The MSFD (Recital 8 and 44, and Article 1(3)) and the MSPD (Recital 14 and Article 5(1)) explicitly promote an ecosystem-based approach to managing human activities in aquatic and marine environments.
- While the WFD does not explicitly use the term "ecosystem-based approach" in its legal text, it requires managing water resources at the river basin level, and holistically protecting all water bodies (surface, coastal, and groundwater) by considering both ecological and chemical status. This reflects an integrated and ecosystem-respecting approach to water management that aims to maintain the integrity of the entire aquatic ecosystem

The contribution of the three framework Directives to the Source-to- Sea approach

The Source-to-Sea approach recognizes the interconnectedness of different water systems the continuum of inland, transitional, coastal, and marine waters. Effectively managing this continuum requires an approach that acts on the different dynamics and pressures in this continuum. This does not mean that there needs to be a one single policy, or absolute uniformity in the policies, but that different legal frameworks or policies for a joint and coherent framework.

Source-to-Sea has been mentioned in the Ocean Pact (i.e. within its strategic framework for improving ocean health and tackling pollution) (EC, 2025a), but also in the Water Resilience strategy (as a central principle for addressing water management in Europe (EC, 2025b).

The three Directives each contribute to this approach:

- The WFD promotes river basin management and integrates of all water types (inland, transitional, coastal surface waters, and groundwaters).
- The MSFD complements the WFD by extending integrated management into the marine domain.

- The MSPD emphasizes the importance of considering land-sea interactions to promote sustainable use of maritime space. This includes accounting for how land-based activities affect the sea and vice versa, promoting coherent and integrated planning across the land-sea interface.

Acknowledging that staggered timelines can persist

Rather than forcing every directive or agency to align their planning schedules or processes, smarter bridging mechanisms are needed, and the concept of *practical interoperability* should be seen as a goal. This concept refers to the ability of different plans, systems, and organizations, each with their own timelines, data formats, and policy goals, to work efficiently together without requiring full synchronization or identical cycles. Through shared tools, data standards, and coordination mechanisms, the exchange and mutual understanding of information, monitoring results, and policy decisions can take place across domains (CNR-ISMAR, 2024; Gómez-Ballesteros, et al, 2021; Haugen et al.2024).

Findings from the case studies illustrate actions that can support the achievement of this *practical interoperability* concept and **advancing policy coherence** by fostering synergies and minimizing conflicts among plans, systems, and organizations operating under diverse timelines, data formats, and policy objectives.

Deliverable 3.6 (D3.6) documents the 2nd cycle of the case study work carried out between September 2024 and April 2025. The 1st cycle of the case study work (March 2023 to May 2024) was documented in Deliverable 3.2 (June 2024) as part of an internal mid-term assessment of Task 3.2. Deliverable 3.2, intended for internal use, was primarily aimed at CrossGov partners. The content of this document was the basis for the discussions taking place at CrossGov’s third Consortium meeting (Marseille, June 17th – 19th, 2024).

In this 2nd cycle, emphasis was placed on bringing into the case study work, where relevant, the findings from D2.1 (EU and international policy landscape), D2.2 (Horizontal coherence in EU law and policy) and D2.3 (Vertical coherence in EU and national policies and laws). Emphasis was also made on operationalizing further the co-creation approach (WP5). Participatory workshops (e.g French Med⁴), webinars (e.g Fisheries in the Med) and co-creation sessions (e.g Archipelago and Oslo Fjord⁵) allowed us to integrate local knowledge and at the same time validate findings and refine the recommendations for improving policy coherence. Results of these WP3 processes were, along the results from WP2 work, transmitted into the WP4 products (Roadmaps).

In preparation for this phase, best practices for co-creation and stakeholder engagement were reinforced to the case study leaders. The project had been actively operationalizing its conceptual model of co-creation, particularly in the co-design of the scope of the case study work, research questions, and interview content, supported by the CrossGov *Stakeholder Operational Guideline* (2023)⁶, which was developed under co-creation principles to guide stakeholder engagement in the case study areas.

⁴ The stakeholder event, open to all potential stakeholders, was attended by public authorities (60%) and researchers (40%).

⁵ A selected group of stakeholders in the Oslofjord form the ‘reference group’. Part of this reference group is Oslo County Governor, and representatives of the Fishermen's Association, Oslo Region, and Oslofjord Outdoor Council.

⁶ Operational Guidance for Stakeholder Mobilisation and co-building in CrossGov (2023) – internal report.

The topic of co-creation was discussed during the internal WP3 meeting held on September 2024. Concrete messages were given on the distinctions between co-creation and traditional collaboration. Suggestions were also presented on how to manage stakeholder fatigue which had been repeatedly mentioned as a barrier to meaningful engagement in co-creation processes (see *Figure 2*). The topic of gender balance within stakeholder engagement activities was also brought into the discussion.

Figure 2: Examples of the slides used as part of the re-enforcement of a co-creation approach in CrossGov

D3.6 needs to be seen as entry point for detailed information contained in other internal reports (Step1, Step 2, and Step 3 reports⁷) but also as the “behind the scenes” for the material that has been produced as part of WP4 and WP5 (e.g. [CrossGov Webinar Series](#), [Marine Policy Coherence Roadmaps](#), and the [CrossGov MOOC](#)).

Note to the reader:

The case study chapters contain a rich collection of information. To enhance readability and facilitate comprehension, selected content has been organized into highlighted information boxes.

Key elements emphasized in these chapters from Deliverable D3.6 include:

- Elements supporting horizontal and vertical coherence
- Potential strategies to enhance coherence, both in addressing the specific challenge explored in the case study, and in contributing to the delivery of the EGD objective.

⁷ See Annexes 1 to 3 for the templates; selected examples of the Step reports can be seen in [Publications](#).

2. Research design

This section gives a description of the Methods, Research Questions, and Frameworks of Analysis used for carrying out Task 3.2. Detail accounts of the methods are specified in the case study chapters (chapter 3). Detail descriptions of the Frameworks of Analysis can be consulted in the respective CrossGov deliverables which are referenced in sub-section 2.3.

2.1 Methods

Task 3.2 is carried out following the case study approach described in D3.1 (2023)⁸. In addition, and guided by the questions included in the assessment frameworks (see section 2.3), case study leaders collected primary empirical material by means of document analysis and stakeholder engagement (semi-structured interviews and workshops). Secondary data (peer reviewed journal manuscripts, and grey literature) was also collected and analysed. Among the analysed documents were national and regional level-policy documents, the respective RBMP, MaS, and MSP planning documents, and other documents related to specific sectors of interest to the case study.

Table 5 gives an overview of the CrossGov partners participating in the case study work and who are the authors of the respective case study chapters. A detailed account of the documents explored in each of the case studies, and the stakeholder events which took place can be found in the respective case study sections.

Table 5: CrossGov partners participants of the Task3.2 work and who are authors of the current Deliverable..

Finnish Archipelago	
	Antti Belinskij
	Eerika Albrecht
	Elina Heikkilä
	Teppo Linjama
	Arto Hietaniemi
	Anton Ruotsalainen
Northern Adriatic Sea	
	Ginevra Capurso
	Emiliano Ramieri
	Andrea Barbanti
French Mediterranean	
	Laura Bastide
	Sarah Loudin
	Pierre Strosser
Oslo Fjord	
	Gunnar Sander
	Saskia Trubbach
	Aase Jeanette Kvanneid
Task 3.2 lead	
	Paulina Ramírez-Monsalve

Three pivotal workshops have taken place during the three CrossGov' s annual meetings. The Kick-off meeting in Oslo (September 2022), the second consortium meeting in Venice (June

⁸ D3.1 (2023) A framework for implementing case studies in CrossGov – internal report

2023) and the third consortium meeting in Marseille (June 2024) gathered stakeholders from the Oslo-Fjord, the North Adriatic and the Mediterranean case⁹ respectively. The workshops resulted very useful in either collecting initial information about the case study, or input for the co-creation of the case study and its research questions. In relation to the Oslo Fjord and the North Adriatic, the discussions highlighted the challenges of moving towards an integrated implementation of the three framework directives.

The collected primary empirical material and secondary data was structured by case study leaders into three internal reports referred to as Step 1, Step 2, and Step 3 (D3.1, 2023). Annexes 1 to 3 bring the templates used for each of these reports. *Table 6* gives a brief description of the intentions for each of internal reports. Although the Step reports were meant to be for internal use, some of these are now available at the CrossGov website (see [Publications](#)).

Table 6: The three Step reports used by Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 to document the collected data.

Step 1 report	
	Prepares the case study research design by giving a brief contextual description of the case study; describes the specific problem at focus, specifies the research objectives, and presents a preliminary list of documents to analyse and actors to include in stakeholder events.
Step 2 report	
	Assesses, within the relevant case study area, the current state of play in coherence and cross-compliance and the implications for policy outcomes. Brings the results from applying the two assessment frameworks (see section 2.3 for a brief overview of the frameworks).
Step 3 report	
	Answers WP3 and case-study specific research questions; summarises other findings (if any); draws conclusions from the cases including areas for improvement

The data has been under an evolving level of analysis throughout the Task 3.2 work (see Figure 3), moving from the Step 2 report (documenting the results from the two assessment frameworks¹⁰) into the Step 3 report (answering the Task 3.2 research questions¹¹), and finally into the sub-sections presenting the analysis of horizontal and vertical coherences in each of the case study sub-sections documented in Chapter 3. This last step followed a Grounded Theory inspired process of coding. Through *initial (open) coding*, relevant categories from collected data were extracted; through *focused (axial) coding*, connections between the categories were obtained (Box 3).

⁹ The Mediterranean case study, part of Task 3.3, is documented in Deliverable 3.7, which serves as a companion report to the current Deliverable 3.6.

¹⁰ Section 2.3 presents a concise overview of the two assessment frameworks.

¹¹ Section 2.2 presents the research questions developed by the case study leaders, inspired by the overarching questions of Task 3.2.

Figure 3: Relationship between the information documented in the Step reports and how it fed the respective sections of this Deliverable. Ovals represent a processing of the information, and straight arrows represent where the information has been documented.

Box 3: A brief account of Grounded Theory and the coding process

(Charmaz, 2001)

Grounded Theory is a qualitative research methodology aimed at developing theories that emerge directly from empirical data, rather than being derived from preconceived hypotheses. This approach often adopts a constructivist viewpoint, emphasizing the co-construction of knowledge between researchers and participants. It is a flexible and iterative method that promotes simultaneous data collection and analysis, the identification of emergent themes, and the theoretical integration of abstract categories to explain the phenomena under study.

The coding process typically occurs in two main phases. The first phase, initial (open) coding, involves breaking down qualitative data into discrete units that capture basic actions, events, or ideas. The second phase, focused (axial) coding, explores the relationships among the initial codes, identifying the most significant or frequent ones and further developing them to organize larger segments of data. This often involves grouping codes into categories and subcategories based on their properties and dimensions. The overall coding process is not linear; researchers move back and forth between data and codes, using constant comparison to refine categories and construct a grounded theoretical framework.

2.2 Research questions

As mentioned earlier, case study leaders developed specific research questions inspired by the overarching questions of Task 3.2 (see *Table 2*) and informed by the interests of stakeholders in their respective case study areas. These questions explore both horizontal and vertical coherence within each case study.

2.2.1 Horizontal coherence

Within the CrossGov project, we understand horizontal coherence as to how well policies at the same governance level work together. An assessment of horizontal coherence can help

identify excessive administrative burdens, overlaps, gaps, inconsistencies, implementation problems, and/or obsolete measures. Understanding horizontal coherence can also help identify potential synergies across policies and policy areas that could be strengthened to improve overall policy performance (D4.2, 2025).

The horizontal coherence between the implementation of the WFD, MSFD and MSPD planning documents was addressed in Task 3.2 through the overarching question:

“How do the interlinkages between national and local plans developed under the WFD, MSFD, MSP provide an integrated approach to govern and protect the marine environment?”

Drawing on this overarching question and guided by a defined analytical focus, case study leaders formulated specific questions to explore horizontal coherence (see *Table 7*)

Table 7: The case-study specific research questions addressing horizontal coherence of planning documents in a nutshell.

Which synergies and conflicts / challenges appear in the operational implementation of River basin management plans (WFD), Marine Strategies (MSFD), and Marine Spatial plans (MSPD) with the goal of...	
Finnish Archipelago case	...addressing eutrophication?
North Adriatic case	... contributing to managing conflicts between uses and to achieving a good status of water and marine environment in an area with many anthropic uses?
French Mediterranean case	... improving biodiversity conditions consideration within the marine governance setting?
OsloFjord case	...addressing the ecosystem deterioration of the Oslo Fjord?
What needs to be done to enhance horizontal coherence to ...	
Finnish Archipelago case	...contribute the goal of addressing eutrophication?
North Adriatic case	... contribute to managing conflicts between uses and to achieving a good status of water and marine environment in an area with many anthropic uses?
French Mediterranean case	... improving biodiversity conditions consideration within the marine governance setting?
OsloFjord case	...addressing the ecosystem deterioration of the Oslo Fjord

2.2.2 Vertical coherence

Within the CrossGov project, we understand vertical coherence as to how well policies are aligned between different governance levels. Assessing vertical coherence involves assessing whether national policies are coherent with specific EU Directives. It also involves assessment within the national context as after transposition into national legislation, vertical coherence challenges might be created, for example between municipal and national policies. Assessing vertical coherence may also involve assessing whether national policies are in line with the broader policy ambitions and objectives, such as those in the European Green Deal, or the more recent EU Oceans Pact, or international policies such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (D4.2, 2025)

The vertical coherence between the implementation of the WFD, MSFD and MSPD planning documents and the achievement of the EGD was addressed in Task 3.2 through the overarching question:

“To what extent does the resulting interplay between these three Directives’ national and local plans assists the reaching of the three EGD objectives of focus in CrossGov?”

Just as with the horizontal coherence, each case study developed its own set of case specific questions inspired by this overarching question targeting a specific EGD objective (see *Table 8*).

Table 8: The case-study specific research questions addressing vertical coherence with the EGD in a nutshell.

Whether and how the operational implementation of RBMP, MaS, and MSP are coherently contributing / considering measures to the delivery of the EU EGD objectives ...	
Finnish Archipelago case	...of zero pollution?
North Adriatic case	... of protection of marine biodiversity?
French Mediterranean case	... of protection of marine biodiversity?
OsloFjord case	...high-level Norwegian objectives of zero pollution, biodiversity, and climate change adaptation?
What needs to be done to enhance vertical coherence that would contribute to the delivery of the EU EGD objectives...	
Finnish Archipelago case	...of zero pollution?
North Adriatic case	... of marine biodiversity?
French Mediterranean case	... of marine biodiversity?
OsloFjord case	...high-level Norwegian objectives of zero pollution, biodiversity, and climate change adaptation?

The answers to these questions have been documented in the Step 3 reports for each of the case studies. See Annex 3 for the template of the Step 3 report. Although the Step 3 reports were meant to be for internal use, some of these are now available at the CrossGov website (see [Publications](#)).

2.3 Framework of analysis

Two frameworks of analysis were applied by case study leaders. The first one refers to the Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework (D1.3 rev. Feb 2024). The second refers to the Science Policy Society Interface assessment framework (D1.4 October 2023).

2.3.1 Policy coherence evaluation framework

The CrossGov policy coherence evaluation framework allows to understand where in the policy cycle (design and/or implementation) or at which governance level (EU, national, sub-national) problems or challenges of coherence emerge. This methodological approach is based on two components:

- Two coherence attributes (**objectives** and **policy instruments**) which are relevant for influencing the degree of coherence in policy design and implementation (see *Figure 4*).

Figure 4: The two coherence attributes and some examples of the guiding questions.

- Three explanatory variables (**governmental organizational structures, science-policy-society interfaces, and stakeholder involvement**) that help explain the extent of coherence (see *Figure 5*).

Figure 5: The three explanatory variables and some examples of the guiding questions.

- *Guiding questions* to support the assessment of why there is (in-) coherence; they provide a common structure for the evaluation of policies from different perspectives. The answers to these questions have been documented in the Step 2 reports for each of the case studies. See Annex 2 for the template of the Step 2 report. Although the Step 3 reports were meant to be for internal use, some of these are now available at the CrossGov website (see [Publications](#)).

Not all attributes and variables were equally relevant in all the case studies. Likewise, the case studies adjusted the guiding questions to make them more fit-for-purpose for their policy context, governance level, and case study focus.

For an updated version of assessment framework, based on the experiences from its implementation in WP3, please consult [D4.2 \(2025\) Handbook on Policy Coherence](#).

2.3.2 Science-Policy-Society Interface assessment framework

Science-policy-society interfaces (SPSI) are social processes which encompass relations between several actors in the policy process and which allow for exchanges, co-evolution, and joint construction of knowledge with the aim of enriching decision-making (D4.3, 2025).

The step-by-step operational procedure for SPSI analysis is structured in 4 steps¹² (*Figure 6*)

¹² Not to be confused with the “Step reports”

Figure 6: The step-by-step procedure for conducting SPSI analysis (source: D4,3, 2025)

The third step makes reference to Building Blocks. Six Building Blocks have been identified as the main constituent elements of SPSI that are potentially relevant to EGD-related marine legislation and policies (Figure 7). While all Blocks can in theory contribute to the analysis, the case study leaders selected the Blocks that were most relevant for them, depending on policies under analysis, geographical domain, relevance in the policy cycle, and research questions of main interest.

Figure 7: Building Blocks as part of CrossGov’s SPSI assessment framework (source: D4,3, 2025)

The SPSI framework is seen as the further elaboration of one of the explanatory variables of the Policy Coherence Framework; something that can help explain the lack of coherence. Both frameworks (the SPSI and the Coherence framework) have been aligned: in the Coherence framework, the guiding questions for the SPSI explanatory variable are the main questions of each building blocks in the SPSI framework.

The answers for each case study are included in the Step 2 template for the explanatory variable nr 2 (SPSI) and should be seen as a synthesis of the work on SPSI. The extended responses on

the SPSI analysis, collected by means of the Excel template¹³, were included in an annex of this Step 2 report, and as a narrative following a suggested structure (See Annex 2 for details).

For an updated version of assessment framework, based on the experiences from its implementation in WP3, please consult [D4.3 \(2025\) Blueprint for SPS](#).

3. The explored cases

The chapter is structured around the four case studies included in Task 3.2. Each case study begins with succinct contextual information outlining the geographic scope and the specific challenges addressed. This is followed by a description of the methodology applied, including a list of key documents and actors involved. The subsequent sub-sections present the results of the analysis on Horizontal and Vertical coherence. These sub-sections also include concise information on how the three Directives are implemented in the countries hosting the case studies. Key elements emphasized in these sections are: (i) elements supporting horizontal and vertical coherence, and (ii) potential strategies to enhance coherence, both in addressing the specific challenge explored in the case study and in contributing to the delivery of EGD objectives.

3.1 Finnish Archipelago: Eutrophication

The Finnish Archipelago case study examined eutrophication, primarily driven by diffuse sources of pollution such as agricultural runoff and forestry, but also from point source pollution (industry and urban wastewater discharges) and aquaculture (Laurila et al., 2022, pp 14). (Box 4).

The analysis of horizontal and vertical coherence examined, respectively, how interlinkages between national and local plans developed under the WFD, MSFD, and MSP frameworks contributed to an integrated approach for addressing eutrophication (horizontal coherence), and also, how the interlinkages between these plans supported the delivery of the EU Green Deal's zero pollution goal (vertical coherence). As mentioned in section 2.2, the specific questions explored in this case are listed in *Table 7* and *Table 8*.

The findings of this analysis are organized into sub-chapters that present elements supporting both horizontal and vertical coherence, as well as potential strategies to further enhance coherence.

¹³ The Excel file is to be considered a tool to gather and structure information on the analysis of building blocks. There is no need to submit the Excel pages. The important part is that case studies leaders use the information/knowledge gathered through the Excel file (or other means) to develop the narrative of the 4 SPSI-steps (and step 3 in particular) to be included in the annex.

Box 4: Geographic scope and challenges addressed in the Finnish Archipelago case study

Figure 8: Geographic scope of the Finnish Archipelago case study (source of the figure: authors).

According to the River Basin Management Plans (RBMP), the ecological status of the Archipelago Sea is less than good. Most of the water bodies have a moderate status, but some have a poor or even bad ecological status

The Archipelago Sea is a part of the Baltic Sea located southwest of Finland in the southernmost part of Finnish territorial waters. It consists of tens of thousands of islands. The Archipelago Sea lies between the Gulf of Bothnia, the Gulf of Finland and the Åland Islands (Figure 8). The sea area is shallow and fragmented, making it vulnerable to nutrient loads from anthropogenic sources. HELCOM has listed the Archipelago Sea as an Agricultural Hot Spot in the Baltic Sea, making it the only remaining Hot Spot in continental Finland (Bonsdorff et al., 1997; Leppäkoski et al., 1999; HELCOM, 1993; Westberg et al., 2022). The catchment basin consists of nine river basins that run through an agricultural area with clay soil.

The main challenge in the Archipelago Sea is eutrophication due to nutrient emissions of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P). Climate change is predicted to increase internal pressures and thus further increase eutrophication (Korpinen et al. 2018). In the Archipelago Sea, the largest contribution to the total nutrient load comes from agriculture (49% of N, 71% of P), followed by natural leaching (34% of N and 15% of P), point sources like aquaculture (fish farming) and urban wastewater treatment (UWWT) (10% of N and 5 % of P), forestry (1% of both N and P) and other sources such as dispersed settlements and rainwater (6-8% of N and P). To note also that the overall contribution of fish farming to the nutrient load from human activities is small (1-2%), but in the Archipelago Sea its contribution to P is about 8% (Fleming et al. 2023).

Thus, speaking of the Archipelago Sea maritime condition, the distinction must be made between point source pollution (which has somewhat declined) and diffuse non-point source pollution (which is the key problem seen from the point of view of eutrophication). For example, the non-point source pollution of P has not reduced on any sea area in 20 years (Laamanen et al., 2021, pp 14).

Although agriculture is the major source of nutrient pollution, there are several other sectors which cause eutrophication. For example, the MaS includes measures to reduce eutrophication for following sectors: UWWT, aquaculture, agriculture, industry, peat production, forestry, rural settlements, road transport, maritime transport, boating and stormwaters. Moreover, the sectors identified in the RBMP are urban and rural settlements, industry and mining, aquaculture, peat production, forestry, agriculture and acid sulphate soils, and hydraulic engineering. Therefore, industry, UWWT, rural settlements, agriculture, forestry, peat production and aquaculture are sectors which are both regulated by the MaS and RBMP in terms of nutrient discharges and eutrophication.

In terms of MSP, the plans basically concern the location of maritime activities. No indication exist that such allocation of space takes into account issues of existing nutrient load.

3.1.1 Methodology

The first step was to carry out a document analysis. Since the implementation happens at the national level, and the case study concerns the Archipelago Sea, national and regional level-policies were the most relevant to explore.

In this analysis, we focused on policies at the Archipelago Sea case study level. Firstly, this means the coherence of different water and marine policies, exemplified by the regional River Basin Management Plan (RBMP) and the Finnish Marine Strategy (MaS) and the Maritime Spatial Plan (MSP). The Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP) of the Helsinki Commission (HELCOM) under the 1974 Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area (Helsinki Convention) is a relevant policy document as well¹⁴. Second, the coherence between water policy and other key policy areas that contribute to nutrient loads is important. The analysis included cross-sectoral documents such as documents related to specific sectors of interest to this case study (aquaculture, agriculture, forestry, industry, urban wastewater). The analysis of policy documents took place between March – August 2023. (see Table 9).

Table 9: Documents analysed as part of the Finnish Archipelago case study and their relevance to the framework directives and/or sectors of interest to this case study.

	WFD	MSFD	MSPD	Sector (aquaculture, agriculture, forestry, industry, and UWWT)
Act on the Organisation of River Basin Management and the Marine Strategy (RBMS Act 1299/2004) ¹⁵	x	x		All sectors included.
Land Use and Building Act (LUB Act 132/1999)			x	Maritime sectors included; aquaculture.
River Basin management plan 2022–2027 for Kokemäenjoki – Archipelago Sea – Botnian Sea River- Basin area, part 1: Information by river basin district	x			All sectors
River Basin management plan 2022– 2027, Part 2: Methods and principles used in planning	x			All sectors
Finnish Marine Strategy part I : State of Finland’s marine environment 2018		x		All sectors
Finnish Marine Strategy part II: Monitoring Program for the period 2020– 2026		x		All sectors
Finnish Marine Strategy part III: Program of measures of the Finnish Marine Strategy 2022–2027		x		All sectors
Maritime spatial plan for Finland 2030			x	Maritime sectors, no land-based activities
Effectiveness programme of water protection (documents produced in the program)	x	x		All sectors
Water Resources Management Strategy of Finland 2030	x	x		All sectors

¹⁴ The BSAP is more closely scrutinized in the Baltic Sea case study document of Step 2, in which the EU strategy for the Baltic Sea Region (EUSBSR) is also considered

¹⁵ Laki vesienhoidon ja merenhoidon järjestämisestä 1299/2004.

	WFD	MSFD	MSPD	Sector (aquaculture, agriculture, forestry, industry, and UWWT)
Guidelines for environmental protection in fish farming, Publications of the Ministry of Environment 2020:22	x	x		Aquaculture
Finland's national CAP Strategic Plan 2023–2027	WFD mentioned			CAP, agriculture
Planning document for water management measures for 2022–2027: Agriculture, fur production and acidification control	x	x		Agriculture
Archipelago Sea Programme for Agriculture				Agriculture
Finland's Aquaculture Strategy	x	x		Aquaculture
The Finnish Bioeconomy Strategy	x	x		All sectors
Spatial planning of aquaculture	x	x	x	Aquaculture
Planning document for water management measures for 2022–2027: Municipalities, rural settlements and industry				
Planning document for water management measures for 2022–2027: Hydraulic engineering, regulation and restoration				
Planning document for water management measures for 2022–2027: Forestry				
Planning document for water management measures for 2022–2027: Peat Production				
Planning document for water management measures for 2022–2027: Aquaculture				
Regional level documents				
Programme of measures of the River Basin Management Plan 2022–2027 for Southwest Finland and Satakunta	x			All sectors
The Archipelago Sea Hot Spot Road Map Project: Road map of water protection in agriculture	x	x		Agriculture
The Archipelago Sea Hot Spot Road Map Project: bottlenecks of agricultural water protection	x	x		Agriculture

The document analysis was combined with information collected through stakeholder events (workshops) and semi-structured interviews. This process supported the co-creation approach with the stakeholders relevant to the Archipelago Sea case study. Some of these events are:

- 12 January 2023. Meeting with the Southwest Regional Authority (ELY Centre) on CrossGov cooperation possibilities.
- 10 October 2023. Participation in a panel discussion at the workshop on marine multi-use and marine spatial planning organised by the Regional Council of Southwest Finland.
- 22 January 2024. Presentation at the event “Cooperation and new opportunities to tackle the challenges of nutrient cycling and improve the status of the Archipelago Sea” organised by the Southwest Finland ELY Centre.
- In 2024. Numerous planning meetings with Finnish ministries and regional authorities to support a co-creative pilot project of the GOVAQUA Horizon Europe project on water stewardship in the food industry under the Archipelago Sea Program.
- 26 April 2024. Presentation “CrossGov Baltic Sea and Finnish pilots – from EU regulation to regional practice” at the BlueMissionBanos Arena 2_Policy Coherence

Workshop (Policy Coherence as a Platform for Better Integration of Marine Conservation in MSP and Sectoral Policies) in Riga.

In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted as part of the case study work in April 2023. The participants were contacted based on their expert status in marine governance and in policy sectors of agriculture, forestry, aquaculture. The list of institutions and other relevant stakeholders involved in data collection activities are registered in *Table 10*.

Table 10: Institutions and other relevant stakeholders involved in data collection activities for the Finnish Archipelago case study.

Organization	Relevance
Ministry of the Environment	WFD/MSFD/MSPD
HELCOM	International organization, MSFD implementation
Regional Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (Ely Centre), Finland Proper	Regional administration, WDF / MSFD
Regional State Administrative Agency, Finland Proper	Regional administration, environmental permitting related to the WFD/MSFD
The Regional Council of Southwest Finland	Regional administration, MSPD
The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners (MTK), Finland Proper	Advocacy group, WFD, MSFD, CAP
The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners (MTK), main office	Advocacy group, WFD, MSFD, CAP
Forest Centre	Regional administration, WFD, MSFD
Finnish Fish Farming Association	Advocacy group, WFD, MSFD, MSPD
Keep the Archipelago Tidy Association	NGO, WFD, MSFD
Archipelago Sea Fish Leader	Regional development, WFD, MSFD

The objectives, instruments, authorities and involved stakeholders of different sectors were analysed using the Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework and the Science-Policy-Society Interface assessment framework described in Section 2.3 of this report. The data was structured into the three sets of internal reports referred to as Step 1, Step 2, and Step 3.

3.1.2 Horizontal coherence

Within the context of the Finnish Archipelago, this case study examined the coherence between the planning processes associated to the three framework directives. This section begins with an overview of how these directives have been implemented in Finland (Box 5), followed by two subsections: (i) elements that support the coherent implementation of planning-related instruments linked to the three directives, and (ii) potential measures to further enhance this coherence.

Box 5: Marine management in the Finnish Archipelago: an overview

Finland is an EU Member State and therefore the Archipelago Sea is covered by the Water Framework Directive (WFD), the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directives (MSPD) and their respective planning systems. The geographical scope of the River Basin Management Plans (RBMP), the Marine Strategy (MaS) and the Maritime Spatial Plan (MSP) partly overlap in Finland, as they all cover coastal waters according to the Finnish legislation. In practice, the entire Archipelago Sea is covered by all these plans, as the large number of islands results in a wide coverage of coastal waters in the area

Introduction to the governance system

In the Archipelago Sea, eutrophication is addressed through multi-level and multi-actor governance system. First, there is EU water and marine policy, exemplified by the WFD, MSFD and MSPD. WFD and MSFD are mainly transposed into national law by the Act on the Organisation of River Basin Management and the Marine Strategy (RBMS Act 1299/2004). These policies state that good status (inland and marine waters) is to be achieved by 2027 at the latest. The MSPD is transposed by the Land Use and Building Act (LUB Act 132/1999)

Second, the governance of eutrophication involves other key policy areas that contribute to nutrient loads. These include agricultural, wastewater treatment and aquaculture policies in relation to the above-mentioned nutrient load contributions. At the Baltic Sea level, forestry policy is also important. These policy areas have their own governance systems such as the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the national CAP Strategic Plan and the Archipelago Sea Programme¹⁶ for Agriculture and Aquaculture Strategies.

Coherence of different processes, instruments and objectives, as well as compliant behaviour of actors would be required to tackle the issue of eutrophication in the Archipelago Sea. Ideally, the different sectors would be mutually supportive and work together to achieve the overall policy goals. However, different sectors may have different priorities, goals, and regulations, which can potentially create incoherences

The main actors are the Finnish Ministry of the Environment, the Southwest Finland Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (ELY Centre), which is responsible for the preparation of a RBMP and MaS in its area of operation (RBMS Act), the Regional Council of Southwest Finland, which is responsible for preparing the MSP in the Archipelago Sea (LUB Act), and the HELCOM. Water and marine policy also involve various stakeholders, such as municipalities and NGOs. Other actors are involved as well in the governance of eutrophication, such as the Finnish Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, and agricultural and aquaculture producers.

The key elements of the implementation of the three framework Directives in Finland in terms of the transposition law, the environmental goals to achieve, the geographical scope, and the authorities in charge can be seen in Table 11. Focus of the table is on the issue of marine eutrophication.

It is important to note that the spatial scales of the RBMP, MaS, and the MSP partly overlap as they all cover coastal waters. RBMPs and MaS overlap in the area of coastal waters. RBMPs cover inland waters and coastal waters up until one nautical mile (nm) from the baseline, while the MaS covers territorial waters, including coastal waters, and the exclusive economic zone (EEZ). The MaS covers coastal waters to the extent that the specific aspects of the status of the marine environment are not covered by the provisions on RBMP. The MSP covers territorial waters and exclusive economic zone (EEZ) In practice, all these plans cover the entire Archipelago Sea

Table 11: Key aspects of the implementation of the three framework Directives in Finland

		Transposition law	Environmental goals to achieve	Geographical scope	Authority	Sectors covered (eutrophication related)
WFD	RBMP and their PoM	Act on the Organisation of River Basin Management and the Marine Strategy (RBMS Act 1299/2004) ¹⁷	Good status of water bodies should have been achieved by 2015 (RBMS, section 21) The RBMP PoM defines the measures to be taken to achieve	According to the RBMS Act, the RBMPs cover coastal waters up to 1 nm on the seaward of the baseline. In practice, the entire Archipelago	The Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (ELY Centre) is responsible for the preparation of a RBMP and	Agriculture Forestry Wastewater

¹⁶ The Archipelago Sea Programme for agriculture aims to reduce phosphorus and nitrogen loads in the Sea so that the water body can be removed from the list of HELCOM hot spots by 2027

¹⁷ Laki vesienhoidon ja merenhoidon järjestämisestä 1299/2004.

			the water status objectives by 2027 at the latest (Westberg et al., 2022, 10)	Sea is covered due to the presence of various islands.	its PoM as well as the MaS and its PoM in its area of operation (Section 5)	
M S F D	MaS and its PoM		Good environmental status of the marine environment should have been achieved by 2020 (RBMS, section 26b) The MaS PoM identifies the measures to be taken to achieve good marine status by 2027 (Laamanen et al 2021)	The marine waters covered by the MaS include coastal waters and extend to the outermost extent of Finland’s EEZ (RBMS Act) The MaS covers coastal waters to the extent that the specific aspects of the status of the marine environment are not covered by the provisions on RBM (Section 2 of RBMS Act).	The RBMPs and the MaS are approved by the Government (RBMS Act, Sections 17 and 26 k). In the Archipelago Sea, the RBMP and MaS are prepared by the Southwest Finland ELY Centre	UWWT, aquaculture, agriculture, industry, peat production, forestry, rural settlements, road transport, maritime transport, boating and stormwaters
M S P D	MSP	Land Use and Building Act (LUB Act 132/1999).	The LUB Act aims to support the achievement of the good environmental status of the marine environment but does not provide a timeframe or clear measures for the achievement of this objective	The MSP covers both Finnish territorial waters and the EEZ (LUB Act).	The MSP is prepared and approved in cooperation between the regional councils (LUB Act). The Regional Council of Southwest Finland is responsible for the preparation of the MSP in the Archipelago Sea	Covers a wide range of water uses and their reconciliation, in particular energy, maritime transport, fisheries and aquaculture, tourism, recreation and marine environment protection

3.1.2.1 Elements assisting the coherence

We identified several elements that support the coherent implementation of the WFD, MSFD, and MSPD planning instruments in the Finnish Archipelago. These elements also promote an approach to coherent operational implementation of measures targeting eutrophication in the Finnish Archipelago Sea.

- ✓ **WFD and MSFD transposed into Finnish legislation in the same act.** This approach was selected for enabling a more integrated management and implementation across freshwater (rivers, lakes, groundwater) and marine environments (the Baltic Sea and archipelago areas) (Mancheva, et al., 2024; FI Ministry of the Environment, n.d). The main act (Act on the Organisation of River Basin Management and the Marine Strategy (1299/2004) sets the general framework, and it is supplemented by several government decrees that provide further detail and operational guidance.
- ✓ **ELY Centres: central role in freshwater management and key regional actor in marine strategy implementation:** The RBMPs and MaS are prepared in close cooperation in Finland. The RBMS Act stipulates that the relevant ELY centre must coordinate the work between the MaS and river basin management. The ELY Centres (Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment) are regional state authorities in Finland responsible for the preparation and implementation of RBMPs and their PoMs (Albrecht et al, 2025). Although the main responsibility for establishing the MSFD's MaS lies with the Ministry of Environment, the ELY Centres play a significant role in the implementation of the MaS and its PoM at the regional level.
- ✓ **Linking RBMP and MaS for marine nutrient reduction:** In the Finnish Archipelago context, the RBMP explicitly references the objectives of marine environment policy particularly by integrating the requirements of the MSFD into their objectives and measures. In turn, the MaS is required to consider the RBMP especially since land-based nutrient loads significantly affect marine waters.

A clear and intentional connection between the MaS and RBMP is evident in the inclusion of nutrient loading measures in the MaS, such as sea basin-specific nutrient input ceilings established under the HELCOM Baltic Sea Action Plan (HELCOM, n.d1; HELCOM n.d2). These marine measures are directly linked to land-based nutrient pollution controls outlined in the RBMPs, as achieving the marine nutrient reduction targets relies on coordinated reductions in land-based nutrient inputs, particularly from agriculture and wastewater sources.

- ✓ **Integrated coastal and marine monitoring:** The monitoring of the coastal waters conducted for the RBMP is integrated into the monitoring of the marine environment under the MSFD. Data collected for the RBMPs is used to inform marine status assessments and to ensure consistency between freshwater, coastal, and marine monitoring programs.

The Archipelago Sea's coastal monitoring network, initially set up for WFD and RBMP purposes, now functions as an integral part of the broader marine monitoring program. Data collected at these stations, including nutrient concentrations and phytoplankton, are used in the HELCOM Eutrophication Assessment. This assessment informs both national (MSFD) and international (HELCOM) marine status evaluations.

- ✓ **Aligned coastal-marine eutrophication indicators and objectives** The objective of achieving GES for nutrient loading is largely harmonized between the WFD and MSFD

in Finland. Both frameworks aim to reduce nutrient inputs and combat eutrophication with combined targets and measures in the Finnish Archipelago.

While the MaS notes difference in the management approaches for water and the marine environment (scope and spatial scale), it also confirms that the indicators and status class boundaries for assessing eutrophication are aligned

3.1.2.2 Potential ways to improve coherence

Identified actions that would strengthen the horizontal coherence among the planning instruments of the three framework directives in the Finnish Archipelago area are:

- **Exploit the role of MSP in the integration of environmental objectives into spatial decision-making for marine areas.** While the MaS emphasize the role of MSP in promoting the sustainable use of marine resources, balancing various uses, and supporting the objectives of marine environmental management, the MSP, although mentioning support for the GES objectives, does not elaborate on specific measures or collaborative mechanisms with MaS for achieving GES in the marine environment (Haapasaari and van Tatenhove (2022)).
- **Integrate land-based nutrient load data into site selection within the MSP processes:** There is minimal direct cross-referencing between RBMPs and MSP documents in the Finnish Archipelago context. Although MSP background documents mention inland water management objectives, these references are not detailed or operational.

In the Finnish Archipelago, marine spatial plans concerning the location of maritime activities do not explicitly indicate that land-based nutrient loads are considered in the allocation process. While the marine spatial plans may acknowledge the importance of nutrient reduction for marine environmental objectives, the direct integration of land-based nutrient load data into site selection or spatial allocation decisions is generally lacking. **Box 6** describes the situation on nutrient loads from agriculture vs aquaculture licencing requirements, which was considered as the main coherence challenge that was revealed in the Archipelago Sea case study.

Box 6: Coherence gap between agriculture payments and aquaculture regulation

The main coherence challenge that was revealed in the Archipelago Sea case study, was between the environmental payment scheme of agriculture and the environmental licensing of the aquaculture sector

The main coherence challenge that the interviewees pointed out was between the environmental payment scheme of agriculture and the environmental licensing of the aquaculture sector. It is the interviewees' view that because of the strict requirements for environmental licensing, although aquaculture has improved in terms of nutrient load to the Baltic Sea, the agricultural sector has done little or even increased its nutrient load.

To tackle this problem, policy coordination across sectors would be required, aiming at the management of the cumulative nutrient load to the Baltic Sea through improved coherence, technological development and nature-based solutions (NBS) (Puharinen, S.T., 2021). Consequently, incoherent policy goals, lack of effective

measures for the management of cumulative nutrient load, tightening permit requirements and a lack of clear strategy for the renewal of the aquaculture operators hinder the development of the entire aquaculture sector (Valve et al., 2019). Furthermore, further policy integration of environmental topics into the core of economic policies is needed.

The fish farming sector's impact on water quality and biodiversity depends on where the operation is located, and the technology used. Therefore, a location management plan for aquaculture and its efficient implementation is needed. At the level of policy goals, there are incoherences that have led to a situation in which it is unclear to the businesses, governmental authorities, NGOs and other societal actors which direction the sector should take. For example, investment in the aquaculture sector is encouraged by EU and national policies, and at the same time, both the EU and national water management objectives aim to achieve the good ecological status of waters. Meanwhile, water and marine environmental policies aim at an improved status of coastal and marine waters and the subsequent decrease in cumulative nutrient load from different sectors, including aquaculture. In line with the MSFD, the Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP) aims at a good ecological status in the Baltic marine environment. The incoherence of policy goals that do not offer clear pathways for the future development of the sector was previously identified (Soininen et al, 2019).

The National RBMP, MaS PoM and MSP consider following measures concerning the management of aquaculture: one of the measures identified in the MaS PoM and the RBPM, is to update the Aquaculture location management plan. The National aquaculture location management plan aims to reconcile the interests of environmental use and water protection, identifying suitable areas for aquaculture (Finnish Government, 2022a, pp 10). Further, the development and adoption of new aquaculture technology is one of the most essential tools for reducing the nutrient load from aquaculture. Construction of water recirculation plants is mentioned as a measure in RBMP.

To be noted, the area-specific development vision for the Archipelago under the MSP recognises that aquaculture has also grown its importance in the Area by 2030. According to the vision, aquaculture would continue to increase its importance in the Archipelago Sea. There is a need to increase fish farming, but the objective of increasing fish farming is still incoherent with environmental objectives of water management plans (Westberg et al, 2022, pp 48). The challenge of reconciling objectives has also been identified in the MaS PoM: it stresses the challenge of reconciling the aquaculture strategy and blue bioeconomy with the objectives of water and marine management objectives (Laamanen et al, 2021, pp 85).

3.1.3 Vertical coherence

The case study investigated whether the planning processes associated with the MSFD, WFD, and MSPD operate in cross-compliance to support of the delivery of the EGD zero pollution objective (see Box 7). This investigation focused through the lens of diffuse pollution (from agricultural runoff and forestry), but also on aquaculture, and point source pollution (from identifiable facilities or activities such as industry and urban wastewater discharges).

In Finland, the Environmental Protection Act (527/2014, as amended) could be considered as one of the key legislative instruments relevant to the EGD objective of zero pollution. This Act explicitly covers actions in Finland's land areas, inland waters, territorial waters, and exclusive economic zone, including the Finnish Archipelago, that may cause marine pollution. In terms of point source pollution and diffuse pollution, the Act imposes obligations on operators to prevent environmental damage and sets out notification and liability requirements for pollution incidents. The ambitions of the zero pollution objective under the EGD are further reinforced through the Helsinki Convention, a regional agreement specifically targeting the protection of the Baltic Sea from land-based sources of pollution.

Box 7: Key elements of the EGD related to zero pollution

- Ambition: Achieve a **toxic-free environment** by reducing pollution from all sources, including air, water, and soil.
- This ambition is operationalized primarily through the **Zero Pollution Action Plan**; other strategies are of support, including the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the 2030 Climate Target Plan, the EU Climate Change Adaptation Strategy, and the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy.
- Among the elements that specifically relate to the **marine environment** are: reduce chemical and nutrient run-off from agriculture and industry that affect coastal and marine waters, and support the transition to a circular economy to prevent plastics and other waste from entering marine ecosystems.

More information on the mapping exercise of the EGD's ocean-related objectives and targets, and the results from stakeholder interviews can be consulted in see [D1.1 \(2023\) Green Deal Objectives and Scenarios](#) and [D2.1 \(2024\) EU and international policy landscape](#)

The following subsections present case study findings that highlight both current as well as potential ways to enhance coherence among the three planning instruments in support of the zero pollution goals of the EGD.

Before addressing this, it is important to note that in Finland, the RBMPs and MaS are prepared through distinct, yet coordinated processes. RBMPs focus primarily on land-based sectors and pressures, such as agriculture, forestry, and wastewater, and are the main instrument for addressing land-based nutrient pollution. In contrast, MaS and MSPs focus on marine sectors, including maritime transport, offshore energy, and issues such as underwater noise, which are not covered by RBMP. Among these three planning processes, only the RBMP directly address land-based nutrient pollution. Meanwhile, the Finnish MSP is a strategic and non-binding plan; it does not have direct legal effect or binding power over permitting or land use decisions, but it provides guidance for regional planning and sectoral development.

3.1.3.1 Elements supporting the vertical cross-compliance with EGD

In addition to the elements that assist horizontal coherence (i.e. the role played by the ELY Centres in terms of the RBMP and MaS; the connections between the MaS and RBMP in terms of nutrient reduction; the integrated coastal and marine monitoring; and the aligned coastal-marine eutrophication indicators and objectives) we could site the following as additional key aspects that support the efforts in contributing to the achievement of the EGD's zero pollution goal.

- ✓ The RBMP and MaS PoM both consider measures for the **management of diffuse pollution** arising from agriculture and forestry. For example, increasing the vegetation coverage of fields is identified as one of the most important water protection measures for agriculture (Kipinä-Salokannel et al, 2022, pp 122-124). One of the essential measures in forestry against discharge of nutrients into water bodies is the protection strips for logging. The measure is included in both the RBPM and the Forest Programme for Southwest Finland 2021-2025 (Kipinä-Salokannel et al, 2022, pp 119). In addition, in terms of forestry management instruments, the RBPM outlines the need of development of intersectoral cooperation in water protection (Kipinä-Salokannel et al, 2022, pp 121). Shared use of water protection structures should be improved, as demonstrated by the establishment of shared surface water drainage fields and

wetlands. This could create synergies between agricultural and forestry water protection.

- ✓ In terms of **point source pollution**, nutrient loads from wastewater treatment facilities and industry are controlled through environmental permits, which set requirements for phosphorus, nitrogen, etc (Kipinä-Salokannel et al, 2022, pp 106). The RBPM states that treatment of wastewater should be further improved and expanded with particular attention to risk management. One of the key measures in the RBPM is the voluntary improvement of the removal of nutrients with the Green Deal Agreement on urban wastewater treatment.¹⁸
- ✓ **The MaS incorporates complementary measures** aimed at reducing eutrophication to meet marine environmental objectives in the Archipelago Sea. Specifically, it includes actions targeting nutrient loading, such as improving nutrient recycling, increasing plant cover on arable land, optimizing fertilizer use, promoting the use of buffer zones, and enhancing manure management, to address the primary sources of nutrient pollution and reduce agricultural runoff.
- ✓ **A range of programs and strategies have been developed to support the implementation** of river basin and marine management plans in addressing eutrophication in the Finnish Archipelago Sea. A key initiative is the water protection enhancement programme led by the Ministry of the Environment (EC, n.d). This programme has allocated significant funding to support effective water protection measures, foster collaboration among stakeholders, and ensure long-term continuity in water management. Complementary efforts, such as the Archipelago Sea Programme for Agriculture, specifically target diffuse agricultural pollution with measures like improved soil management, nutrient recycling, and increased use of soil conditioners, aiming to remove the Archipelago Sea from the HELCOM Hot Spot list by 2027 (FI Ministry of the Agriculture and Forestry (n.d.)). Finally, it has also been mentioned that enhancing nutrient load reduction effectiveness requires also developing new instruments and methods.¹⁹

3.1.3.2 Potential ways to improve the cross-compliance with EGD

The analysis also identifies key actions that would strengthen the vertical coherence among the planning instruments of the three framework directives, thereby supporting the effective implementation of the EGD zero pollution objective

- With regard to the zero-pollution objective and nutrient loading in the Finnish Archipelago, **greater integration** between different planning processes, such as water management, marine protection, and land use planning, can create opportunities to achieve these goals. Among the instruments and measures introduced by these different planning processes, which could serve as linking elements, are:
 - Land-based nutrient loading, primarily addressed through a multi-instrumental approach (i.e RBMPs, the Archipelago Sea Programme, and agri-environmental

¹⁸ The Green Deal Agreement on urban wastewater treatment, available [here](#).

¹⁹ River Basin management plan 2022-2027, Part 2: Methods and principles used in planning, pp. 142-143.

measures under the Common Agricultural Policy-CAP), assist in reducing these inputs, which is crucial for achieving the MSFD objective of good environmental status in the marine environment.

- The MaS include measures to address nutrient loading, such as the implementation of sea basin-specific nutrient reduction targets. These targets are based on the Maximum Allowable Inputs (MAI) established under the HELCOM Baltic Sea Action Plan, which set scientifically determined thresholds for annual nitrogen and phosphorus inputs to each sub-basin, including the Archipelago Sea (HELCOM, 2021a)
 - MSP on the other hand provides strategic guidance for the location of aquaculture and other marine activities, aiming to support the achievement of good environmental status objectives by identifying suitable areas and taking into account ecological values and sustainability considerations.
- Explore opportunities to **further strengthen the approach to managing diffuse sources**, particularly in agriculture, to complement the more stringent regulation of point source discharges (see Box 8)

Box 8: Regulatory approaches for point and diffuse source pollution in the Finnish Archipelago

Nutrient pollution in Finnish waters originates from both point and diffuse sources, each requiring distinct regulatory and policy approaches. While point source discharges are typically subject to strict environmental permitting, diffuse sources, particularly from agriculture, are addressed through a combination of legislation, strategic planning, and voluntary measures. A brief overview is provided below on how these two categories are managed within the frameworks of Finnish law and EU directives.

Point source

Discharges from point sources, such as wastewater treatment plants and industrial facilities are regulated through environmental permits. These permits set specific requirements for the reduction of substances like phosphorus and nitrogen among others, based on the sensitivity of the receiving waters and the risk of eutrophication (Kipinä-Salokannel et al, 2022 pp 106). The environmental objectives of the WFD, including the requirement to achieve good water status, are legally binding and must be considered in the permitting process.

Furthermore, according to the Finnish Environmental Protection Act (527/2014, Section 51) and the Water Act (587/2011, Chapter 3, Section 6), the RBMP and the MSFD's MaS must be taken into account when issuing environmental permits for activities causing point source pollution or physically affecting water resources such as industrial plants, wastewater treatment plants and fish farms.

That means that an inland, coastline or marine project that jeopardizes the achievement of the environmental objectives of water management cannot be granted a permit without an exemption stipulated in the WFD and the RBMS Act. (Finnish Supreme Administrative Court, (see e.g. case 2019:166), in line with the Weser ruling of the EUCJ (C-461/13)).

In terms of the MSFD's MaS, this has primarily influenced environmental objectives and planning, but has not resulted in concrete, legally binding changes to the permitting of point sources. The developed measures (PoM) are often implemented through existing sectoral policies and voluntary actions, rather than new, concrete legal controls over permitting of point source activities.

Diffuse sources

While point source regulation is robust, the main challenge for the Finnish Archipelago Sea is nutrient runoff from diffuse (non-point) sources, especially agriculture, which typically managed through a mix of statutory regulations and soft law instruments, rather than specific permit requirements

For example, both the RBMP and the MSFD's MaS include various measures to manage diffuse pollution from agriculture and forestry and reduce eutrophication (e.g. legislation and strategies, financial guidelines, increased information, and research).

It should be noted that under the Finnish Environmental Protection Act, animal housing facilities exceeding a certain size require an environmental permit. The permitting process also addresses the management and spreading of manure. However, other diffuse pollution sources are generally not subject to prior authorisation procedures.

The MSFD's MaS, like their approach to point sources, have not resulted in direct, enforceable legal measures targeting diffuse sources of pollution such as agricultural runoff. Instead, the regulation of these activities continues to rely on existing national legislation and sectoral policies. The MSFD's influence has primarily remained at the level of strategic guidance, planning, and target-setting, without introducing concrete legal obligations specific to diffuse sources.

- **Broader participation and secured funding:** The RBMP itself acknowledges that the implementation of multi-sectoral measures to reduce eutrophication has been negatively affected by their voluntary nature and reliance on cross-sectoral cooperation (see Box 9). It also emphasizes that, to ensure more effective implementation, the range of involved actors should be expanded, new active participants should be engaged, and sufficient funding should be secured for the planned measures (Westberg et al., 2022 pp 99).

Box 9: Governance and cooperation in eutrophication measures

Both the RBMP and the MSFD's PoMs engage a wide **range of stakeholders**, as the implementation of multi-sectoral measures to reduce eutrophication depends on the involvement of various actors, including operators, companies, NGOs, government agencies, regional authorities, municipalities, associations, research institutes and volunteers (Kipinä-Salokannel et al 2022 pp 141; Westberg et al, 2022, pp 99).

However, the measures outlined in these plans are legally binding only for the competent authority, and the different administrative sectors contribute to the implementation of PoM within the limits of their own budgets and mandates. Meanwhile, for other stakeholders, the implementation of measures across sectors **relies primarily on voluntary action and extensive cooperation among various actors** (Kipinä-Salokannel et al 2022 pp 141; Westberg et al, 2022, pp 99).

- The vertical coherence in question concerns in particular the **regulation and financing of agricultural water protection measures**. The complexity of the agricultural subsidy system has slowed down the implementation of the measures; for example, CAP-based targeting has been perceived as complex. A key challenge lies in the financing and subsidies of preventive measures, as well as in effectively targeting them to the most problematic areas. In addition, the project funding of measures has faced problems in engaging farmers and ensuring continuity (Laurila et al, 2021 pp 27, 30), (see Box 10).

Box 10: Challenges in agri-environmental policy in the Archipelago Sea Basin

Many of the current agricultural practices in the Archipelago Sea basin cause nutrient runoff, which decreases water quality and causes eutrophication.

The RBMP, the Archipelago Sea Hot Spot Road Map project, and our interviewees stated that the challenge lies in the financing and subsidies of the preventive measures and targeting them to the most problematic areas.

There are several reasons for this.

- First, the voluntary support scheme consisting of agri-environmental support and eco-schemes continues to be inefficient and expensive and provides low incentives for innovation. It does not allow the targeting of agri-environmental policies to the most vulnerable river basin areas or to the most efficient measures.
- Second, the management of nutrient loading and the sharing of related costs and benefits continue to be inefficient. Finland's agri-environmental scheme has typically overcompensated for conservation costs, providing implicit income support to farmers. This has resulted in high participation rates in the scheme compared to other EU member states, although the net benefits of participation are close to zero or even negative, and water protection measures in agricultural areas have been insufficient (Laukkanen, M. & Nauges, C. (2014).
- Third, Finland's scheme pays for management practices instead of paying for performance in reducing nutrient loading, which is costly, complicated and backward-looking (Shortle et al, 2021). In Finland, the aim has been to enrol as many farmers as possible in the programme.

In addition to funding challenges, there are problems with targeting. Water protection measures have not been sufficiently targeted to areas where they would bring the greatest benefits (Laurila et al, 2021 pp 25). The Archipelago Programme highlights the of upgraded environmental subsidies in the national CAP plans for the Archipelago Sea basin, despite the intensive agriculture in the area and the need to improve the state of the sea. Furthermore, one of the reasons for the low level of implementation of agricultural water protection measures is the lack of information among farmers in the Archipelago catchment area (Laurila et al, 2021 pp 26). As the measures are voluntary and operators are responsible for their implementation, information is essential

- On the basis of the bottlenecks (Box 11), the Archipelago Sea Program has developed a roadmap describing the most effective agricultural water protection measures in the region. This programme, developed with stakeholders, identifies 10 effective measures that still have gaps in their implementation or funding (Laurila et al, 2021 pp 2).

Box 11: Agricultural Bottlenecks in Nutrient Reduction Efforts

The HELCOM Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP) recognises that agriculture has significant nutrient reduction potential, as the diffuse sources have not achieved a significant reduction during a 20-year observation and that the diffuse nutrient emissions contribute to 35% of riverine input (HELCOM, 2021).

The Archipelago Sea Hot Spot Road Map project produced a separate document on the bottlenecks in agricultural water protection in the area (Laurila et al, 2021).

According to the project report, the main reason for the incoherence between water protection and agriculture is the low profitability of agriculture and the low level of subsidies for conservation measures. It is also stated in the RBMP that the challenge remains financing the measures and targeting them more precisely to the most problematic areas. The subsidies available for the measure are often insufficient. For example, this has been the case for subsidies for buffer zones. Hence, there has been a request for improvements in subsidies for individual effective measures (e.g., protection strips and collector plants). As identified in the bottleneck project, the complexity of the subsidy system has slowed down the implementation of the measures; funding for agricultural water protection measures originates from several sources, and CAP-based targeting has been perceived as complex.

An audit report by the National Audit Office of Finland (10/2024)²⁰ examined the effectiveness of financial instruments for water management. The financial instruments are CAP environmental payments (average of around 200-250 M€/year in Finland between 2015 and 2022) and water and marine management payments (average of around 26 M€/year). The report highlights some of the bottlenecks in the water management support system:

- Funding for water and marine management is not planned and monitored as a whole
- Cost-effectiveness has not been an important criterion in the selection, design and monitoring of measures.
- Lack of data for monitoring and evaluation of impacts has also hampered reporting and communication of results
- Targets for reducing nutrient pollution are not sufficient to achieve good coastal water status.

3.2 The North Adriatic case: Achieving a good status of the marine environment in an area with many anthropic uses

The North Adriatic case study focuses on the achievement of a good status of the marine environment in the Italian portion of the Northern Adriatic, an area characterized by many anthropic uses (Box 12).

The analysis of horizontal and vertical coherence examined, respectively, how interlinkages between national and local plans developed under the WFD, MSFD, and MSP frameworks contributed to an integrated approach for reaching good status in the marine environment (horizontal coherence), and also, how the interlinkage between these plans supported the delivery of the EGD's marine biodiversity goal (vertical coherence). As mentioned in section 2.2, the specific questions explored in this case are listed in *Table 7* and *Table 8*.

The findings of this analysis are organized into sub-chapters that present elements supporting both horizontal and vertical coherence, as well as potential strategies to further enhance coherence.

Box 12: Geographic scope and challenges addressed in the North Adriatic case study

Figure 9: Geographic scope of the Italian Northern Adriatic case study (source of the figure: Ministerial Decree n.237 of 25th September 2024, on the Approval of Maritime Spatial Plans).

The geographic scope of this case study is the Italian portion of the Northern Adriatic, extending from the Friuli Venezia Giulia to the Emilia Romagna regions. It includes the marine area between the Italian coastline and the delimitation of the continental shelf agreed with the facing countries of Slovenia and Croatia (Figure 9).

Due to the several biophysical, anthropic, and governance-related land-sea interactions relevant for the case study, the geographic scope extends to land (as represented by the yellow arrows in Figure 9) including the watersheds of some of the major Italian rivers.

²⁰ Tuloksellisuustarkastuskertomus. Vesien- ja merenhoidon ohjaus, rahoitus ja tuloksellisuus. Maatalouden ravinnekuormituksen vähentäminen. Valtiontalouden tarkastusviraston tarkastuskertomukset 10/2024. [Link](#)

The Adriatic Sea is a semi-enclosed basin characterized by increasing depths and geomorphological features that vary markedly along a north-south gradient. Its northern part is rather shallow (about 35 m), including the largest continental shelf area of the entire Mediterranean Sea. Deltas, lagoons, and wetlands characterize the dominant landscape of the coastal area. Some of the major Italian rivers flow into the Northern Adriatic Sea; from south to north: Po, Adige, Brenta, Piave, Isonzo. The supply of freshwater from these rivers strongly influences the Adriatic oceanographic characteristics (such as salinity and density) while conveyed nutrients make this area as one of the most productive in the Mediterranean.

The Italian sector of the Northern Adriatic Sea is characterized by high levels of maritime activity, leading to growing spatial constraints and intensified competition for marine resources. This area accommodates a wide range of uses, including fishing, aquaculture, tourism, port operations, maritime transport, recreational boating, and offshore gas extraction. Additional uses, such as offshore wind energy, may also be developed in the future

In addition, the Northern Adriatic is considered a climate change hot-spot. Climate and sea-level rise related risks include flooding, coastal erosion, prolonged anomalies of high sea temperature and saltwater intrusion into freshwater systems.

All these aspects call for an integrated management and planning of the considered area across the land-sea interface. Policy and planning integration is essential to ensure the proper and coherent management of such a complex system

3.2.1 Methodology

As part of the of co-creation and co-development of the case study, a workshop was held on the 29th of June 2023 during the CrossGov 2nd Consortium meeting. The workshop involved several key institutions responsible for implementing the WFD, MSFD and MSPD in the Italian Northern Adriatic.

The workshop proved highly valuable for gathering information about the case study and for co-creating its research questions. Key insights were collected on: (i) the various pressures affecting the North Adriatic area; (ii) the context and implementation of WFD through RBMPs by the River Po Basin District and the Eastern Alps Basin District; (iii) the MSFD implementation process in Italy, including examples of its integration with WFD and MSPD processes; and (iv) the implementation of MSPD in the Northern Adriatic Sea, with a focus on the roles and approaches of the Regional Administrations of the Northern Adriatic Sea (Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Veneto, and Emilia Romagna). In general, the discussion highlighted both the importance and the challenge of achieving integrated implementation of the three framework directives.

Building on this information, the analysis of policy documents was conducted between October 2023 and February 2024. A chain-referral approach was used to identify the relevant documents for inclusion in the analysis. The most relevant and important documents analysed are listed in Table 12.

Table 12: Documents analysed as part of the Northern Adriatic case study and their relevance to the framework directives and/or sectors of interest to this case study.

	WFD	MSFD	MSP	Fisheries	Aquaculture
Italian laws transposing WFD, MSFD and MSPD	x	x	x		
Italian guidelines providing common principles for the MSP plans (DPCM 1 December 2017)			x		
The MSP Plan approval Decree (n.237 of 2024) for the Adriatic maritime area (including: assessment, analysis of interactions between uses, analysis of impacts on the environment, strategic objectives, planning, monitoring mechanism).			x		
Management Plan (2021) of the Po River Basin District	x				
Management Plan (2021) of the Eastern Alps Basin District	x				
Management Plan (2021) of the Northern Apennines Basin District (secondary relevance)	x				
Management Plan (2021) of the Central Apennines Basin District (secondary relevance)	x				
Documents of the MSFD II cycle: (i) initial assessment (2018), (ii) GES and targets definition (2019) , (iii) monitoring programs (2021), (iv) programs of measures (2022)		x			
National Strategy for Biodiversity at 2030	x	x	x		
GFCM Recommendations, e.g. Multiannual management plan (2019) for sustainable fisheries in GSA 17 and 18 (GFCM/43/2019/5) and Multiannual management plan for small pelagic fisheries in the Adriatic Sea (2013) (Recommendation GFCM/37/2013/1).				x	
National Management Plans adopted by MASAF, e.g. on trawling (2011) and hydraulic dredges (2019)				x	
National Program funded by EMFAF 2021-2027				x	
National Strategic Aquaculture Plan 2021-2027					x
Technical guide for the Allocation of Zones for Aquaculture (2020)					x
Documents about AZA (Allocated Zones for Aquaculture) identifications in the three regions part of the case study					x

Semi-structured interviews with stakeholders were conducted between January – March 2024. The purpose of the interviews was to integrate, refine, and validate the findings from the document analysis. In addition, a questionnaire was designed and distributed in May 2024 to representatives of regional fishing and aquaculture sectoral policies. The aim was to gather more detailed information on, among others, plans regulating fishing activities and designating zones for aquaculture. The list of institutions and stakeholders involved in the data collection activities is reported in Table 13.

Table 13: Institutions and stakeholders involved in data collection activities for the Northern Adriatic case study

Organization	Relevance
Po River Basin District Authority	WFD (and links to MSFD and MSPD)
Eastern Alps Basin District Authority	WFD (and links to MSFD and MSPD)
Italian National Institute for Environmental Protection and Research	MSFD (and links to WFD and MSPD)

Organization	Relevance
Italian National Institute for Environmental Protection and Research	Biodiversity conservation
WWF Med and WWF Italy	MSP, biodiversity conservation, fishing
Emilia-Romagna Region	MSPD (and links to WFD and MSFD), fishing and aquaculture
Veneto Region	MSPD (and links to WFD and MSFD), fishing and aquaculture
Friuli-Venezia Giulia Region	MSPD (and links to WFD and MSFD), fishing and aquaculture

The analysis of the collected data was conducted using both the Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework (focusing on coherence attributes and explanatory variables), and the Science-Policy-Society Interface (SPSI) Assessment Framework (based on its building blocks), as described in Section 2.3 of this report. For the Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework, the analysis covered: (i) links among the planning documents implementing the three framework directives; (ii) interactions among the institutional mechanisms established for their implementation; (iii) perceptions of how stakeholder engagement processes function; and (iv) perspectives on how the directives contribute to biodiversity conservation and support sustainable fisheries and aquaculture. Regarding the SPSI Assessment Framework, the interviews addressed the key topics identified by the methodology for analysing the SPSI system: data and knowledge, assessments, knowledge transfer models, permanent SPSI platforms, competences, and funding and resources. The analysed data was organised into three internal reports, referred to as Step 1, Step 2, and Step 3.

3.2.2 Horizontal coherence

Within the context of the North Adriatic Sea, this case study examined the coherence between the planning processes associated to the three framework directives. This section begins with an overview of how these directives have been implemented in Italy (Box 13), followed by two subsections: (i) elements that support the coherent implementation of planning-related instruments linked to the three directives, and (ii) potential measures to further enhance this coherence.

The alignment between WFD and MSFD is particularly relevant for the Northern Adriatic Sea where major river inputs (e.g. from the Po and Adige) along with widespread non-point source pollution (including the extensive agriculture activity) significantly affect coastal and marine ecosystems. Moreover, this area supports a wide range of activities (i.e. fishing, aquaculture, tourism, port activities, maritime transport, recreational boating, offshore gas exploitation), and others might be developed in the future (such as offshore wind energy). The implementation of the MSPD aims to manage competition for space among these different uses of the sea and promote their synergies, while adopting an ecosystem-based approach for the management of marine activities. The MSPD aligns with the MSFD's objective of achieving a GES, aiming at ensuring that human activities do not exceed the marine ecosystem's carrying capacity. The MSP also takes into consideration land-sea interfaces, including the impacts of flooding, and potentially allowing for an integrated management of the coastal areas.

Box 13: Overview of the implementation of the three framework Directives in Italy

A progressive integration of these policies can be observed in *Figure 10*. This is still partial and should be further strengthened along the future cycles of implementation

Figure 10: WFD, MSFD and MSPD implementation processes in Italy through time

Water Framework Directive

At the national level, **Legislative Decree no. 152 of April 3, 2006**, containing Environmental Regulations, and subsequent amendments, transposed the Directive 2000/60/EC into Italian law. The Decree:

- Divided the national territory into **Hydrographic Districts**,
- Provided for the drafting of River Basin Management Plans²¹ for each District
- Assigned responsibilities to the **Hydrographic Basin District Authorities** (*Autorità di Bacino Distrettuale*) which are also tasked with preparing **Flood Risk Management Plan**, as required by Legislative decree 49/2010 implementing the Floods Directive (2007/60/EC)
- Set, for the first-time biological quality objectives, in addition to chemical ones, for surface waters, including marine waters

We signal that the implementation process of the WFD provided –this district level of planning in addition to the regional one, already present at the time of the adoption of WFD, as it will be explained next.

Management responsibilities are assigned to the **Hydrographic Basin District Authorities** which collaborate with the **Regional administrations**.

- The Hydrographic Basin District Authorities of relevance for this case study are the Po River Basin District, and the Eastern Alps Basin District Authorities; of secondary relevance are those of Northern Apennines, and the Central Apennines.
- The Relevant Regional authorities within this case study are the Regions of Emilia-Romagna, Veneto, and Friuli-Venezia Giulia

At the **district** level, and in relation to the **RBMP**

- For each of the **three implementation cycles** (2010-2015, 2015-2021 and 2021-2027) all competent Hydrographic Basin District Authorities adopted their respective RBMP, which was subsequently approved by a Decree of the President of the Council of Ministers (DPCM).
 - Of primary relevance for this case study are:

²¹ In Italian, the translation of River Basin Management Plans would be *Water Management Plan (Piani di Gestione delle Acque)*

- The 2021 RBMP of the Po River Basin District
- The 2021 RBMP of the Eastern Alps Basin District
- Of secondary relevance for this case study are:
 - The 2021 RBMP of the Northern Apennines Basin District
 - The 2021 RBMP of the Central Apennines Basin District

At the **regional** level, and in relation to the **Water Protection Plans**

- These plans had been in existence when the WFD entered into force.
- Within these plans the Regions define instruments for the protection and conservation of water resources in conformity with the objectives and intervention priorities established by the relevant Hydrographic District Basin Authorities in their respective RBMPs.
 - e.g. provisions for the protection and remediation of surface and groundwater bodies and the sustainable use of water, identifying measures for the qualitative and quantitative protection of water resources.
- In recent years, the Regions have initiated processes to revise and update these plans. Often, the content of these plans is either used to inform the RBMPs or is overlapping with it.
- To note that no Regional Water Protection Plan was analysed as part of this case study.

Other relevant governmental actors are:

- The Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security (**MASE**), with the scientific and technical support of **ISPRA** (*Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale*), defines the technical methodologies (standardization, inter-calibration, monitoring protocols, and classification systems) needed for the WFD implementation in Italy.
- The Regional Agencies for the Protection of the Environment (**ARPAs**), are responsible for the operational monitoring, assessment, and reporting of the status of water bodies within their respective regions, in accordance with the methodologies established at the national level.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive:

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) 2008/56/EC was transposed into Italian law through **Legislative Decree no. 190 of October 13, 2010**.

The phases, defined based on the model proposed by Directive 2008/56/EC, are:

- The **Initial Assessment** of marine waters' ecological status and anthropogenic impacts
- The definition of **Good Environmental Status (GES)**, based on 11 qualitative descriptors
- The establishment of **Environmental Targets** to achieve GES
- The implementation of nationally coordinated **Monitoring Programs** with regional execution, and
- The adoption of **Programmes of Measures (PoMs)** to attain and maintain GES, reviewed every six years

For the **first cycle of implementation** (2012-2018), Italy published the Initial Assessment Report in 2012, followed by the adoption of the following key legislative instruments:

- The Ministerial Decree of 17 October 2014 which established the requirements of GES and defined the Environmental Targets.
- The Ministerial Decree of 11 February 2015 which adopted the Monitoring Programme, and,
- The Prime Ministerial Decree of 10 October 2017 approving the PoM.

The **second implementation cycle**²² (2018-2024) focused on updating and integrating the actions identified during the first cycle. The Initial Assessment Report was published in 2018 and was followed by:

- The Ministerial Decree of 15 February 2019 which established the criteria for determining GES and defined Environmental Targets
- The Ministerial Decree of 2 February 2021 which approved the Monitoring Programme, and
- The Prime Ministerial Decree of 7 July 2022 approving the PoM

²² In 2017 the European Commission amended Annex III of the Framework Directive (Directive 2017/845/EU), updating the indicative lists of elements to be taken into account for the elaboration of strategies. Additionally, aiming to provide Member States with a standardized and as quantitative as possible approach allowing for an organic representation of the GES of marine waters, it repealed Decision EU 2010/477, replacing it with Decision EU 2017/848.

Competence for the implementation on the MSFD in Italy is assigned to **MASE** (the Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security).

- The different phases of the MSFD are coordinated by a **Technical Committee** established within MASE, with the involvement of relevant regional and local authorities and bodies.
- Following public consultation and consultation with the Unified Conference²³, decisions regarding the implementation steps of the MSFD are adopted through Ministerial Decrees.
- The **PoM** is adopted by Ministerial Decree of MASE in accordance with the procedures established by national legislation.
- Monitoring Programs have been implemented through specific agreements (adopted since 2014) between MASE and the ARPAs (Regional Agencies for the Protection of the Environment). Specifically, one ARPA for each designed sub-region under MSFD (Tyrrhenian, Ionian and Adriatic) is identified as leader representing all ARPAs in the sub-region. All ARPAs, commissioned by their respective Regional administration, also participate in the implementation of the Monitoring Programs.

Of relevance to this case study are the documents of the MSFD II cycle:

- The 2018 Initial assessment
- The 2019 GES and target definitions
- The 2021 Monitoring programs
- The 2022 Programs of Measures

Relevant governmental actors in the Italian implementation of the MSFD include:

- **MASE's Technical Committee**, composed of representatives from central and regional administrations, the Union of Italian Provinces (UPI), and the National Association of Italian Municipalities (ANCI). This committee oversees the various phases of MSFD implementation.
- **ISPRA** which provides scientific and technical support to MASE for the coordination of MSFD activities.
- The **ARPAs** identified as leaders for the coastal and marine sub-regions: Liguria for the West Mediterranean, Emilia-Romagna for the Adriatic Sea (the one of relevance for this case study), and Calabria for the Central Mediterranean and Ionian Sea.

Maritime Spatial Planning Directive

The MSPD 2014/89/EU was transposed into Italian legislation through **Legislative Decree no. 201/2016 of October 17, 2016**.

Under Article 6(2) of this decree, the "**Guidelines Containing Directions and Criteria for the Preparation of Maritime Spatial Plans**" were formally adopted through Decree of the President of the Council of Ministers (DPCM) No. 230 of December 1, 2017. These guidelines established harmonized principles to develop maritime spatial plans.

The Guidelines have identified the following three **maritime sub-regions aligned with the MSFD** (art. 4 of Directive 2008/56/EU):

- Western Mediterranean Sea
- Adriatic Sea
- Ionian Sea and Central Mediterranean Sea

The plans are carried out in six Phases, corresponding to as many Sections of the same Plans:

- Phase 1 - Initial state and ongoing and expected trends
- Phase 2 - Analysis of interaction between uses and impacts on environmental components
- Phase 3 - Vision and strategic objectives
- Phase 4 - Strategic-level planning
- Phase 5 - Methodology and indicators for monitoring and adapting the Plan

Phase 6 - Activities for consolidation, implementation, and updating of the Plan

The **Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport** (MIT) the competent authority responsible for MSP. The legislative decree 201/2016 also acknowledges that MSP competencies in Italy are shared between the central government and sub-national administrative bodies.

²³ The Unified Conference brings together the Ministry, the Regional administrations and the local administrations, i.e. provinces and municipalities.

Of relevance to this case study are:

- The Guidelines DPCM, of 1 December 2017, providing common principles for the MSP plans
- The MSP Plan (2024) for the Adriatic Sea.

Other relevant governmental actors are:

- The **Inter-Ministerial Coordination Table** for MSP, which drafted the 2017 Guidelines and ensures the MSP plans are consistent with these guidelines.
- A **Technical Committee**, coordinated by MIT, oversees the development of the MSP plans. This committee includes representatives from several ministries (Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry; the Ministry of Enterprises and Made in Italy; the Ministry of Culture; and the Ministry of Tourism) as well as the coastal regions.

3.2.2.1 Elements assisting the coherence

We identified several elements that support the coherent implementation of the WFD, MSFD, and MSPD planning-related instruments in the North Adriatic Sea. These elements also contribute to achieving GES in a region characterized by extensive human activities:

- ✓ **Complementarity WFD and MSFD objectives.** When the MSFD was transposed into Italian law in 2010, it established a complementary framework to the WFD by extending environmental protection objectives to marine waters. Additional objectives were introduced by the MSFD, such as the reduction of marine litter and the mitigation of underwater noise.

All the RBMP prepared by Italy's Basin District Authorities (the ones relevant in the area being Po, Eastern Alps, Northern Apennines, and Central Apennines) generally include references to the MSFD in sections addressing policy integration and coordination. This approach supports coherence between the WFD and MSFD, particularly regarding the management of transitional and coastal waters where the two Directives overlap.

For example, the Po District Authority, in its General Report of the RBMP (2021) defined objectives related to water quality, ecosystem protection, and environmental conservation. These objectives show alignment with several targets set under MSFD.

- ✓ **Alignment of WFD and MSFD Objectives: mainly regarding biodiversity, eutrophication, and chemical contamination.** The WFD's objectives of preserving wetlands, halting biodiversity loss, conserving native species, and controlling the spread of invasive species, are aligned with the targets set under MSFD's Descriptor 1 (**biodiversity**) and Descriptor 2 (**non-indigenous species**). These alignments are reflected in the RBMP and the MSFD's PoM which incorporate measures to protect habitats and native biodiversity while addressing the risks posed by invasive species.

Similarly, the WFD's objectives of reducing pollution from nitrates, organic substances, and phosphorus are closely aligned with the MSFD targets defined under Descriptor 5 on **eutrophication**. In the Italian context, MSFD D5 targets build upon and extend WFD requirements by addressing stricter standards for wastewater treatment and further reducing nutrient loads (nitrogen, phosphorus) from both point and diffuse sources entering marine environments via rivers and runoff. This alignment

is particularly significant in transitional waters (e.g. Po Delta, Venetian lagoons) and in coastal zones. All targets set in 2019 under the D5 of MSFD (T 5.1-5-5) are substantially consistent with the provisions of Legislative Decree 152/2006 (transposing the WFD) and its Annex 5 specifically.

Another element of synergy between WFD and MSFD in Italy is related to the shared focus on **chemical contamination**. The WFD's chemical status objectives align with MSFD Descriptor 8 (contaminants in marine waters). For instance, MSFD targets set under D8 aim to reduce contaminant concentrations exceeding WFD-derived Environmental Quality Standards (T8.1); address knowledge gaps on biological effects of chemical pollution (T8.2) and mitigate acute pollution events and their impacts (T8.3). In coastal and territorial waters, Italy applies WFD thresholds (Legislative Decree 152/2006) to achieve these targets, particularly relevant in areas where industrial and agricultural inputs drive contamination.

- ✓ **Integration of WFD and MSFD objectives within the MSP framework.** The MSP Adriatic Plan's Phase 3 (on vision and strategic objectives) acknowledges the RBMP and MSFD's PoM as key references, as documented in Annex I. Annex I, titled "Collection of the main guiding documents considered in the identification of strategic objectives," explicitly lists both the WFD and MSFD among the principal legislative and policy frameworks that informed the plan's development.

The guidelines establishing common principles for MSP in Italy (DPCM 1 December 2017) explicitly identify the ecosystem approach as the principal coordinating method between **MSP and MSFD**. The document states that, in the process of defining strategic objectives for MSP, coherence with the environmental objectives set out by the MSFD must be ensured. This ensures that MSP planning in Italy is aligned with broader EU environmental policy goals, particularly those aimed at achieving and maintaining GES of marine waters, as required by the MSFD. Among the strategic objectives of the MSP framework related to environmental protection, Objective OS_N|03 explicitly mandates the integration of spatially relevant measures from the MSFD's PoM into maritime planning measures.

In terms of coordinating methods between **MSP and WFD**, the guidelines Italy adopted on MSP (DPCM 1 December 2017) list WFD among the main sources of policies relevant for the development of maritime spatial planning, reinforcing the importance of integrating WFD in the definition of the maritime spatial plans vision and objectives.

- ✓ **Coordination of WFD, MSFD and MSP monitoring activities.** Monitoring activities for descriptors like **eutrophication** under the MSFD complement existing WFD programs in Italy. Operational monitoring under both directives is conducted by Regional Environmental Protection Agencies (ARPAs), though with differentiated sampling protocols and reporting frequencies. At the national scale, (the Italian National Institute for Environmental Protection and Research) ISPRA is the institution responsible for the management of both freshwater and marine data and information. Two are the data repositories: SINTAI (*Sistema Informativo Nazionale per la Tutela delle Acque Italiane*) for the management of information under WFD and SIC (*Sistema Informativo Centralizzato*) for the management and sharing of data under MSFD.

A relevant exchange of information between MSFD and MSP concerned the information gathered through EIONET²⁴ during the second MSFD cycle (2018-2024). This was used, among other sources, to inform the description of the environmental status and the analysis on the interaction between uses and impacts on environmental components (Adriatic MSP's Phase 2).

The MSP monitoring plan aims at integrating data from established national monitoring frameworks, including MSFD, WFD, and the H&BDs ones.

- ✓ **Coordination mechanisms for integrating MSFD, WFD, and MSP Governance.** Important examples of these mechanisms include: ISPRA, which coordinates technical and scientific support to the implementation of both MSFD and WFD, and ARPAs (Regional Environmental Protection Agencies), which are involved in the implementation of the monitoring plans of both policies.

The MSP Technical Committee, includes, among others, representatives from MASE²⁵, Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport (MIT), and regional administrations. It plays an important role in enhancing coordination among the different authorities and related policy domains (e.g. between MSP, MSFD and WFD). The Committee is also supported by a Scientific Team (including research centres and universities) for data, knowledge and methodological inputs and contribution to the Plan.

At the regional level, formal and informal working groups have been established to involve various departments responsible for MSFD and WFD implementation in the MSP process.

- ✓ **Knowledge brokers and boundary organizations.** Environmental agencies (such as ARPA and ISPRA), together with universities and research institutions, are increasingly acting not only as knowledge providers and policy advisors, but also as knowledge brokers²⁶ and boundary organizations²⁷. They actively participate in co-design and co-management processes, collaborating with stakeholders and policymakers. Importantly, these institutions operate across multiple policy frameworks, thereby potentially enhancing policy coherence and integration.

While collaborative models tend to prevail over linear ones, there are differences among policies. **MSPD** adopts intensively collaborative models (which is also in its nature). The most emblematic example is the role and composition of the Technical Committee, that, next to the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, elaborate the management plans. The Committee is composed by representatives of relevant Ministries and Regions. At Technical Committee meetings, representatives of other administrations may participate as observers whenever issues falling within their competence are

²⁴ The European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET) is a partnership network coordinated by the European Environment Agency (EEA) that connects national environmental bodies, thematic centers, and other institutions across Europe to collect, manage, and share environmental data and information.

²⁵ Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security.

²⁶ Intermediaries that facilitate the transfer and exchange of knowledge between producers (such as researchers) and users (such as policymakers or practitioners), supporting co-development and improving the innovative capacity of organizations (McGonigle et al, 2020)

²⁷ Entities or structures that operate at the interface between different communities (e.g., science and policy), helping to mediate, translate, and negotiate knowledge and interests across institutional boundaries (McGonigle et al, 2020).

discussed. Representatives of recognized associations and category representatives, as well as representatives of institutions and research bodies, may be invited to participate in committee meetings. This underlines the importance of the role played by the Scientific Pole CNR-IUAV-Corila in the preparation of the plans and as support to the MIT in the monitoring of their implementation. **MSFD** is widely collaborative due to the strong role played by "knowledge brokers" represented in this case by the national and regional environmental agencies. A relevant example is the role played by ISPRA, that provides support to the competent Ministry of the Environment, Safety, and Energy (MASE) for the revision of the technical-environmental content of the PoM. As also confirmed during interviews, **WFD** is more on linear models, maybe also because is very (more than other policies) projected towards concrete actions (i.e. the management actions of the RBMP to improve the quality of water bodies and water resources. In this case, the central actors are the Basin District Authorities, that design the management plan in their area of competence and ensure their implementation. Here ISPRA and ARPA give their contribution as part of the District working groups, that support the competent authorities in the design of the plans.

- ✓ **Science-Policy-Society Interface (SPSI) platforms.** They facilitate the exchange and use of knowledge across different policies and governance levels. These platforms are mainly composed of public administrations, agencies, research institutes, and academia. Besides facilitating knowledge transfer, these platforms also provide advice and offer technical and scientific support in the policymaking process.

Examples include, among others:

- **At national level:** the MSP Technical Committee and the national scientific pole (CORILA/CNR/IUAV), ISPRA and the regional environmental agencies (ARPAs),
- **At the Adriatic level:** ADRION technical groups, Technical Committees of the Hydrographic District Authorities and the Socio-Economic Observatory of Fisheries and Aquaculture

Furthermore, by promoting engagement and dialogue among stakeholders and those responsible for implementing various policies (e.g. WFD and MSFD Technical and Working Groups and the Italian MSP Technical Committee), these platforms can potentially foster greater policy coherence. Workshops and training initiatives, often developed within EU-funded and cross-border projects (e.g., MEDREGION and ADRION), also play a significant role. Notably, such projects frequently adopt a cross-policy or cross-sectoral approach, thereby enhancing capacity building and potentially contributing to coherence of policy implementation processes.

- ✓ **Coordination of MSP with terrestrial planning instruments:** The Adriatic MSP includes reference to terrestrial planning instruments, notably the Flood Risk Management Plans (FRMPs) adopted by the Basin District Authorities (also tasked with preparing the RBMP and implemented under Legislative Decree 49/2010).

Within the MSP strategic objectives for coastal defence, a specific objective (OS_DC|01) aims to promote the development, harmonization, and implementation of strategies and measures for coastal defence and erosion control. These strategies are outlined in the Flood Risk Management Plans at the River Basin District level, in

accordance with the Floods Directive (2007/60/EC), as well as in Coastal Plans and Integrated Coastal Zone Management Plans developed by various regions.

This coordination addresses issues such as coastal erosion, and through integrated policy approaches, aims to contribute to the efficient management of coastal flooding taking into consideration the best available climate scenarios and developing advanced solutions, e.g. nature-based solutions, in coordination and collaboration across regions.

3.2.2.2 Potential ways to improve coherence

Identified actions that would strengthen the horizontal coherence among the planning instruments of the three framework directives in the North Adriatic Sea area are:

- **Strengthening explicit links from PoM and the RBMP to MSP:** While the Adriatic MSP plan aims at contributing to the objectives of the RBMP and MSFD' PoM (see previous sub-section), the WFD and MSFD plans do not explicitly consider or aim at contributing to the MSP objectives or measures. Therefore, a stronger and more reciprocal alignment between MSFD's PoM and the RBMP with MSPD is recommended. This would help ensure that land-based actions under RBMP positively impact the marine environment and the maritime uses planned under MSP. Indeed, several MSP objectives (such as the planning of areas suitable for aquaculture activities, for the protection of coastal ecosystems, and for the support to blue economy sectors) could be compromised if they are not supported by a robust WFD basin plan. Similarly, concerning MSFD, there are some MSFD targets that can be directly related MSP elements, such as T6.1, which aims at limiting the impacts resulting from physical loss on biogenic substrates associated with the construction and/or installation of anthropogenic structures. The MSP has the potential to take these elements into account in an integrated manner.
- **Supporting temporal alignment for better integration across policies:** The MSFD and WFD both operate on 6-year cycles, but their implementation phases in Italy show a 2-year misalignment: the MSFD 2nd cycle runs from 2018–2024, while the WFD 3rd cycle covers 2021–2027. In addition, the MSP plans, adopted in 2024, follow a 10-year cycle, with the possibility of mid-term reviews.

A temporal alignment of the MSP policy cycles with the MSFD and WFD ones would improve their integration. Such alignment, for example potentially linked to the reporting phases under MSFD and WFD, as well as informing MSP plans with WFD and MSFD data, can have positive impacts on the consistent, coherent and more efficient implementation of the three policies (e.g. through better integrated objectives, measures and monitoring systems).

- **Strengthening structured coordination across all governance levels:** Despite the existence of high-level coordination mechanisms were synergies between MSFD, WFD, and MSP are enabled (see previous sub-section on technical committees) there is the need -as reported during the interviews, of further strengthening the cross-policy integration at all governance levels. This includes more effective involvement of institutions responsible for implementing these policies, from the national to the regional and local scale.

In this sense, the “Report: operational proposal for the start of the implementation and monitoring phase of the plans” (2024) launched with the adoption of the MSP plans in Italy, already offers the opportunity to develop such coordination. Among the actions to prioritize for the implementation of MSP, there are two in particular aimed at supporting a close and continuous inter-institutional dialogue to support the update and coherence of MSP implementation with other planning frameworks (e.g., among others, of the MSFD’s PoM and the update of the RBMP). In particular, the report envisages the creation of two technical working groups: a first one on land-sea interactions (bringing together representatives of the processes under MSP – WFD – Floods Directive – Port development – Spatial and landscape planning) and a second one on MSP – MSFD – Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (Protected Areas and Restoration) – Fisheries Policies.

- **Progressively developing an integrated land-sea stakeholder engagement process:** Stakeholder involvement related to the WFD, MSFD, and MSP has largely been implemented in silos, with each policy operating its own engagement processes. This risks limiting coherence and integration across the three frameworks.

The predominant form of stakeholder engagement remains formal public consultation, which is managed separately for each policy and does not always ensure effective, transparent, or inclusive engagement of all relevant stakeholders. These consultation processes emerged during our interviews as not always being sufficiently participatory, both in terms of type of engagement (mainly formal consultation) and timing (stakeholders are typically involved only after policy options have been defined, rather than during earlier stages of policy development).

Progressively aligning and integrating consultation processes across different policies can enhance coherence and strengthen stakeholder engagement mechanisms. This progressive alignment can serve as a foundation for developing an integrated stakeholder engagement process that supports the overall management of the sea in line with the Integrated Maritime Policy (IMP). A key objective should also be to ensure inclusive and effective participation throughout the entire policy cycle.

For instance, enhancing the establishment of stable multi-actor platforms and structured consultation mechanisms across policies and across actors, would enhance the provision of transdisciplinary knowledge to the monitoring and adaptation of the MSP Plans. This is something that the “*Report: operational proposal for the start of the implementation and monitoring phase of the plans*” (2024) supports as one on the actions to prioritise, by envisaging hearings held by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport on topics relevant to MSP, involving public administrations, associations and sector operators, research institutions and universities, and civil society organizations.

- **A well-conducted Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA)** can play a key role in improving coherence between policies and the planning instruments that stem from them. However, SEA processes are too often treated as formalities, with limited influence on actual planning decisions. Strengthening the quality and integration of SEA procedures could significantly enhance the consistency and sustainability of policies and planning implementation, e.g. in relation to MSP efforts.

- **A continuous system of funding** is needed to ensure stable human resources and to fund research and capacity building, also to approach the complex issue of coherent implementation of different policies. Strengthened technical competence is also needed to address some specific topics and knowledge gaps which are essential components of the coherent implementation of the three policies (e.g. GES, NBS, LSIs etc.). This requires not only ad hoc projects and initiatives to offer capacity-building activities and trainings to improve the competence framework of policymakers and scientists, but also more long-term institutional funds.
- **Reinforcing the research and analysis of Land-sea interactions (LSI)** and the understanding of the way these affect land and sea planning and management within the implementation of three directives can enhance horizontal coherence. Indeed, LSI can be seen as a common denominator linking the three policy and planning processes, i.e. from the watershed to the coastline, the onshore and offshore sea space. It is important to acquire in-depth knowledge on LSIs, their dynamics and functioning in order to manage them in an integrated manner.

3.2.3 Vertical coherence

The case study investigated whether the planning processes associated to the MSFD, WFD, and MSPD act in cross-compliance in support of the delivery of the EGD marine biodiversity objective (Box 14).

The National Biodiversity Strategy 2030²⁸ serves as Italy's primary connection to the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. This instrument, combined with the planning ones derived from the three framework directives creates a multi-layered governance framework that advances the EGD biodiversity goal.

Box 14: Key elements of the EGD related to marine biodiversity

- By 2030, 30% of EU seas must be designated as protected areas, with **10% under strict protection** (no extractive or industrial activities permitted)
- Legally binding targets to restore **20% of degraded marine ecosystems** (e.g., seagrass meadows, oyster beds) by 2030 and all ecosystems by 2050.
- Biodiversity considerations must be integrated into all EU policies, including fisheries, energy (e.g., offshore wind), and climate adaptation.

More information on the mapping exercise of the EGD's ocean-related objectives and targets, and the results from stakeholder interviews can be consulted in see [D1.1 \(2023\) Green Deal Objectives and Scenarios](#) and [D2.1 \(2024\) EU and international policy landscape](#)

This section begins by describing how planning instruments derived from the three framework directives support the operationalization of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, specifically in relation to marine biodiversity objectives in Italy (see Box 15). It is followed by two subsections: (i) elements that support vertical cross-compliance, and (ii) potential measures to enhance this cross-compliance.

²⁸ Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica. (2023). [Strategia Nazionale per la Biodiversità al 2030](#) [National Biodiversity Strategy 2030].

Box 15: EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (marine biodiversity objectives) through the lens of the three framework directives in Italy

Marine Strategy Framework Directive

The MSFD is a key contributor to the EGD on biodiversity, as its main objective of achieving a Good Environmental Status, is closely linked to biodiversity, while also aiming to address pressures on the marine environment such as habitat loss, overfishing, and pollution.

Italy's PoM for the second cycle of the MSFD (DPCM, 2022) includes both existing measures related to the management of marine protected areas (such as those implemented under the Habitats and Birds Directives for the Natura 2000 sites), and additional measures aimed at supporting the objectives of the Habitats and Birds Directives as well as the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. One example is a measure aiming to increase the coverage of marine protected areas to 20% of Italy's territorial waters (including both MPAs and Natura 2000 sites), as well as to strengthen management measures within these protected areas.

Water Framework Directive

The WFD, with its goal of ensuring the ecological health of coastal and transitional waters, complements the MSFD by addressing hydrological pressures and land-based pollution.

For instance, the RBMP of the Po District, in its 2021 General Report, includes a section explaining how the plan contributes to EGD objectives, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. Relevant measures mentioned include: the prevention and/or management of invasive species (e.g. water turtles in the Po Delta); the development of more stringent objectives and measures for water bodies affecting Natura 2000 sites; and the inclusion of a specific measure aimed at achieving the "Renaturation of the Po area".

In the other three RBMP explored in the study (Eastern Alps, Northern Apennines, and Central Apennines), although not explicitly referring to the contribution to the EGD objectives, a strong link between the WFD and the Habitat and Birds Directive can be seen. For example, in line with WFD requirements and specific EC Guidelines (most recently updated in 2022), all plans, including the one for the Po District, include a Register of Marine Protected Areas. This register lists areas granted a specific level of protection at the EU level, including Natura 2000 sites.

Maritime Spatial Planning Directive

The MSP aims at minimizing ecological harm through a coordination of human activities at sea.

The MSP for the Adriatic Sea addresses biodiversity protection and conservation, as well as related EGD in several ways: through strategic objectives, the designation of nature protection vocations for various planning units, priority zones for conservation and the implementation of measures at both national and regional levels.

Among the strategic objectives of the Adriatic MSP (MIT, 2024) that reference to the EGD objectives related to biodiversity, and which are relevant for both nature protection and nature restoration, there are:

- OS_SS|03 – “Contribute to the European Green Deal”,
- OS_N|02 – “Promote the extension of the protection of EU seas to 30%, with 10% under strict protection, by 2030”,
- OS_N|04 – “Integrate land-sea interaction aspects and integrated coastal zone management, with particular reference to environmental aspects”,
- OS_N|05 – “Take into account in the medium to long term the process and objectives of marine ecosystem restoration, as indicated in the proposal for a European Environmental Restoration Law”.

In addition, the Adriatic MSP (Chapter 6 – Phase 4) includes several national and regional measures addressing a wide range of nature protection and restoration issues (MIT, 2024). For example, one such measure aims to enhance knowledge about the distribution of habitats and species, including those identified as priorities in the EU Nature Restoration Regulation, in order to better inform MSP.

Other elements

Within the on-going process of implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy, other elements can be highlighted:

- Similarly to other countries, Italy aims to achieve the objective of protecting 30% of its marine area by 2030 not only through MPAs and Natura 2000 sites, but also by **establishing Other Effective Area-based Conservation Measures (OECMs)**. The improved alignment of MSFD, MSPD and Habitats & Birds Directives is essential both to contribute to this objective and to operationalize the OECM concept in practice.
- Concerning the goal of designing **10% of marine areas as strictly protected**, based on existing definitions and key documents (e.g. European Commission, 2022) different options are currently being considered. For example, there is ongoing debate about whether areas where certain forms of sustainable small-scale fisheries are permitted could be included within the 10% target. This issue is still under discussion, and at present, no sites in Italy are officially classified as strictly protected according to these criteria.
- Projects are being conducted (e.g. Marine Ecosystem Restoration -MER, funded through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (2021) by NextGeneration EU) to advance initiatives toward the goal of restoring **20% of marine and coastal areas. These initiatives include** passive restoration actions (e.g., installing buoys to prevent anchoring in vulnerable seagrass meadows), as well as active restoration of habitats such as seagrass (*Posidonia oceanica*, *Cymodocea nodosa*) and oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) beds (PNRR MER project)²⁹.

3.2.3.1 Elements supporting the vertical cross-compliance with the EGD

Findings from the case study highlight the following key aspects that could enhance the coherence of the planning instruments under the three framework directives, supporting the achievement of the EGD goals for marine biodiversity:

- ✓ **Cross-information** (exchange and integration of data across different monitoring frameworks) and cross-policies assessments play an important role in integrating biodiversity conservation into policy. ISPRA plays a central coordinating role in this process, collecting and synthesizing data provided by the regional environmental agencies (ARPAs) and coordinating information from the MSFD and WFD monitoring processes. This data is further integrated, e.g. with habitat-specific monitoring required under the Habitat Directive (e.g. corals and *Posidonia*). Another example is provided by the comprehensive environmental report that includes an assessment of the hydrosphere (Ispra, 2023), published every year by ISPRA. This report incorporates indicators from the WFD, MSFD and H&BD, establishing connections to the EGD.
- ✓ **Collaborative models of knowledge transfer** are prevalent in most of the policies considered, where knowledge production is closely integrated with policy-making processes. Environmental Agencies (e.g. ARPAs and ISPRA particularly for the MSFD), universities and research institutions (e.g. the Scientific Pole for the MSPD) are increasingly acting not only as knowledge providers or policy advisors, but also as knowledge brokers and boundary organizations. They play a key role in co-design and co-management collaborative process. Operating across multiple policies, these actors have the potential to enhance policy coherence.

²⁹ [PNRR MER Project](#) (Marine Ecosystem Restoration)

- ✓ Regarding **coordinating inter-institutional mechanisms**, one of the priority actions to be implemented as foreseen in the aforementioned “Report: operational proposal for the start of the implementation and monitoring phase of the plans” (2024) launched with the adoption of the MSP plans in Italy, concern the creation of a technical working group bringing together representatives of the processes under MSP – MSFD – Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (Protected Areas and Restoration) – Fisheries Policies. Among its objective, this group should aim at identify priority areas for environmental and/or marine resource conservation with the aim of expanding the network of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and/or Natura 2000 sites, as well as assessing the potential of Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures (OECMs) to achieve environmental protection objectives, in line with the provisions and instruments set out in the MSFD Directives (with particular reference to Measure 1 of Descriptor 1 in the updated MSFD PoM of 20/12/2021), the Natura 2000 framework, and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

3.2.3.2 Potential ways to improve the cross-compliance with the EGD

The analysis also identifies key actions that would strengthen the vertical coherence among the planning instruments of the three framework directives, thereby supporting the effective implementation of the EGD marine biodiversity objective.

- **Better acknowledgement** within RBMPs on the EGD objectives. This could be achieved by clearly communicating the implications and requirements of the EGD for the RBMP, also considering the local scale of application of some of their measures.
- **Reinforce the connection** between MSP and the process of identification and designation of **new protected areas**. This could for example imply more detailed planning in the next MSP cycle, to properly consider the progressive designation of new MPAs, Natura 2000 sites and OECMs. The action presented in the section above on the creation of working group can support the further development of this recommendation.
- A clearer and more harmonized definition of “**strictly protected**” and “**biodiversity restoration**” areas, as promoted by the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, could facilitate the effective integration of the EGD biodiversity objectives into Italy’s implementation of WFD, MSFD and MSPD policies and plans. Ongoing efforts at both the EU and national levels to define strict protection and biodiversity restoration targets, and to identify concrete areas at sea for strict protection and ecological restoration, will support a more coherent alignment of biodiversity objectives across these policy frameworks.
- There is the need for the regional authorities to **ensure the effective** management of Natura 2000 sites, which are often designed but not always effectively protected or managed through concrete measures. This is necessary for these sites to be counted towards the 30% target for protected areas under the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030.
- Facilitate that **reporting and assessments** are **temporally aligned between H&BDs, WFD, and MSFD**. Despite the system being centralized (ISPRA), some (spatial and temporal) misalignments affect the efficient integration of the data: the reporting under the Habitat Directive is carried out every 6 years, but with no correspondence to WFD

and MSFD. As each policy has its own timeline, not always best and most updated data are timely made available among policies and for the specific policy deadlines (e.g. the MSFD monitoring 2019-2024 was not available to inform the MSP process carried out in 2022, for which data from 2018 were used). An efficient and consistent alignment should be based on a continuous exchange of data and information, as well as regular updates on objectives and measures between the three policies (WFD, MSFD and MSPD) and the implementation process of the EU Biodiversity Strategy and the H&BDs.

- Relevant **knowledge gaps** are an important factor hampering the proper and effective protection of biodiversity, e.g. on nature-based solutions, non-indigenous species, restoration priorities and means etc. Further research on these aspects would benefit the formulation and implementation of policies related to biodiversity protection and restoration.

3.3 French Mediterranean: Improving biodiversity conditions within the local marine governance setting

The French Mediterranean case study focuses on the achievement of biodiversity protection objectives. France's marine governance remains centralised, despite some decentralisation since 1982. The case study explores how this centralised structure affects the integration of biodiversity protection into local marine governance actions (**Box 16**), and which leverages do regional and local stakeholder have to implement biodiversity measure and make planning document implementation coherent.

The analysis of horizontal and vertical coherence examined, respectively, What are the challenges brought about by the interaction of river basin management (WFD), marine spatial plans (MSPD) and MSFD strategies at the regional and local level (horizontal coherence), and also, how the interlinkage between these plans supported the delivery of the EU Green Deal's marine biodiversity goal (vertical coherence). A particular focus of analysis is the land-sea interface, therefore attention was given to the bottlenecks and solutions for ensuring an efficient coastal management in the French Mediterranean.

The findings of this analysis are organized into sub-chapters that present elements supporting both horizontal and vertical coherence, as well as potential strategies to further enhance coherence.

Box 16: Geographic scope and challenges addressed in the French Mediterranean case study

Figure 11: Geographic scope of the French Mediterranean case study (Poileton et al., 2015).

The geographic scope of this case study is the French portion of the Mediterranean Sea, in specific the Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur (PACA) and the island of Corsica. It includes: (1) the yellow landward zones: groups of coastal municipalities; and (2) the blue seaward zones: homogeneous RBMP (SDAGE) zones.

Although the Mediterranean Sea represents only 0.7% of the surface area of the oceans, it is one of the major reservoirs of marine and coastal biodiversity, with 28% of endemic species and 7.5% of the world's marine fauna and 18% of its marine flora (SPA/RAC, Biodiversity in the Mediterranean Sea, n.d.). Despite that, 20% of the fishes landed in the French ports still come from overfished stocks and 2% from collapsed stocks (Ifremer 2024).

The Mediterranean Sea waters evaporate faster than what the river can bring in terms of fresh water. Such unbalanced supply in water makes the Mediterranean Sea a territory very sensitive to climate change and pollution. Managing waters from the Rhône River (located in the Provence-Alpes-Côte-D'Azur region) is key to manage the French mediterranean sea.

France is a centralised country, particularly when it comes to managing the marine environment. The guidelines and strategies for the marine environment are decided at national level and implemented at the regional level. However, since 1982, certain administrative powers have been decentralised with the creation of regional authorities, in particular Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur and Corsica, which is studied in the case study. Nevertheless, the central government retains significant control over marine policy, especially regarding strategic decisions and regulatory frameworks

Building on this context, the case study examines the challenges arising from the interaction between river basin management plans (WFD), marine spatial planning (MSPD) and MSFD strategies at regional and local level, focusing on how the biodiversity protection objectives are incorporated into local marine governance actions

3.3.1 Methodology

A combination of document analysis and stakeholder events served to collect the empirical data for this case study work. Document analysis took place between July – April 2024. A chain-referral approach was used to identify the relevant documents to include in the analysis. The most relevant and important documents analysed are listed in Table 14. To complete document review, 14 interviews with relevant stakeholders were carried.

The document analysis and stakeholder interviews were combined with information collected through an online workshop on the 18th of April 2024 (French Med Workshop, 2024). The event gathered around 20 representatives from universities and public institutions. The topic covered was “*Ensuring consistent implementation of public policies relating to the protection and use of marine ecosystems*”. Three presentations from representatives of public institutions

were included, one on the topic of land-sea interface, a second one on the topic of marine policy processes at the marine protected area scale, and a third one on the articulation of the economic development with the biodiversity protection.

The presentations were followed by debates on two topics:

- “What constraints and/or opportunities does climate change present for strengthening the integration of marine environment management policies?” and,
- “Are the mechanisms for implementing the various marine environment management policies at local/territorial level (regulatory tools, support, training, financial instruments, etc.) consistent with each other? “.

Three group sessions followed on the topic of (1) how to improve the policy coherences at the local scale; (2) economic development and environmental protection: what are the conditions for decision-making in public financing, and (3) what knowledge (scientific, operational, local) is needed to improve the coherence of marine environment management policies?

Table 14: Documents analysed as part of the French Mediterranean case study and their relevance to the framework directives and/or sectors of interest to this case study.

	WFD	MSFD	MSP	Coastal territory (land management)	Natura 2000 and Birds Directives
River Basin Management Plan (SDAGE) of the Rhône-Méditerranée Hydrographic Basin	x				
River Basin Management Plan (SDAGE) of the Corsica's Hydrographic Basin	x				
Program of measure of the River Basin Management Plan (SDAGE) of the Rhône-Méditerranée Hydrographic Basin	x				
Program of measure of the River Basin Management Plan (SDAGE) of the Corsica's Hydrographic Basin	x				
Environmental impact assesment of the River Basin Management Plan (SDAGE) of the Rhône-Méditerranée Hydrographic Basin	x				
Environmental impact assesment of the River Basin Management Plan (SDAGE) of the Corsica's Hydrographic Basin	x				
Façade Strategic Document		x	x		
Program of measure of the Façade Strategic Document		x	x		
Environmental impact assessment of the Façade Strategic Document		x	x		
Strategic impact assessment of the Façade Strategic Document		x	x		
Corsica's sustainable development plan (land - management plan for Corsica)				x	
Provence-Alpes-Côte-d'Azur Region Regional plan for spatial planning, sustainable development and territorial equality (land-management plan for the Provence-Alpes-Côte-D'Azur Region)				x	
Environmental impact assessment of Corsica's sustainable development plan (land -management plan for Corsica)				x	
Environmental impact assessment of Provence-Alpes-Côte-d'Azur Region Regional plan for spatial planning, sustainable development and			x	x	

	WFD	MSFD	MSP	Coastal territory (land management)	Natura 2000 and Birds Directives
territorial equality (land-management plan for the Provence-Alpes-Côte-D'Azur Region)					
Schema de coherence territoriale (scot) provence mediterranee chapter individualised as a sea development scheme			x	x	
Deliberate opinion of the Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur regional mission of environmental authority on the revised Provence Méditerranée territorial coherence scheme (SCoT)			x	x	
Impact assessment guide for offshore projects			x		
Management Plan National Parc of Port-Cros	x	x			x
Management Plan Marine Protected Area Cote Agathoise	x	x			x

Between December 2023 and April 2024 semi-structured interviews took place with local stakeholders, representatives from the local and regional authorities, as well with researchers specialised in French Marine Spatial Planning and Land-Sea interactions. The list of institutions and other relevant stakeholders involved in data collection activities are registered in Table 15.

Table 15: Institutions and stakeholders involved in data collection activities for the French Mediterranean case study

Organization	Relevance
Water Agency Rhône-Mediterranean (AERMC) -2 interviews	WFD, MSFD
French Biodiversity Office	MSFD, MSPD, Natura 2000, fishing
Provence-Alpes-Côte-D'Azur Region	MSFD, fisheries, Natura 2000
Corsica regional assembly	MSFD, MSPD, WFD, Natura 2000
Façade Maritime Council	MSPD,
University of Nantes	MSPD, fisheries
University of Montpellier	MSPD
Regional directorate for the environment, planning and housing (DREAL)	MSFD, MSPD
France Nature Environnement (NGO)	MSFD, MSPD, WFD, Natura 2000
Centre d'études et d'expertise sur les risques, l'environnement, la mobilité et l'aménagement (CEREMA)	MSFD, MSPD,
Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer (IFREMER)	MSFD, MSPD, WFD

The analysis of the collected data was carried out using two frameworks: the Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework, which includes coherence attributes and explanatory variables, and the Science-Policy-Society Interface (SPSI) Assessment Framework, based on its defined building blocks as described in Section 2.3 of this report. For the Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework, the analysis focused on the following topics: (i) links among the planning documents implementing the three framework directives, (ii) interactions among the institutional mechanisms established for implementing the three directives, (iii) perceived effectiveness of stakeholder engagement processes, and (iv) perspectives on how the framework directives contribute to biodiversity conditions within MSP processes. Regarding the SPSI Assessment Framework, the interviews addressed the key components identified by the methodology for analysing the SPSI system: data and knowledge, assessments, knowledge

transfer models, permanent SPSP platforms, competences, and funding and resources. The analysed data was organized into the three internal reports referred to as Step 1, Step 2, and Step 3.

3.3.2 Horizontal coherence

In the context of the French Mediterranean, this case study explores the coherence between the planning processes associated with the three framework directives, and how this coherence contributes to improving biodiversity conditions within the local marine governance framework. This section begins with an overview of marine management in the French Mediterranean (**Box 17**), followed by two subsections: (i) elements that support the coherent implementation of planning-related instruments linked to the three directives, and (ii) potential measures to further enhance this coherence.

Box 17: Marine management in the French Mediterranean: an overview

France's National Sea and Coast Strategy (*Stratégie Nationale de la mer et du littoral* -SNML) outlines the national framework for marine protection and integrated management. Some regional adaptations capture the specificities of regional marine ecosystems, watersheds, and economic stakes, but always within the boundaries set by national policies and strategies.

- The MSFD and MSPD are implemented through the *Document Stratégique de Façade* (DSF) - Façade Strategic Document (DSF) and developed under the SNML what is unique in Europe.
- The WFD is transposed at the Hydrographic basin level through the *Schéma Directeur d'Aménagement et de Gestion des Eaux* - SDAGE (RBMP)

On paper, marine environment management policies objectives are the same throughout France.

In addition to these two documents, other policies and planning documents have an impact on the marine environment:

- The land-related document (SRADDET) which allow coastal municipalities to develop a sea development schemes (*Schémas de Mise en Valeur de la Mer* -SMVM). This SMVM has a strategic importance because it is anterior to the MSPD (early 2000's). This overlap helps explain why the MSPD is included in the same strategic document than the MSFD
- Biodiversity protection document such as the Natura2000 management plans (applying Nature Directives)
- Local French Mediterranean planning documents such as new management tools for pollution and restoration (the so-called STERE and Bay contracts).

The relationship between land-related documents, sea-related documents, and inland-water documents is graphically represented in Figure 12

Figure 12: Implementation WFD, MSFD and MSPD within the land, freshwater, and marine policies in France Adapted from Abregal (2021)

Actors

In addition, management of the marine environment in the French Mediterranean, particularly within the Public Maritime Domain that extends from the coastline to 12 nm, involves a wide variety of actors at the regional level (Figure 13). These include:

- The *Maritime Prefect*, which represents the State's authority at sea, responsible for decision taken after 12 nm,
- State departments such as the *Interregional Directorate for Maritime Affairs* (DIRM) coordinating the *Document Stratégique Façade*, and the *Regional Directorate for the Environment, Planning and Housing* (DREAL),
- The Region, involved in implementing the European Maritime, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)
- State operators such as the Water Agency (*Agence de l'Eau Rhône-Méditerranée-Corse*. AERMC) implementing the SDAGE (RBMP) and managing most of the Façade Strategic Document funding.
- The *French Biodiversity Office* (OFB) managing the MPA strategies as well as most of the biodiversity protection projects.

For sectoral policies, there are also committees such as those for fisheries (*FranceAgriMer* and the National Committee for Marine Fisheries and Marine Aquaculture, CNDPMEM).

Finally, many private stakeholders and environmental NGOs are also active in the French Mediterranean Sea, i.e., France Nature environment (FNE) and the World Wild Fund-Mediterranean (WWF).

3.3.1.1 Elements assisting the coherence

We identified several elements that support the coherent implementation of the WFD, MSFD, and MSPD planning instruments in the French Mediterranean. These elements also promote an approach to improving biodiversity conditions within the marine governance framework.

- ✓ **A single strategic framework aligning the requirements of MSFD and MSP.** The Façade Strategic Document serves as the main regional planning instrument that integrates the objectives of both the MSFD and the MSPD³⁰. This document aims to ensure coherence between biodiversity protection measures and economic development.
- ✓ **Coordinated WFD and MSFD monitoring:** Historically, MSFD perimeter was established to cover what was not already covered by WFD (beyond coastal area and eutrophication and pollution issues). In the French Mediterranean, certain monitoring activities established under the WFD, such as those collecting data on physicochemical parameters, phytoplankton, and coastal benthic habitats, are also used to support the

³⁰ To facilitate the readers' comprehension, the acronyms "(MSFD+MSPD)" will be added when referring to the Façade Strategic Document as this integrates the requirements of both the MSFD and the MSPD.

implementation of the MSFD. The Water Agency (responsible for the WFD) monitoring these ecosystems, then shares reports to support the MSFD implementation and reporting.

Monitoring systems and indicators are built by national scientific institutions (IFREMER, SHOM etc.). Indicators and thresholds are defined at a national level and it sometimes makes it impossible to apply some requirements that were built taking into consideration the reality of one territory (e.g. Brittany) and to implement it in another territory (Mediterranean Sea)³¹. A more important role could be given to regional universities when setting up the indicators

- ✓ **Measures defined taking into consideration environmental and economic interactions** These measures are included in the annexes of the Façade Strategic Document (MSFD + MSPD), which specify environmental, socio-economic, and operational objectives. In addition, “vocation area maps” (*cartes de vocation*), also part of the Façade, and representing the intended uses of maritime zones, help guide strategic decision about balancing sectoral interests with ecological limits and helping to monitor potential interactions between environmental state and economic objectives.
- ✓ **Mandated coherence between the Façade (MSFD+MSPD) measures to SDAGE (RBMP) objectives:** The two main planning documents: the Façade Strategic Document (MSFD+MSPD) and the SDAGE (RBMP) share objectives including GES, biodiversity protection, and pollution reduction. French law mandates coherence between these two documents regarding their objectives and program of measures. Façade’s annex specifically indicate how its measures contribute to SDAGE’s objectives
- ✓ **Consultative governance of the French Mediterranean coast:** To support synergies in the operational implementation of the WFD, the MSFD, and the MSPD, as well as to address broader Mediterranean maritime issues, France has established the *Maritime Façade Council* CMF. This consultative body brings together over 50 different actors including state representatives, state services at sea and inland, freshwater representatives, university experts, work union representatives, and NGOs. The CMF meets twice a year to discuss and provide recommendations on strategic orientations for the Mediterranean Sea, while more targeted work is undertaken by specialized technical committees focusing on topics such as MPAs, marine renewable energy, and maritime employment. The CMF’s role is to facilitate dialogue and expose both environmental and economic challenges in the Mediterranean, contributing recommendations to the French Ministry of Environment, which retains the authority to adopt and implement measures and solutions.
- ✓ **Multidisciplinary expertise in freshwater and marine domains among civil servants:** French public services are often confronted with administrative complexity and resource constraints, which can hamper the efficient implementation of operational mechanisms, particularly in the environmental and marine sectors. Besides, civil servants are specialised in their own domain of activities (fresh water in the water agency, marine water in the marine-related services). Each Water agency has (since 2012) a **service or an expert dedicated** to marine coastal areas (2-3 person). One point

³¹ Interview with an expert of the Water Agency Rhône-Méditerranée-Corse

underlined by many experts in France is that if the Water Agency from the Mediterranean coast has achieved positive impacts and projects on the Mediterranean Sea, partly because it has created a marine service and integrated deeply qualified marine environment experts into its teams, providing strategic advice and active involvement. Besides, the involvement of Water Agency supports the land-to-sea continuum. A French-water **coastal committee** has been created for coastal municipalities to support the specific implementation of freshwater measures impacting the marine environment.

3.3.1.2 Potential ways to improve coherence

Based on findings from desk research, interviews, workshops, and other research activities, the following recommendation has been highlighted to strengthen horizontal coherence among the planning instruments of the three framework directives, and to support improvements in biodiversity conditions within the marine governance framework in the French Mediterranean

- **Synergistic implementation through alignment in temporal cycles.** The current staggered development of the plans in the French Mediterranean risks creating policy gaps that could undermine a coherent approach. For example, the strategic cycles the MSFD (6-year reporting) and MSPD (10-year revisions) are not fully aligned with the SDAGE cycle (the six-year WFD planning cycle for river basins). In addition, even internally, the institutions have different cycles. For example, the internal strategic cycles of the Water Agencies (multi-year planning and operational frameworks that guide their activities, funding, and priorities) are not aligned with the SDAGE cycle (the six-year official planning and management cycle for river basins under the WFD) (see Table 16). This misalignment could fragment monitoring systems, duplicate stakeholder consultations, and create conflicting priorities in funding allocations.

Table 16 : Planning documents and institutional cycles from 2020 to 2027

	SDAGE (RBMP)		Façade Strategic Document (MSFD+MSPD)	PADDUC (Corsica land management)	SRADDET (Provence-Alpes-Côte-d'Azur land management)
Institution	SDAGE cycles	Water Agency cycles	DIRM	Corsica's assembly	PACA regional council
Adoption of 1 st plan	2010–2015	2013–2018	2012–2018	2015	2020
Adoption 2 nd plan	2016–2021	2019–2024	2018–2024		
Adoption 3 rd plan	2022–2027	2024–2029	2024–2030		

- **A clearer coordination mechanism with one existent institution clearly having a full coordination role for inter-agency alignment.** Multiple institutions are involved in managing the French Mediterranean maritime public domain (up to 12 nm), each according to their area of expertise (e.g. fresh water, marine water, pollution, biodiversity), their relationship with the State (e.g. representation of regional authorities, allocation of funding) and the specific plans they implement (MSFD, WFD,

MSPD, H&BD etc.). The more foundational problem improving marine biodiversity within the marine governance setting is the high number of interlocking and interrelated policy documents and strategies (up to eight at the local level) and institutions involved (eight to nine state representatives). An example can be seen in *Figure 14*.

Figure 14 Schematic representation of the planning documents applicable in the Narbonne Area (54,000 inhabitants) within the MPA Côte Agathoise. Adapted from Blouet, 2024; (French Med Workshop, 2024)

This complex division of competencies leads to overlapping responsibilities and coordination difficulties. In addition, the distribution of funding responsibilities among French institutions is unclear and often fragmented across various actors, including State departments, regional administrations, and sectoral committees (see for example Box 18).

Box 18: An example of overlapping funding responsibilities for biodiversity

The geographical distribution of institutional competencies can lead to competition between actors over certain responsibilities, particularly in the restoration and protection of emblematic ecosystems such as corals and Posidonia meadows. These restoration and protection responsibilities are shared between the Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea (DIRM) and the French Biodiversity Office (OFB) through the Façade

Strategic Document (MSFD+MSPD) and the Water Agency (AERMC) which focuses on the good status of coastal species within the 1nm.³²

This situation has systemic repercussions. For instance, policy instruments can lead to tensions and incomprehension, as seen in overlapping funding responsibilities for biodiversity. The Water Agency (AERMC), responsible for the WFD and managing areas from the coast to 1nm, shares a "biodiversity" budget with the Mediterranean branch of the French biodiversity Office (OFB), which is officially tasked with biodiversity protection. However, if one of these two institutions uses this budget to restore Posidonia meadows, a task within its mandate, the other (Water agency AERMC) should not use the same budget for the same purpose, even though it also has jurisdiction³³. This overlap creates confusion and can lead to inefficiencies in implementation.

Since both institutions work on the same topic (such as mooring strategies), there is significant overlap, which several interviewees in this case study identified as problematic. This situation is specific to the Mediterranean façade where the Water Agency (AERMC) plays a strong role in marine environmental management. Such overlap does not occur in other Façades³⁴.

Options for addressing the overlapping responsibilities and coordination challenges include for example strengthening the authority of one existing agency to act as a central coordinating body enabling the implementation of strong coordination mechanisms between institutions. This could be complemented by measures such as harmonizing reporting requirements and establishing a unified environmental monitoring platform to improve data integration, entailing the alignment of objectives, measures, and biodiversity-related indicators. In addition, clarifying the distribution of funding responsibilities among competent authorities would enhance effectiveness by enabling a single point of contact to address sectoral policy issues, such as environmentally harmful subsidies. Ultimately, this means understanding which issues should be prioritised: economic development or biodiversity, and determining who is in charge of this responsibility³⁵

- **Shared data platforms for the integration of WFD and MSFD indicators:** It is important to note also that while progress has made in harmonizing monitoring systems through the Façade Strategic Document (see previous section), full indicator alignment remains constrained among other by distinct assessment methodologies. The lack of alignment between WFD and MSFD indicators can lead to create irrelevant decision-making (especially on the fresh-marine water indicators)³⁶. Common indicators are in development since 2014 but local authorities have underlined the inconsistency of these indicators that can create irrelevant decision-making.³⁷ Such misalignment between directives makes it difficult to implement projects locally, as the same data may support one directive's indicators but not the other's (French Med Workshop, 2024). Efforts is currently ongoing to align these indicators for the next MSFD cycle.

Cross-fertilization of knowledge is now supported by a new platform created in October 2024 that compiles data for both directives (MSFD and WFD).

³² Interview with a marine environment project manager in a state environmental administration

³³ Interview with a marine environment project manager in a state environmental administration

³⁴ Interview with Prof. In Marine Spatial Planning and geography; March 2024

³⁵ French Med Workshop, 2024

³⁶ Interview with a scientific expert of an NGO specialised in the land-sea interface

³⁷ Webinar, 23rd of January 2023, *Tuesdays at Sea debate: How do we define and achieve good environmental status at sea?*, National Commission of public debate.

- **Structured feedback channels for incorporating local input into national strategies:** The main fundamental problem (in the French Mediterranean context) in the interrelationship between the MSFD, the MSPD and the WFD is not at the national and regional level, but rather at the local level³⁸. One of the main variables to consider when looking at the sea management in France is that the sea is a “matter of the state” (quoted in several of the interviews³⁹) and that the Façade Strategic Document (MSFD+MSPD) orientation are decided at a national scale with few considerations of local specificities and obligations which can create frustration and incoherences with the regional stakes⁴⁰

Structured feedback channels, institutionalized mechanisms that systematically collect, process, and incorporate local input into the Façade Strategic Document (DSF) and *Stratégie Nationale pour la Mer et le Littoral* (SNML) could be a way forward. For example, a regional maritime council with a formal process for reporting back to stakeholders on how their input shaped the final plan, digital platforms for submitting local concerns, and a reduction of administrative burden of policy and reporting for local stakeholders. These mechanisms would allow for continuous input, review, and adjustment of plans based on stakeholder feedback and new information.

In addition, managers and people involved in the marine environments at the local level have emphasized the importance of strong political support, sufficient time, and open dialogue with civil society and businesses to ensure that the measures are accepted (French Med Workshop, 2024).

- **Stakeholder engagement can be deepened by involving more key NGO.** These organizations are often engaged in the MSFD and MSPD program of measure, bringing strong scientific expertise and maintaining good relationships with local populations. The role of key NGOs has been highlighted as essential in bridging the gap between state services (such as Maritime Directorates and Water Agencies), which are often met with public skepticism, and local economic actors. NGOs also play a crucial role in raising awareness on the importance of environmental regulations.
- **Strengthening local implementation capacity.** Local municipality authorities must comply with the programs of measures outlined in the Façade Strategic Document (MSFD and MSPD) and the SDAGE (WFD’s RBMP). Additionally, municipalities located within MPA or a Natura 2000 site must implement requirements from both the Birds and Habitats directives. Finally, they also have to take into consideration local economic development that often prevails over biodiversity objectives (for political reasons).

Local authorities frequently face implementation challenges due to resource constraints, particularly limited human capacity within supporting institutions⁴¹, as although the Water Agency *Rhone-Méditerranée-Corse* (AERMC) and the Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea (DIRM) provide support services, there are not enough human resources to respond to all the requests. As a result, local

³⁸ Interview with a marine environment project manager in a local institution, April 2024

³⁹ Interview with representants of the Maritime facade Council, of regional institutions and with local representatives, December 2023-April 2024

⁴⁰ Interview with a representative of the Corsica’s assembly

⁴¹ Interview with a marine environment project manager in a local institution, April 2024

authorities sometimes abandon efforts to develop a more integrated management plan that could cover all requirements, instead prioritizing solutions that are more feasible within their limited resources and guidance (see Box 19).

Box 19: Deprioritizing comprehensive planning due to complex policy demands

Coastal municipality representatives have the opportunity to mobilize various management tools to protect and manage the marine environment. These can include sea-enhancement schemes aimed at fostering economic activities along the coastline (up to 300m from shore).

However, engaging with these planning tools often requires substantial administrative expertise and long-term commitment to paperwork, sometimes spanning several years. This level of complexity may exceed the administrative capacity or technical knowledge of local authorities

As a result, balancing these various policy demands can lead to giving up on developing a comprehensive management plan, opting instead for approaches that are more immediately manageable and less administrative burdensome.

In larger cities such as Marseille, new management tools are currently being developed to support municipalities. The so-called bay Contract and STERE are managed by municipalities but with support of the land-institutions, the Water Agency Rhone-Mediterranée-Corse (AERMC) and the Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea (DIRM). The bay contract, a collaborative agreement where economic, industrial and institutional stakeholders work together to mitigate the negative impacts of industrial, port, and tourism activities on water and marine ecosystems. Additionally, municipalities can implement territorial ecological restoration schemes, which serve dual purposes: reducing marine pollution originating from inland waters and promoting ecological restoration efforts.

Strengthening collaboration with local authorities, building local capacity through targeted training and knowledge-sharing, optimizing internal workflows, streamlining administrative procedures for project approval and funding, and forming public-private partnerships to supplement the workforce, are some of the actions that can address insufficient staffing levels.

3.3.3 Vertical coherence

The case study investigated whether the planning processes associated to the MSFD, WFD, and MSPD are coherently contributing to the delivery of the EGD marine biodiversity objective (see Box 20).

Box 20: Key elements of the EGD related to marine biodiversity

- By 2030, 30% of EU seas must be designated as protected areas, with **10% under strict protection** (no extractive or industrial activities permitted)
- Legally binding targets to restore **20% of degraded marine ecosystems** (e.g., seagrass meadows, oyster beds) by 2030 and all ecosystems by 2050.
- Biodiversity considerations must be **integrated into all EU policies**, including fisheries, energy (e.g., offshore wind), and climate adaptation.

More information on the mapping exercise of the EGD's ocean-related objectives and targets, and the results from stakeholder interviews can be consulted in see [D1.1 \(2023\) Green Deal Objectives and Scenarios](#) and [D2.1 \(2024\) EU and international policy landscape](#)

France's National Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (NBS2030)⁴² is closely aligned with the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and serves as its national implementation. The NBS2030 aims at reverse biodiversity loss by 2030 by reducing pressures such as land use change, overexploitation, climate change, pollution, and invasive species, while restoring degraded ecosystems and mobilizing all stakeholders (including government, businesses, and citizens). Concrete targets include protecting 30% of France's land and sea areas, with 10% under "strong protection". In the French Mediterranean, this includes for example the protection of 100% of *Posidonia* seagrass beds and other key marine habitats⁴³

This section begins by describing how planning instruments derived from the three framework directives support the operationalization of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, specifically in relation to marine biodiversity objectives in France (see Box 21). It is followed by two subsections: (i) elements that support vertical cross-compliance, and (ii) potential measures to enhance this cross-compliance

Box 21: EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (marine biodiversity objectives) through the lens of the three framework directives in France

In addition to the measures introduced by the Birds and Habitats Directives, the achievement of the marine biodiversity objective of EGD is supported by the following (non-exhaustive) list of complementary measures:

The Façade Strategic Document (MSFD + MSPD):

- Designates Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and Other Effective Conservation Measures (OECMs) to safeguard biodiversity hotspots like *Posidonia* seagrass meadows and coralliferous reefs. For example, it restricts industrial activities (e.g., offshore wind farms, dredging) in ecologically sensitive zones, such as the Golfe du Lion, to minimize habitat fragmentation
- Mandates cumulative impact assessments for new maritime projects, ensuring compatibility with the MSFD's GES objectives. This includes evaluating pressures from shipping, tourism, and fisheries to protect endangered species like the Mediterranean monk seal
- Operationalizes the National Sea and Coast Strategy (SNML) by linking MSPD spatial plans with MSFD monitoring cycles and WFD pollution controls. For instance, it aligns coastal development restrictions with River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs) to reduce land-based nutrient runoff into MPAs
- The document prioritizes blue carbon ecosystems (e.g., seagrass meadows) as natural climate solutions, restricting bottom trawling in carbon-rich sediments and supporting habitat restoration projects to enhance biodiversity resilience

The SDAGE (RBMP) introduces biodiversity measures that directly benefit marine ecosystems by addressing land-based pollution and habitat degradation.

- SDAGE (RBMPs) target agricultural pollutants (e.g., nitrogen and phosphorus) from major rivers like the Rhône, Var, and Hérault, which contribute to Mediterranean eutrophication
- A stormwater master plan and the upgrade of coastal wastewater systems aim to improve water clarity and reduce toxic impacts on marine life.
- This pollution controls indirectly safeguard critical marine habitats like *Posidonia* seagrass meadows.

⁴² Ministère de la Transition écologique. (2022). [Stratégie nationale pour la biodiversité 2030: Premier volet pré-COP15](#).

⁴³ French CHM (n.d) [National Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#). National Clearing-House Mechanism website of the Convention on Biological Diversity.

3.3.2.1 Elements supporting the vertical cross-compliance with EGD

Findings from the French Mediterranean case study highlight the following aspects that could enhance the coherence of the planning instruments under the three framework directives, supporting the achievement of the EGD goals for marine biodiversity.

- ✓ **Targeted local funding initiatives.** To achieve the biodiversity objectives set by both the MSFD and WFD, the Water Agency (AERMC), which manages one of the most significant state budgets for aquatic and marine conservation in the French Mediterranean Sea, and the French Biodiversity Office (OFB) have launched numerous calls for projects. These initiatives fund biodiversity protection and ecosystem restoration, specifically including the conservation of Posidonia seagrass meadows, and the management of MPA such as through mooring and anchoring regulations.

In addition, both the Interregional Directorate for the Mediterranean Sea (DIRM) and the Water Agency provide financial support to local authorities and municipalities for the development of marine environmental enhancement plans known as STERE (*Chémas Territoriaux pour la Reconquête de l'Environnement marin*). These integrated management plans aim to reduce marine pollution and promote the ecological restoration of coastal and marine ecosystems. As of now, four STEREs are being supported along the Mediterranean coast. To strengthen these initiatives, DIRM has launched four complementary calls for projects addressing ecological restoration strategies; the impact of diving activity on frequently visited marine sites; dredging practices and onshore management of dredged sediments; and the pooling, valorisation, and ecological functioning of soft substrate habitats.

Although local funding can have a positive impact, to contribute effectively to a global solution, the indicators, measures, and planning timelines of these funded activities must be better aligned to enhance the efficiency of regulations and the projects supported.

- ✓ **A regulatory tool between biodiversity protection and MSP.** To reinforce the link between biodiversity protection and MSP in the French Mediterranean, a key instrument is the ERC sequence (avoid–reduce–compensate). The ERC sequence applies to any developer, public or private, required to obtain approval for infrastructure development projects that may impact the environment. It obliges project sponsors to assess environmental conditions before construction and to take measures that first avoid, then reduce, and finally compensate for negative effects on ecosystems and biodiversity.

The ERC approach has been adapted for marine biodiversity in France through comprehensive national guidelines, which include a dedicated section for marine environments. It is primarily applied to major infrastructure, such as offshore wind farms and coastal developments. However, the effectiveness of the ERC strategy relies on high-quality scientific knowledge, robust environmental baselines, and the ability to forecast ecosystem impacts prior to project approval

3.3.2.2 Potential ways to improve the cross-compliance with EGD

The analysis also identifies key actions that would strengthen the vertical coherence among the planning instruments of the three framework directives, thereby supporting the effective implementation of the EGD goals for marine biodiversity. In specific, within the French Mediterranean, working on improving vertical coherence to deliver the EGD objectives implies enhancing the governance and organisation of competencies rather changing operational mechanisms.

- **Progress in integrated land-sea management is still expected:** The land-sea interface is a critical factor in achieving good environmental status (GES) in the Mediterranean Sea. According to the latest environmental impact assessment in the Mediterranean Façade Strategic Document (MSFD + MSPD), approximately 80% of marine contamination originates from inland waters. Additionally, the Mediterranean coastline faces intense pressure from the tourism industry. These observations put into perspective the scope of the Façade Strategic Document's efforts to limit coastal pollution and highlight the need for significant progress in integrated land-sea management (see Box 22).

Box 22: The need for enhanced land-sea dialogue

The French administrative division has separated the administration of land and sea, with two Prefects, one regional (land) and one maritime (sea), representing the state and at least 14 different institutions from land and sea having management competencies on the sea.

According to the interviewees, such opposition triggers bottlenecks with “land people/administration” with no relation and no consideration of “marine people/administration”. A key example is the one of the from the new discharges from the Montpellier wastewater treatment plant in 2016, where the municipality decided to discharge wastewater into the sea because the indicators were more permissible than those for freshwater, with the argument that this would "fertilise the sea", demonstrates several facts: 1) land-freshwater-sea indicators that are not aligned, 2) the organisation of activities on land that do not take account of impacts at sea, and 3) a lack of knowledge among people on land about the challenges of the marine environment

The question of who is responsible for the marine spatial planning and the organisation of activities at sea is crucial, especially given that at least ten to twelve institutions are involved, each with different mandates (see Figure 13). In France, land-sea discussions on this issue remain limited. For instance, during the public consultation on the new Façade Strategic Document (November 2023 to April 2024), only one out of approximately 100 webinars addressed the connection between land, freshwater, and sea

Achieving GES requires coordinated efforts within the watershed (SDAGE); The RBMP program of measure plays a key role in this land-sea interface with 276 actions in total related to the marine environment (186 on transitional waters and 90 on coastal waters including 49 on mooring, 24 on bathing areas, and 25 on reducing pollution by hazardous substances)

A proposed solution is to strengthen capacity building within existing framework, such as the RBMPs, since most representatives of inland municipalities are already involved in their respective basin committees. Another solution pointed out by interviewees is to reduce the number of planning documents and clarify the distribution of responsibilities, for example, assigning a single institution to oversee the financing of restoration projects and mooring, instead of two or three. Finally, it has been suggested

to create new cross-sectoral positions to improve the integration of marine considerations into municipal planning. A notable example is the position created in the municipality of Marseille to manage the *Contrat de Baie*⁴⁴ and strengthen connections with marine professionals.

Another important aspect expected to be integrated as part of the land-sea management is the misalignment between land-use planning and water-related plans, particularly regarding economic development and biodiversity protection (see Box 23).

Box 23: Misalignment between land-planning priorities and marine biodiversity protection

Analysing biodiversity condition within the marine governance framework in the French Mediterranean context requires looking beyond the planning documents related to MSFD, MSPD and WFD. In the French context, land-management documents influence marine biodiversity's condition.

In the division of the Maritime Public Domain, such division has a strong impact (see *Figure 15*) with land management policies mostly oriented to the economic development in the first 300 metres while the marine-related policies emphasise biodiversity protection

Figure 15: Repartition and overlap of land-sea and freshwater planning document

This analysis has revealed a degree of misalignment between land-management and water-related plans, particularly in relation to economic development and biodiversity protection.

⁴⁴ The "*Contrat de Baie*" is a multi-stakeholder environmental management agreement implemented at the bay or coastal area level. In Marseille, the *Contrat de Baie* initiative involved coordinating actions across municipalities to improve water quality and manage the coastline; pooling resources and expertise among public and private stakeholders; focusing on challenges like pollution reduction, biodiversity preservation, and sustainable development of marine and coastal activities.

For example, the regional land-management plan (SRADDET) of the Provence-Alpes-Côte-d’Azur Region and Corsica’s sustainable development plan (PADDUC) allow coastal municipalities to draft a “sea-enhancement plan” to develop and authorize economic activities at sea.

Although this document are, in principle, required to align with the Façade Strategic Document (MSFD + MSPD) and SDAGE (RBMP) regarding biodiversity requirements, two key challenges arise when attempting to reconcile economic development with biodiversity protection:

- (a) The SRADDET and PADDUC (land-management) define 14 operational objectives, of which only 2 relate to biodiversity protection, while the remaining 12 focus on economic development. These objectives are not aligned with those outlined in the SDAGE (RBMP) and Façade (MSFD+MSPD)
- (b) While local actors involved in land management are generally aware of the biodiversity requirements set out in the SDAGE (RBMP), they are often unaware of the MSFD and MSPD, leading to inconsistencies in implementation.⁴⁵

➤ **Strengthen stakeholder involvement and transparency in multi-level planning.**

Consultation is part of the planning process for documents such as the DSF, SDAGE, and SRADDET, involving both the general public and private sector stakeholders. However, in the final drafting stages, there is often a lack of consideration for local stakeholders, those ultimately responsible for implementing the plans.

To improve vertical coherence, the first step should be to co-construct these plans. A bottom-up approach to designing implementation mechanisms should run in parallel with national strategic orientations, enabling local stakeholders to effectively implement the requirements of the MSFD, MSPD, and WFD⁴⁶.

The drafting process of the Façade Strategic Document (DSF) is worth examining and improving. While it includes public consultation and input from the Façade Maritime Council, there is a lack of transparency regarding how these contributions are reflected in the final document⁴⁷. This has led to disengagement from certain regions, such as Corsica, where some stakeholders have expressed a desire to develop their own Maritime Strategic Document rather than remain part of the Mediterranean Façade Strategic Document⁴⁸.

3.4 Oslo Fjord: Addressing ecosystem deterioration

The Oslofjord is a coastal inlet with an extensive catchment area, currently facing an ecological crisis. This is characterised by severe eutrophication, the collapse of demersal fish stocks, and widespread habitat loss and degradation. These impacts are primarily driven by intense human activities, including overfishing, urbanisation, and pollution originating from the entire catchment, especially agricultural runoff and sewage discharges (Box 24).

⁴⁵ Provence-Alpes-Côte-d’Azur Region Regional plan for spatial planning, sustainable development and territorial equality (land-management plan for the Provence-Alpes-Côte-D’Azur Region), 2020.
Corsica’s sustainable development plan (land -management plan for Corsica), 2015.

⁴⁶ Interview with a local stakeholder implementing the MSFD, MSPD and WFD at a local scale, April 2024

⁴⁷ Interview with two experts involved in the Maritime Facade Council, February 2024.

⁴⁸ Interview with a representative of the Corsican’s regional assembly, March 2024

Box 24: Geographic scope and challenges addressed in the Oslo Fjord case study

Figure 16 The delimitation of the Oslofjord and its catchment area (red line). The two coloured areas show the spatial coverage of the two RBMPs that addressed the Fjord during the work (Figure: NMBU).

The Oslofjord, a coastal inlet with an extensive catchment area, is the marine entrance to the capital of Norway – Oslo. There are also other cities along the fjord. Two major river systems, Drammenselva and Glomma, connect the Fjord to a large catchment area that covers most of central Norway. The population along the fjord and its catchment area has grown significantly and is 2,5 million inhabitants today, or half of Norway’s population (Norwegian Environment Agency, 2019).

The Oslofjord ecosystems face severe deterioration after centuries of intensive use, including discharges from industries, settlements and agriculture, impacts from fisheries, hunting, shipping and leisure activities as well as constructions along the shores and waterways. In recent policy documents, *eutrophication* is highlighted as a major challenge. Sewage pipes leak, only four wastewater treatment plants actively remove nitrogen, while precipitation washes out particles and nutrients from both the sewage network and all kinds of surfaces throughout the catchment area. Agriculture is a particularly important source of such runoff. The effects of eutrophication include growth of filamentous algae that suffocate benthic flora, causing oxygen depleted zones. *Overfishing*, partly historical, is considered another major problem since it has disrupted the balance between species throughout the ecosystem. The cascading trophic effects contribute to aggravate problems of eutrophication. A third problem that has high priority, is to *halt constructions in the coastal zone*. This has reduced the public’s access to the Fjord and destroyed important biotopes, also in the sea. The fjord is also exposed to emissions of environmental toxins, dumping of masses, pollution, alien species, and heavy boat traffic. Climate change contributes to exacerbating many of the other problems (Norwegian Environment Agency, 2019).

The research design in CrossGov investigates the relationship between environmental directives and spatial planning at sea. The WFD is transposed in Norwegian legislation, while MSFD and MSPD are not covered by the EEA Agreement. Norway has its own national approach for managing the issues covered by the MSFD (Integrated Ocean management Plans), while there is no direct counterpart to the MSPD. To include the dimension of spatial planning into the Oslo Fjord case, the analysis has instead assessed the interplay between environmental policies and municipal spatial planning. It should be noted that Norwegian municipal spatial plans would be comparable to municipal spatial plans of other countries but is different from the MSPD plans analysed in the other case studies. However, due to differences between municipal spatial planning and the MSPD regime analysed in the other cases, the spatial planning element has not been a central focus in the Norwegian case study. Box 25 below provides further information on Norway’s relationship with the European Union and the country’s administrative system.

The analysis of the Oslofjord case focuses therefore on the horizontal coherence between the RBMPs, the Integrated Ocean Management Plans, and municipal spatial planning in the coastal zone. The case study also considers the extent to which the plans contribute to high-level Norwegian objectives that align with the EU Green Deal. In addition to the research questions

mentioned in *Table 7* and *Table 8*, case-study specific research questions, which follows from the inclusion of a government's action plan⁴⁹ were: Is the Oslofjord Plan coherent with the three other plans reviewed? How does it affect the realization of their objectives?

The findings of this analysis are organized into sub-chapters that present elements supporting both horizontal and vertical coherence, as well as potential strategies to further enhance coherence

Box 25: Norway: EU relationship and administrative system

Norway is not a member of the European Union. Through the European Economic Area (EEA) Agreement (1994), however, Norway is part of EU's internal market. The condition is that Norway accepts certain types of EU legislation, defined in the EEA Agreement. This includes environmental regulations, such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive. However, ocean affairs, fisheries and agriculture are exemptions in the Agreement. Therefore, the MSFD, the MSPD, the Common Fisheries Policy and the Common Agriculture Policy do not apply to Norway. On such issues where Norway is not bound by the EU, Norway has national approaches, thereby providing a broader basis for comparisons in CrossGov.

The kingdom of Norway is a unitary state with three political-administrative levels: The national government, the counties (regions) and the municipalities. The counties and municipalities perform their tasks according to national legislation. At the same time, there is a strong tradition for local self-determination, creating tensions in discussions about the role of the lower governance levels: Delivering nationally defined policies and services, or creating their own agendas?

There is an important division between coastal and ocean management set at 1 nautical mile (nm) seawards from the baseline. This boundary is defined according to EU legislation, especially the WFD. The Oslofjord mainly lies on the landwards side of this boundary. Ocean management outwards of this boundary is considered a national responsibility. Planning and all kinds of management decisions are therefore almost entirely in the hands of the government with its relevant ministries, directorates and agencies.

The coastal zone of Norway is defined by deep indentations by fiords and by an archipelago of islands that position the baseline far out from land. The responsibility for cross-sectoral planning in the coastal zone according to the WFD and the national Planning and Building Act, are delegated to counties and municipalities. However, governmental agencies participate actively in such planning. Some of the national sectoral authorities have jurisdiction according to legislation that transcends the ocean - coastal divide. Thus, it is also highly variable from sector to sector, whether the counties and municipalities can actively regulate, whether they have certain roles in a system with shared responsibilities, or whether governmental agencies are entirely responsible. Some examples of relevant sectors are:

- **Fisheries and shipping** are almost entirely the responsibility of the national government, also in the coastal zone. The municipalities' role is limited to developing and managing certain types of ports.
- **Agriculture** is a shared responsibility where the government, including its regional branches, has the main responsibilities, with the municipalities undertaking more local guidance, land-use planning etc to the farmers.
- **Urban wastewater** is delegated entirely to the municipalities, within frames established by national legislation and policy.
- **Spatial planning** is delegated to the municipalities, however, with clear roles also for counties and government agencies.

⁴⁹ A concise description of the Oslo Fjord plan is provided in Box 26

3.4.1 Methodology

During the Kick-off meeting in Oslo (September 2022), stakeholders from the Oslofjord were present, providing information about the case study area. The discussions highlighted the challenges of moving towards an integrated implementation of the planning instruments.

In addition, a combination of document analysis and stakeholder events served to collect the empirical data for this case study work. The analysis of policy documents took place between January 2023 – May 2024. The list of analysed documents can be seen in *Table 17*.

Table 17: Documents analysed as part of the Oslo Fjord case study and their relevance to the framework directives and/or sectors of interest to this case stud. *Equivalent in Norway

	WFD	IOMP	Municipal plans	Agriculture	Urban wastewater	Fisheries
<i>Vannforskriften</i> (Regulation transposing WFD)	X					
Guidance documents to water management at “vannportalen”	X					
<i>Vannforvaltningsplan</i> (RBMP) Vestfold - Telemark	X			x	x	
<i>Vannforvaltningsplan</i> (RBMP) for Viken - Innlandet	X			x	x	
Municipal plans of Asker and Fredrikstad, screening of Nordre Follo, Hvaler and Færder municipalities			x			
White papers to the parliament about the IOMPs: St.meld 8 (2005-2006, Meld. St. 20 (2019-2020), Meld. St. 21 (2023 – 2024).		x		x	x	x
The Governments integrated action plan for the Oslofjord	x		x	x	x	x

In addition to desk-based research, several semi-structured interviews were conducted between September 2023 and March 2024. These provided insights in different perspectives and room for exchange of views. Information from the [MAREA](#) project was also used to complement the collected information.

The list of management organisations and other relevant stakeholders involved in data collection activities are registered in *Table 18*.

Table 18: Institutions and other relevant stakeholders involved in data collection activities for the Oslofjord case study

Organization	Relevance
Norwegian Ministry Environment & Climate - Section for Ocean Management & Section for Water Management	IOMP, WFD, Oslofjord Plan
County governor - Local administrative agency	WFD, agriculture
Norwegian Environment Agency - Knowledge provider for ocean management plans	IOMP
Municipalities - Different thematic areas	PBA, WFD
Directorate of Fisheries (planned)	Fisheries, IOMP, (link to) WFD
NGO for the Oslofjord	WFD, PBA. Fisheries, agriculture, Oslofjord Plan
Fisheries association	Fisheries, Oslofjord Plan

To ensure co-creation during the research project, the project team established a core group of four key stakeholders in the Oslofjord, covering different levels of governance, roles and responsibilities. The core group was consulted three times during the project period to ensure alignment of the research focus with actual needs and perspectives from stakeholders.

The researchers have participated at several conferences and meetings on the Oslofjord. The research team also applied for an observer role at the Oslofjord Council and has so far participated in one of its meetings. These have provided good opportunities to engage with all kinds of stakeholders.

In January 2025, a multi-actor stakeholder workshop on the Oslofjord was organised to present and discuss the project results and implications for Norwegian policy planning. The meeting was held in person and attended by more than 25 participants from different governmental organizations, industry representatives, unions, NGOs and researchers across different sectors and levels of governance.

The analysis of the collected data was carried out using two frameworks: the Policy Coherence Evaluation Framework, which includes coherence attributes and explanatory variables, and the Science-Policy-Society Interface (SPSI) Assessment Framework, based on its defined building blocks as described in Section 2.3 of this report. The analysed data was organized into the three internal reports referred to as Step 1, Step 2, and Step 3.

3.4.2 Horizontal coherence

Within the context of the Oslo Fjord, this case study examined the coherence between the planning processes associated to the WFD as well as the planning processes associated to the Norwegian equivalents of the MSFD (Integrated Ocean Management Plans) and MSPD (Municipal Spatial Plans). This section begins with an overview of the national systems for planning which are of relevance given CrossGov's Task 3.2 objectives (Box 26), followed by two subsections: (i) elements that support the coherent implementation of these instruments, and (ii) potential measures to further enhance this coherence.

Box 26: The national systems for planning of relevance for the Oslo Fjord: The WFD and the MSFD and MSPD in Norway

The WFD is transposed in Norwegian legislation, while MSFD and MSPD are not covered by the EEA Agreement. Norway has its own national approach for managing the issues covered by the MSFD (Integrated Ocean management Plans), while there is no direct counterpart to the MSPD.

Here, we present the transposition of the WFD as well as national policy and planning systems that contain elements comparable to the other two directives. The government has also published an action plan for the Oslofjord, which is included in our analysis. Table 19 and Figure 17 provide an overview.

Table 19: Equivalents in the EU and Norwegian setting for planning aimed at environmental management of rivers and sea basins, and of human activities at sea. The Oslofjord Plan “supplements and reinforces” i.a. the RBMPs and municipal planning.

	EU setting	Oslofjord setting
Environmental management of river basins and coastal areas	RBMP (WFD)	RBMP (WFD)
Environmental management of large marine ecosystems	Marine Strategies (MSFD)	Integrated Ocean Management Plans (IOMP)
Marine Spatial Planning: a) In the oceans b) In the coastal zone	a) Marine Spatial Plans (MSP) b) National town and regional planning legislation	a) Not cross-sectorial; only sectoral spatial planning, within certain boundaries set by the IOMPs b) Municipal Spatial Plans according to the Planning and Building Act (PBA) ⁵⁰

Figure 17: Spatial scopes of the plans. Source: Norwegian Environment Agency, adapted by the authors.

The WFD and the planning in the Oslofjord

Norway transposed the WFD into the Water Regulation in 2006, based on four laws: The Pollution Act, the Planning and Building Act, The Water Resources Act and the Biodiversity. Norway’s implementation of the WFD applies to both catchments and coastal waters out to 1nm from the baseline. Due to Norway’s specific coastal geography with deep fjords and many islands, this designates an exceptional large coastal zone managed by the WFD.

The Water Regulation creates an internal multi-level system in Norway (Sander, 2023a). Nationally, there is a group of ministries and a group of directorates that oversee the system, provide mandates for regional and local planning, allocate resources for planning, finally adopts the plans – and reports to the EU. The major responsibility for the planning occurs at the regional level, where the counties are responsible for managing river basin districts that prepare and follow up implementation of RBMPs. Norway has also introduced a local level, where the municipalities and local organizations may provide input to the processes in the counties.

⁵⁰ Plan- og bygningloven

The RBMPs are environmental plans aiming for good chemical and good ecological status. In the coasts, they focus on pollution from land-based sources, both nutrients (N and P) and contaminants. The measures introduced to achieve or maintain the objectives are voluntary commitments formulated and implemented by sectoral authorities and municipalities, within their own budgets.

The RBMPs are adopted as regional plans and finally approved at the national level as a mechanism for solving conflicts of a general nature that cannot be resolved by the counties. According to the Planning and Building Act, the plans should be a basis for the planning and activities of all public entities in the region, including the municipalities (Planning and Building Act, 2008).

Since Norway has a large coastal zone covered by the RBMPs, it is relevant to note that the plans mainly focus on freshwater, do not sufficiently account for land-sea interactions, have a narrow selection of especially marine indicators, and exclude some sectoral activities, especially fisheries. The Oslofjord is covered by two RBMPs.

MSFD*: Integrated Ocean Management Plans (IOMP)

As a non-member of the EU, Norway has opted for national ocean management plans (IOMP) instead of the MSFD. The **IOMPs** are Norway's overarching, cross-sectorial policy instruments for the oceans. Their regulatory spatial scope is the oceans outwards of the baseline under Norwegian jurisdiction. Assessments may cover broader areas, sometimes, also the coastal zone.

The plans are *comparable to the MSFD-based Marine Strategies* in the EU as implementations of ecosystem-based management, sharing major approaches (Sander, 2023a). However, the IOMPs are not entirely environmental instruments; they have the dual purpose of protecting the marine ecosystems and stimulating economic developments. Another difference is that they are not legally based and are ruled by few formal instructions. Instead, they can be considered a well-established, informal custom, which gradually evolves with each new plan. In addition, whereas coastal states in the EU can apply the MSFD in their coastal waters to create overlap with the WFD, Norway's Ocean Management Plans do not cover the coastal waters. Consequently, for coastal areas such as the Oslofjord, the WFD remains the sole policy for managing water quality and ecosystem health, as well as linking coastal and catchment governance

The plans are prepared by a cross-ministerial steering group, based on commissioned reports from scientific advisory bodies. The government is responsible for the plans, deciding when there are internal conflicts between the ministries (Sander, 2018). It presents the final plans as white papers to the Parliament.

The plans conclude with a programme of action that includes frames for further developments. Sectoral authorities are responsible for implementing the measures and operating within the frames. Except from strategic steering of the oil and gas sector's own spatial planning, the plans provide weak direction to the sectoral administration's use of ocean space. The only requirement is to be cautious in defined valuable and vulnerable areas, which have no legal protection since Norway has not designated MPAs in the ocean. In its most recent plan from April 2024 (Meld. St. 21 (2023–2024), *the government declined to make the plans include more elements of cross-sectoral marine spatial planning*). Thus, marine spatial planning and allocation of sea space to users, is done by the individual sectoral administrations.

To facilitate comparability across case studies, the IOMPs will be referred to as MSFD* in the analytical sections.

Marine Spatial Planning in the coastal zone

The Oslofjord lies predominantly within the baseline. Spatial planning of the Fjord therefore occurs according to national planning legislation. This would have been the case also if Norway were an EU-member state, since the MSPD “*shall not apply to coastal waters or parts thereof falling under a Member State's town and country planning*” (art 2) - unless the coastal state determines so. The spatial planning presented in our case study therefore is comparable to coastal plans prepared by EU member states.

The *Planning and Building Act* (PBA) requires municipalities to prepare a Municipal Master Plan that sets out the ambitions for the development of the municipality. The master plan should give direction to a Municipal Spatial

Master Plan. It is mandatory to prepare such a plan for land use, voluntary to do so for sea use, which may be prepared in separate plans. Along the Oslofjord, all municipalities have integrated their marine and terrestrial areas into one single plan. Municipalities may also voluntarily develop thematic plans according to their own ambitions and needs. Relevant examples from the Oslofjord include plans for biodiversity and for sewage.

The government's action plan for the Oslofjord

The deterioration of the Oslofjord has risen on the political agenda the last years. To address the Oslofjord's ecological decline, and in response to a parliamentary request, the national government in 2021 adopted an integrated and cross-sectoral action plan for ecosystem protection and restoration, and sustainable coastal development (hereafter referred as the **Oslofjord Plan**) (Ministry for Climate and Environment, 2021). The plan is designed to reinforce and supplement the existing governance system. It is a unique initiative to mobilize all relevant sectors and levels towards achieving the objectives. The 63 measures include land use, agriculture, sewage, fisheries, invasive species control, cultural heritage, and climate initiatives. There are also 19 measures for achieving better knowledge.

- The Plan covers the **entire Oslofjord**, shifting focus from individual water bodies to the fjord as a whole, addressing the WFD's limited coastal scope.
- Though not legally binding, the Plan has created **strong political and societal mobilisation**, leading to new regulations and stronger sectoral engagement.
- Annual status reports by responsible authorities enhance accountability and implementation, going beyond the WFD's lighter **reporting** requirements. The **coordination** role is assumed by national environmental authorities, which are in a better position to coordinate with sectors than regional authorities that hold the RBMP coordination role.
- The Plan provides a **holistic approach** to managing pressures in the coastal areas. For instance, fisheries (which is not included under the RBMPs) are part of the Plans' scope.
- Targeted **funding** has been allocated through sectoral channels, directing national resources to support measures in the Oslofjord region

The following-up of the plan is administered by a secretariate led by the Norwegian Environment Agency. An **Oslofjord Council** is established for discussions of implementation of the measures twice a year. It is led by the minister for climate and environment and involves representatives from the public sector (national agencies and local authorities), and interest groups (some NGOs and industries).

3.4.1.1 Elements assisting the coherence

We identified several elements that support the coherent implementation between the planning processes associated to the WFD as well as the planning processes associated to the IOMP.

- ✓ **National coordination for WFD and IOMP (MSFD*) under the responsibility of the same governmental organization.** The Ministry of Climate and Environment is responsible for both the RBMP (WFD) and IOMP (MSFD*) systems, though they are managed by separate organizational sections. While no formal coordination mechanism exists, the Water section has increasingly contributed to shaping the updated IOMP (MSFD*), which falls under the responsibility of the Ocean section. The 2024 IOMP included a chapter on coastal management and signalled a review aiming for broadening the scope of indicators under Norway's transposed WFD.

At the ministerial level, there is an increased focus on the interactions and synergies across both planning systems. Interviewees pointed out that by Norway's international commitment through the High-Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy that promotes Sustainable Ocean Management Plans (100% sustainable management of

oceans AND coast), have contributed to focus more on these interactions. The Oslo Fjord plan (see Box 27) has also led to contacts across these planning systems.

- ✓ **Synergistic objectives in the RBMPs and IOMP (MSFD*):** The plans set objectives that aim for good ecological and good environmental status. Excess nutrients have led to severe oxygen depletion and ecosystem decline in the Oslo Fjord. RBMPs and IOMPs (MSFD*) set complementary goals across different zones: RBMPs target good ecological status in catchments and coastal waters, while IOMPs apply ecosystem-based management in marine areas

Box 27: Understanding the role of the Oslofjord Plan

Several of our observations point to the **Oslofjord Plan as a positive example of institutional layering, that has increased the coherence across existing planning instruments** and positively contributes to the alignment of objectives and instruments across sectors

The governance system of the Oslofjord so far has been based on RBMPs, municipal spatial plans, and sectoral instruments (IOMPs for outer part of the Fjord). The Oslofjord Plan emphasizes “coordinating, supplementing, and reinforcing all the positive efforts.” **The Oslofjord Plan uniquely integrates policy objectives and instruments** across multiple sectors, including land use, agriculture, sewage, fisheries, spatial management, invasive species control, heritage, and climate initiatives.

The Oslofjord Plan has elevated the Oslofjord’s importance on **the political agenda**, both nationally and locally.

- The Oslofjord Plan reflects strong national political ambition.
- The dominating discourse in the media has been that the Fjord is in a state of crisis. Despite expensive measures that will affect the inhabitants through sewage taxes, public understanding and support seems to have grown. There were no major protests or setbacks during the electoral campaign for local elections in 2023. This may change when conflicts become more apparent.
- This heightened political focus at the local level influences municipal decision-making. Asker and Hvaler are two municipalities that, by slightly different mechanisms, have tried to incorporate the objectives of the Oslofjord plan into their affairs.

The Oslofjord Plan **aligns and strengthens the RBMP implementation.**

- As stated by one of the interviewees, “*The Oslofjord plan has achieved a high political interest, which has not been the case for the RBMPs – despite their overlapping objectives.*”
- RBMPs fell short on addressing upstream-downstream issues, ref. above. The Oslofjord Plan has increased the understanding and need for an integrated approach across the catchment area.
- Unlike the triennial RBMP reports,⁵¹ the Oslofjord Plan mandates annual reporting by municipalities and sectoral authorities, emphasizing policy implementation progress and accountability.⁵²

The Oslofjord plan **promotes more holistic planning** approaches

- Spatial planning in the Oslofjord is carried out at the level of individual municipalities, resulting in fragmented approaches that fail to account for the cumulative impacts of urbanisation along the entire shoreline. Moreover, the marine components of municipal spatial plans in the Oslofjord area remain underdeveloped, with relatively few specifications or detailed provisions. The Oslofjord Plan includes measures aimed at promoting more holistic planning approaches. However, one of its proposed policy measures to assess the potential for regional planning approaches, has been rejected. Despite increased attention to the issue, fragmented spatial planning with insufficient consideration of impacts on the marine environment continues to pose a serious challenge.

The Oslofjord plan **promotes a cross-sectoral approach.**

⁵¹ Sectoral authorities simply report on whether implementation of instruments has started/ is ongoing/ not begun.

⁵² The reports highlight those that have/haven’t implemented the policy instruments, meaning there is an in-built “carrots and sticks” mechanism in the reporting

- The Oslofjord Plan and Council stand out due to their cross-sectoral approach (Figure 18), going beyond existing planning instruments. The plan addresses traditionally fragmented land-sea dynamics across marine and freshwater frameworks.
- Fisheries was not adequately addressed by the major policy instrument, the RBMPs. In contrast, the Oslofjord Plan integrates all pressures, including fisheries, into a single strategic document. Thus, the plan can be seen as an attempt to introduce ecosystem-based management for the Fjord that captures the whole ecosystem and all relevant sectors.
- The Plan has also contributed to earmarking financial support for environmental agricultural measures in the fjord's catchment area.

Figure 18: To address the Oslofjord's ecological decline, the government launched a cross-sectoral Action Plan in 2021, supported by a broad Council. Layered onto existing structures, the Plan has strengthened RBMP implementation, led to new regulations, and promoted a more holistic approach to coastal management

It is still too early to evaluate results from the Oslofjord plan, but current findings from our research indicates that the government's plan for the Oslofjord promotes a holistic approach to managing the Oslofjord, involves all relevant sectors and levels of governance. The creation of an Oslofjord Council for dialogue on implementation is an innovative political experiment for the involvement of all relevant actors. Despite these positive tendencies, progress towards the objectives has been slow and the second phase of the CrossGov research will focus more thoroughly on its implementation.

3.4.1.2 Potential ways to improve coherence

Identified actions that would strengthen the horizontal coherence among the planning instruments of the three framework directives in the Oslo Fjord area are: are:

- **Strengthen the science-policy interactions between terrestrial, coastal and marine water governance:** To date, there is limited uptake of marine expertise in water governance. Within the Ministry of Climate and Environment, which is responsible for both the RBMPs (WFD) and IOMP (MSFD*) systems, the Water section has been increasingly consulted by the Oceans section during the drafting of the IOMP (MSFD*). However, intra-organizational collaboration remains weak and there is a sharp divide between both plans; the planning cycles are temporarily misaligned, and there is no coordination of measures. At lower levels of governance, the vertical integration and coordination is even less apparent: the **RBMPs** of the Oslofjord catchment area neither incorporate provisions nor mention the **IOMP (MSFD*)**.

- **Create shared knowledge processes and databases:** A separation exists also in terms of knowledge and assessment systems. The environmental assessment of the IOMPs (MSFD*) is conducted at the national level, mobilising national research and management authorities. The ecological assessment of the coast under the RBMPs is conducted in a decentralised manner. The knowledge systems and databases are not interlinked.
- **Improve the interplay between RBMPs and Ocean Management Plans in the coastal zone:** To date, there remains a sharp divide and narrow focus of the RBMPs and IOMPs, which leads to insufficient management of coastal areas. Unlike EU states, where MSFD can create overlap with WFD in coastal waters, Norwegian coastal zone (such as Oslofjord) is managed exclusively by the RBMPs. This creates weaknesses in holistic management:
 - RBMPs provide a framework for cross-sectoral strategic planning, but their influence over sectoral authorities is limited. Implementation relies on sectors' willingness and capacity to act within their own legal and financial systems.
 - The WFD, primarily focused on freshwater, includes coastal areas. River basin management is highly decentralized in Norway, with many small waterbodies as the main planning units. This local and small-scale focus often overlooks broader upstream-downstream connections and coastal impacts
 - WFD coastal indicators offer a narrow view of biodiversity, excluding key ecosystem components. Without complementary assessments from IOMPs, this limited scope hinders comprehensive action against all pressures, such as fisheries
- **Strengthen the environmental provisions of coastal and marine areas within municipal spatial planning and ensure more holistic planning across municipal borders.**
 - Spatial plans are important tools to ensure that impacts on waterways and the coastal zones are minimised. While there are links between RBMPs and municipal planning regulations, these interactions are not sufficient. This can partially be attributed to the narrow focus of RBMPs (see above: limited upstream-downstream linkages, weak authority, freshwater instead of marine focus), which inhibit holistic planning approaches. This is further challenges by fragmented planning approaches, with each municipality developing their own spatial plans. Moreover, planning within the coastal areas of the Oslofjord Plan remains underdeveloped and only few municipalities use spatial provisions to protect important marine habitats; or grant too many exemptions for urbanisation projects along the shoreline. This implies that both inspection, enforcement, and more coordination between policy instruments (RBMPs and municipal planning are required). Enhanced national planning guidelines are important tools to ensure better coherence.
 - There is a spatial and thematic divide between municipal planning and ocean management. Norway has chosen not to extend its IOMPs (MSFD*) into the coastal zone to supplement the thematic scope of the RBMPs. One consequence is that there is weak coast – ocean understandings. The government also carefully avoids taking measures in the IOMPs (MSFD*) directed at specific coastal issues to not interfere with the authority of the counties and municipalities, which are responsible for RBMPs and municipal spatial plans. Moreover, different scientific databases and assessment systems are used. A national GIS tool supports environmental management (IOMP)

and spatial planning for the oceans, which is done by sectoral authorities. The tool contains some information about the coastal zone, but is rarely used in municipal planning.

3.4.3 Vertical coherence

Norway has long-standing environmental objectives that align with the EU Green Deal, including the preservation and restoration of ecosystems and biodiversity; contribution to zero pollution as well as action against and adaptation to climate change. The objectives and their current level of achievement are monitored and evaluated based on national indicators, accessible through a national online portal.⁵³ The objectives are meant to guide all sectors and levels of the Norwegian governance system.

The case study investigated to what extent does the combination of plans (RBMPs (WFD), Integrated Ocean Management Plans (MSFD*), and municipal spatial plans contribute to the Norwegian environmental objectives.

3.4.2.1 Elements supporting the vertical cross-compliance to the high-level Norwegian Objectives

Findings from the case study identified the following contributions to these objectives:

- The **RBMPs** main objectives of achieving good chemical and good ecological status make them highly relevant for halting pollution and improving biodiversity. Their effectiveness in reaching these objectives are reduced by their limited coverage of the whole coastal ecosystems and all activities/pressures affecting it, the limited focus on upstream-downstream dynamics, as well as lack of "sticks and carrots" to stimulate involved parties to take measures: Adaptation to changing climate is mentioned, but not much elaborated, neither for managing water and ecosystem qualities, nor for managing increased quantities of water.
- The ocean management plans (**IOMP**) address biodiversity (ecosystems) and threats upon it from i.a. pollution. They have extensively reviewed occurring and projected climate change with the ambition of adapting ocean management to the changes. Weak legal status and unclear obligations make it hard to evaluate their effects on sectoral management. As mentioned above, their relevance for the coastal zone, including the Oslofjord, is limited.
- The **municipalities** are slow in progress to halt land-based pollution. Their planning and management of land and sea uses in the fjord, along the coastline and along watersheds, have many unused possibilities to address biodiversity loss more effectively. They are at uneven stages of developing plans and actions for climate adaptation, mainly focusing on land-based challenges such as how to tackle extreme events with excessive water and landslides.

⁵³ Source: [Norges klima- og miljømål - Miljøstatus \(miljodirektoratet.no\)](https://www.miljodirektoratet.no/norges-og-eu-klima-og-miljomal) The objectives are cross-sectoral

- The governmental **Oslofjord Plan** reinforces the work on pollution and biodiversity but does not consider climate adaptation as a separate topic. However, the plan takes the general view that climate change reinforces the effects of other pressures on the marine ecosystems. Measures for ecosystem restoration will increase their resilience towards future climate change and should therefore be considered adaptation measures

Considering the plans in combination towards each of the issues, **there is a clear course set to halt pollution of nutrients**, which is essential to combat eutrophication. The extent to which this will be successful depends on the ability to transform general direction from strategic plans to concrete actions, especially in the agriculture and sewage sectors.

Climate change adaptation has received limited attention. There is knowledge about some climate effects on the coastal marine ecosystem. However, the more specific implications for how to manage marine ecosystems still seems to be an open question, at least in the plans for the Oslofjord.

Halting coastal biodiversity loss is hampered by the lack of holistic ecosystem-based management for the Oslofjord. The RBMPs can only address parts of the threats, mostly from pollution. The municipalities can supplement by spatial regulations but do so only to little extent at sea. There remain many unaddressed land-use challenges on land, especially along the coastline, rivers and lakes. The government's Oslofjord Plan sets out a broad agenda also for biodiversity. Importantly, it includes fisheries, although additional measures beyond what already is in place have not been adopted yet. It is an open question to what extent the mobilization under the plan will include the whole range of efforts needed for protecting biodiversity. For instance, marine restoration has not been high on the agenda yet. Neither does the plan account sufficiently for the impacts of future climate conditions

3.4.2.2 Potential ways to improve the cross-compliance with these high-level Norwegian Objectives

The coherence across existing RBMPs, IOMP and municipal plans can be considered as rather limited, explaining why the objectives haven't been reached yet. Especially municipal planning that needs to balance several societal objectives, often leads to economic decisions being taken at the expenses of the environment (and the Oslofjord), which is an example of directly negative effect (= policy incoherence). With regards to the relationship across the other plans, we do not directly observe horizontal incoherence, but rather a lack of directly positive coherence. For instance, limited integration of RBMPs and IOMPs lead to inefficient governance of the coastal zone.

Since a few years, especially due to the contribution of the governmental Oslofjord Plan, we have observed an increased alignment of these strategic plans, with positive effects on the coherent implementation of policy instruments. Compared to these three strategic plans, the Oslofjord plan is driven by a high political ambition which has helped to integrate the focus on the Oslofjord into existing planning.

The following key actions would enhance the delivery of the high-level Norwegian objectives of zero pollution, biodiversity, and climate change adaptation:

- Develop holistic ecosystem-based management for the coast more systematically than in the Government's Oslofjord plan through a permanent framework.
- Better methods for ex-ante assessment of the effectiveness of measures, and for their ex-post evaluation. This applies to all the plans that have been reviewed.
- Introduce more authority to the River Basin Districts in Vannforskriften (Norway's transposition of the WFD).
- Introduce funds that can be allocated to those who implement measures according to the plan of action in the RBMPs.
- Review sectoral instrumentation to be coherent with the objectives of the Oslofjord plan
- Better protection of valuable and vulnerable species and habitats in Naturmangfoldloven (Nature Diversity Act), with obligations for the municipalities to follow suit in their planning and management

4. Conclusion

Throughout Task 3.2, we used a case study approach to examine the practical realities of implementing multiple legal and policy frameworks simultaneously. Specifically, and following the overarching research questions presented in *Table 2*, we assessed the coherence among the three planning systems established under the Water Framework Directive (WFD), the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD) in governing and protecting the marine environment. We also investigated whether the planning processes associated with these directives operate in cross-compliance to support the European Green Deal (EGD) objectives on zero pollution and marine biodiversity. Additionally, the task aimed to test and refine methodologies for assessing both policy coherence and science-policy-society interfaces.

Findings from the case studies illustrate aspects and mechanisms applied by national and local authorities that would contribute to advancing policy coherence across the three planning systems. As reflected in the analysed data (see sections 3.1.3; 3.2.3; 3.3.3; and 3.4.3) strengthening this horizontal coherence would also support the achievement of the of the EGD objectives on zero pollution and marine biodiversity. Key findings from this work, documented in this Deliverable 3.6, are succinctly summarized in Table 20.

Table 20: A selection of aspects and mechanisms applied by national and local authorities to advance policy coherence across the three planning systems and structured according to the coherence attributes and explanatory variables of the policy coherence assessment framework.

Objectives of the policies: Cross-referencing each other; mutually supportive or in potential conflict			
North Adriatic	French Med	Finnish Arch	Oslo Fjord
Complementarity WFD and MSFD objectives. Alignment of WFD and MSFD Objectives: mainly regarding biodiversity, eutrophication, and chemical contamination.	Mandatory alignment between the Façade strategic Document (MSFD+MSPD) measures and the SDAGE (RBMP) objectives.	Linking RBMP and MaS to address marine nutrient reduction.	Synergistic objectives in the RBMPs and IOMP (MSFD*).
Integration of WFD and MSFD objectives within the MSP framework.			
Instruments: Strategic tools or mechanisms used to achieve policy objectives			
North Adriatic	French Med	Finnish Arch	Oslo Fjord
	A single strategic framework aligning the requirements of MSFD and MSP.	WFD and MSFD transposed into Finnish legislation in the same act.	
Coordination of WFD, MSFD and MSP monitoring activities.	Coordinated WFD and MSFD monitoring.	Integrated coastal and marine monitoring. Aligned coastal-marine eutrophication indicators and objectives.	
	Measures defined taking into consideration environmental and economic interactions.		The Oslofjord Plan as a positive example of institutional layering, that has increased the

Coordination of the Adriatic MSP with terrestrial planning instruments.			coherence across existing planning instruments and positively contributes to the alignment of objectives and instruments across sectors.
Governmental structures: Set the framework for policy formulation and implementation (relevant organizations, their roles, responsibilities, and coordination between them)			
North Adriatic	French Med	Finnish Arch	Oslo Fjord
Coordinating agencies (e.g. ISPRA, ARPAs) for integrating MSFD, WFD, and MSP governance.	Consultative governance body of the French Mediterranean coast to support synergies in the operational implementation of the WFD, the MSFD, and the MSPD.	ELY Centres: central role in freshwater management (RBMP) and key regional actor in marine strategy implementation (MaS).	National coordination for WFD and IOMP (MSFD*) under the responsibility of the same governmental organization.
	Multidisciplinary expertise in freshwater and marine domains among Water Agencies (RBMP) civil servants.		
Science-policy-society interface Social processes that outline how knowledge is produced, transferred, and utilized in decision-making			
North Adriatic	French Med	Finnish Arch	Oslo Fjord
Environmental agencies (e.g. ARPA and ISPRA), together with universities and research institutions, acting not only as knowledge providers and policy advisors, but also as knowledge brokers and boundary organizations.			The Oslojord council: ensuring representation among sectors and governance levels, and increasing societal awareness (understanding that action across the entire catchment are needed to restore the fjord).

Potential ways to improve coherence

Findings from our case studies not only highlight areas in need of improvement (areas of incoherence) but also reveal situations that may resonate with other contexts across the EU. For each of these areas of improvement, we present either suggestions that emerged during co-creation processes, and/or opportunities for lesson extraction, particularly where a solution is already operational in one of the case studies.

Table 21: Overview of identified areas of policy incoherence and corresponding co-created solutions or transferable lessons from case studies

Exploit the role of MSP in the integration of environmental objectives into spatial decision-making for marine areas	
Situation:	The MSP, although mentioning support for the GES objectives, does not elaborate on specific measures or collaborative mechanisms with MaS for achieving GES in the marine environment. (Finnish Archipelago case study).
Potential for lesson extraction:	The guidelines establishing common principles for MSP in Italy states that, in the process of defining strategic objectives for MSP, coherence with the environmental objectives set out by the MSFD must be ensured. Among the

	strategic objectives of the MSP framework related to environmental protection, Objective OS_N 03 explicitly mandates the integration of spatially relevant measures from the MSFD's PoM into maritime planning measures (North Adriatic case study).
Strengthen the explicit links from the RBMP to MSP	
Situation:	The RBMP plans do not explicitly consider or aim at contributing to the MSP objectives or measures. MSP objectives (such as the planning of areas suitable for aquaculture activities, for the protection of coastal ecosystems, and for the support to blue economy sectors) could be compromised if they are not supported by a robust WFD basin plan (North Adriatic case study).
Suggestion:	A stronger alignment between the RBMP with the MSP would help ensure that land-based actions under RBMP would positively impact the marine environment and the maritime uses planned under MSP.
Suggestion:	Integrate land-based nutrient load data into site selection within the MSP processes. While the MSP may acknowledge the importance of nutrient reduction for marine environmental objectives, the direct integration of land-based nutrient load data into site selection or spatial allocation decisions is generally lacking.
Strengthen a structured coordination across all governance levels	
Situation:	Despite the existence of high-level coordination mechanisms were synergies between MSFD, WFD, and MSP are enabled, there is the need of further strengthening the cross-policy integration at all governance levels.
Suggestion	Strengthening the authority of one existing local agency to act as a central coordinating body, addressing the overlapping responsibilities and coordination challenges between institutions. This could be complemented by measures such as harmonizing reporting requirements and establishing a unified environmental monitoring platform to improve data integration. In addition, clarifying the distribution of funding responsibilities among competent authorities would enable a single point of contact to address sectoral policy issues, such as environmentally harmful subsidies.
Potential for lesson extraction:	Creation of technical working groups: e.g. one on land-sea interactions (bringing together representatives of the processes under MSP – WFD – Floods Directive – Port development – Spatial and landscape planning); another one on MSP – MSFD – Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (Protected Areas and Restoration) – Fisheries Policies (North Adriatic case study).
Potential for lesson extraction:	To support synergies in the operational implementation of the WFD, the MSFD, and the MSPD, as well as to address broader Mediterranean maritime issues, France has established the <i>Maritime Façade Council</i> CMF. This consultative body brings together over 50 different actors including state representatives, state services at sea and inland, freshwater representatives, university experts, work union representatives, and NGOs. The CMF meets twice a year to discuss and provide recommendations on strategic orientations for the Mediterranean Sea, while more targeted work is undertaken by specialized technical committees focusing on topics such as MPAs, marine renewable energy, and maritime employment (French Mediterranean case study).
Potential for lesson extraction	Oslofjord plan, a positive example of institutional layering, that has increased the coherence across existing planning instruments and positively contributes to the alignment of objectives and instruments across sectors. The plan uniquely integrates policy objectives and instruments across multiple sectors, including land use, agriculture, sewage, fisheries, spatial management, invasive species control, heritage, and climate initiatives.
Progressively develop an integrated land-sea stakeholder engagement process	
Situation:	Stakeholder involvement related to the WFD, MSFD, and MSP has largely occurred in silos with each policy operating its own engagement processes. Public consultations are managed separately for each policy and are sometimes criticised for not being sufficiently participatory. In addition, there is the situation that decisions are made at a national scale with few considerations of local specificities and obligations which can create frustration and incoherences with the local stakes

Suggestion:	Gradually coordinate consultation processes across different policies to establish an integrated stakeholder engagement framework. This will help support more holistic sea management (i.e. land-sea interaction, and “source to sea” approach) by ensuring inclusive and effective participation throughout the policy process.
Suggestion	Structured feedback channels, institutionalized mechanisms that systematically collect, process, and incorporate local input. For example, a regional maritime council with a formal process for reporting back to stakeholders on how their input shaped the final plan, digital platforms for submitting local concerns, and a reduction of administrative burden of policy and reporting for local stakeholders. These mechanisms would allow for continuous input, review, and adjustment of plans based on stakeholder feedback and new information. In addition, managers and people involved in the marine environments at the local level have emphasized the importance of strong political support, sufficient time, and open dialogue with civil society and businesses to ensure that the measures are accepted
Suggestion	Stakeholder engagement can be deepened by involving more key NGO. These organizations are often engaged in the MSFD and MSPD program of measure, bringing strong scientific expertise and maintaining good relationships with local populations. The role of key NGOs has been highlighted as essential in bridging the gap between state services which are often met with public scepticism, and local economic actors. NGOs also play a crucial role in raising awareness on the importance of environmental regulations
Potential for lesson extraction	Establishment of stable multi-actor platforms and structured consultation mechanisms across policies and across actors. This is something that the “ <i>Report: operational proposal for the start of the implementation and monitoring phase of the plans</i> ” (2024) supports as one on the actions to prioritise, by envisaging hearings held by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport on topics relevant to MSP, involving public administrations, associations and sector operators, research institutions and universities, and civil society organizations (North Adriatic case study).
Strengthen local technical competence and implementation capacity	
Situation:	Local authorities frequently face implementation challenges due to resource constraints, particularly limited human capacity within supporting institutions, which, although they provide support services, there are not enough human resources to respond to all the requests. As a result, local authorities sometimes abandon efforts to develop a more integrated management plan that could cover all requirements, instead prioritizing solutions that are more feasible within their limited resources and guidance
Suggestion:	Strengthening collaboration with local authorities, building local capacity through targeted training and knowledge-sharing, optimizing internal workflows, streamlining administrative procedures for project approval and funding, and forming public-private partnerships to supplement the workforce, are some of the actions that can address insufficient staffing levels
Suggestion:	A continuous system of funding is needed to ensure stable human resources and to fund research and capacity building. Ad hoc projects and initiatives are not enough to offer capacity-building activities and trainings to improve the competence framework of national and local authorities, but also more long-term institutional funds
Strengthen the science-policy interactions between terrestrial, coastal and marine water governance	
Situation:	Although the responsibilities for WFD and MSFD are allocated within the same ministry, in some contexts intra-organizational collaboration remains weak, being there a sharp divide between both sets of plans and with limited uptake of marine expertise in water governance and vice versa.
Potential for lesson extraction	Each Water agency (in charge of RBMP) has a service or an expert dedicated to marine coastal areas (2-3 person). One point underlined by many experts in France is that the Water Agency from the Mediterranean coast has achieved positive impacts and projects on the Mediterranean Sea, partly because it has created a marine service and it has integrated deeply qualified marine environment experts into its teams, providing strategic advice and active involvement. Besides, the involvement of Water Agency supports the land-to-sea continuum (French Mediterranean case).

Potential for lesson extraction	A French-water coastal committee has been created for coastal municipalities to support the specific implementation of freshwater measures impacting the marine environment (French Mediterranean case).
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Annex 1: Step 1 report template

Step 1 prepares the case study research design by specifying research objectives, cases, research questions and key actors.

Case Study: _____

1.1 The management and policy context

Basic introduction for someone who does not have much information about the region. It assists in orienting the reader on the “what, where, and why” of the case study. You can include for example key statistics, information on the political regimes in place (EU/non-EU/EEA, ...). A map would be very welcome.

1.2 Research questions

Current situation and main challenges, e.g. statistics on overfishing, climate change statistics and trends, and the biodiversity importance of the region (something that would clarify the reader why the focus on the horizontal and vertical coherence analysis).

Specific problem/focus explored within the horizontal analysis; specific EGD explored within the vertical analysis.

Overarching questions (from D.3.1):

For Task 3.2:

- *Horizontal coherence (e.g., “how do the interlinkages between national and local plans developed under the WFD, MSFD, MSP provide an integrated approach to govern and protect the marine environment?”),*
- *Vertical coherence (e.g., “to what extent does the resulting interplay between these three Directives’ national and local plans assists the reaching of the key GD objectives⁵⁴?).*
- *What is the takeaway?, What needs to be done to facilitate the realisation of the key GD objectives? Which lessons can be distilled that can assist the coherence and cross-compliance of marine policies both for their own intended objectives, as well as for the three Key GD ones?*

For Task 3.3

- *Do policy instruments [delivery mechanisms] set for the implementation of sectoral policies adequately internalize key-requirements of EU policies established to deliver healthy marine ecosystems (MSFD/WFD/MSPD)?*
- *Do policy instruments set for the implementation of sectoral policies adequately internalize the GD objectives⁵⁵?*
- *What can be learnt from impediments and best practices to facilitate the internalization of the key GD objectives into sectoral policies?*

Specific research questions to the case study:

- [...]

1.3 Governance and policy focus

Governance system: Describes the multi-actor at a multi-level system; ways of cooperation; includes the table of the stakeholders (EU, RSC, sub-regional, national, local); includes the policy focus (table, probably as an annex).

1.4 Policies, planning and processes assessed in the case study

Identify existing processes and key documents related to the policy focus. (See M2.1 on Interim mapping of key policies (August 2023), and D2.1 on the EU and international policy landscape

⁵⁴ The three key GD objectives: zero pollution, climate resilience, and the protection of marine biodiversity

⁵⁵ The three key GD objectives: zero pollution, climate resilience, and the protection of marine biodiversity

(December 2023). Information included in the and the SPS assessment framework (D1.4) can also be of help.

	WFD	MSFD	MSPD	Sector

1.5 Institutions and stakeholders involved in the case study definition and in data collection activities.

Identify key stakeholders associated to the “policy focus” (i.e. who have an influence on the implementation of the targeted policies, instruments, planning and implementation mechanisms and who can be influenced when the implementation of such elements take place) (see D5.2 on the stakeholder database, D5.4 on the stakeholder mobilization charter and its associated Internal operational guidance section, and D3.1 -in particular section 4.3 and Annex 1)

Organization	Relevance (WFD/MSFD/MSPD, sector)

1.6 Data collection activities

Identify the sources of data. Case study methodology relies on multiple sources of evidence, and although not all the approaches (questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, observation processes, document analysis) will be applicable in all the cases, relying on one source of data will not be enough to develop an in-depth understanding of the case (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Please refer to the CrossGov Operational Guidance Illustrated v.2

Bear also in mind that you will need the approval of the Ethics Committee as requested by your institute before initiating the data collection process. Remember also that data collected from these approaches needs to be registered as indicated in D6.1 on a plan for managing primary empirical data). It is also relevant to revise D6.2 on diverse ethical considerations.

1.7 Risks associated to this case study approach.

Identify main areas of risk to complete the case study and solutions for addressing them.

Annex 2: Step 2 report template

Step 2 assesses, within the relevant case study area, the current state of play in coherence and cross-compliance and the implications for policy outcomes. Both frameworks (the D1.3 Policy Coherence framework and D1.4 SPSI framework) have been aligned: in the Policy Coherence framework, the guiding questions for the SPSI explanatory variable are the main questions of each building blocks in the SPSI framework. The current document presents the template that case study leaders will use to document the findings of this assessment.

Case Study: _____

Instructions:

*All information answering the frameworks' questions should be made available in this document, which will later be used to write cross-case analyses in WP3, and feed into WP4 (Roadmaps and Methodologies). However, we encourage you to bring out only the **key messages** in the boxes given below. We therefore would suggest a limit of 2 - 3 pages per variable/attribute. Additional and supporting information, linked to the information provided in the boxes, can be included in the form of annexes. The number of Annexes and the number of pages for these is not limited.*

All analyses must be scientifically argued with information gathered from different sources (e.g. literature review, interviews, ...).

The documents to use in order to fill in this section are found on NIVA Teams

- [Clean and Updated D1.3 Coherence & cross-compliance methodology Feb 2024](#)
- [Policy coherence attributes - update and clean](#)

*Based on your case study specificities, **only relevant attributes/variables/blocks** must be selected and answered. In the boxes below you can document the answers for the questions you addressed. Please bear in mind that we are exploring the relationship (coherence) between policies/plans. We understand that not all the specific case study research questions are answered by means of the coherence framework; for those that do we would be expecting to see a set of completed tables. Please **indicate which cluster of policies/plans/strategies the coherence assessment is being applied to.***

*Please also note that the **SPSI framework** is seen as the further elaboration of one of the explanatory variables of the **Coherence Framework**; something that can help explain the lack of coherence. **Both frameworks (the SPSI and the Coherence framework) have been aligned:** in the Coherence framework, the guiding questions for the SPSI explanatory variable are the main questions of each building blocks in the SPSI framework.*

*The answers included in the table below for the explanatory variable nr 2 (SPSI) should be seen as a **synthesis** of the work on SPSI. The **extended responses** on the SPSI analysis, collected by means of the Excel template⁵⁶, are expected to be included in an annex of this*

⁵⁶ The Excel file is to be considered a tool to gather and structure information on the analysis of building blocks. There is no need to submit the Excel pages. The important part is that case studies leaders use the information/knowledge gather through the Excel file (or other means) to develop the narrative of the 4 SPSI-steps (and step 3 in particular) to be included in the annex.

Step 2 report, and as a narrative. This narrative should be structured/outlined in terms of the four SPSI-steps. Each step should describe the **main results** of:

Step 1 – Inception phase

Step 2 – SPS System diagram and description

Step 3 – Building blocks analysis (on all BBs or selected BBs according to step 1)

Step 4 – Synthesis (where needed and **not already covered** in explanatory variable n.2 of C&CC methodology)

The SPSI framework can be found on NIVA Teams [SPS Methodology](#). The material used in the SPSI training (November 2023) can be accessed [here](#).

Please note that this **extended responses for the SPSI analysis** are expected on 28th June 2024. The rest of the **Step 2 report** is expected on 30th April 2024.

When relevant, the Figures provided in [D1.2 Policy brief](#) and Figure 6 of [D1.3](#) on the graphical mapping of coherence for a case study can be used as inspiration for presenting the data from your case study.

Research question addressed ...

Policies being assessed: ...

Coherence attribute nr. 1: Policy Objective	
The outcomes, impacts, or the results that the policy sets out to achieve, as specified in the articles of the policy document, as well as broader objectives referred to in the preamble. May be referred to in policy documents as goals, objectives, targets, or commitments.	For policies to be coherent: - The policy objectives should be aligned or complementary and not contradict or impede each other.
1. Is the policy cross-referencing the policy objectives of another policy?	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 1	
2. Are the policy objectives aligned between policies? (substance as well as spatial and temporal scales such as deadlines for achievement, and geographical application)	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 2	
3. Are the EGD objectives mainstreamed ⁵⁷ into the policy?	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 3	

⁵⁷ Mainstreaming is understood as the integration of key policy and societal goals and considerations across policies from different sectors. In CrossGov, the focus is primarily on mainstreaming of the EGD marine relevant objectives for biodiversity, climate change and pollution

Coherence attribute nr. 2: Policy Instruments	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All mechanisms that are put in place by the policy to achieve its objectives. - Set of techniques that governments use, aiming at influencing the behavior of organizations or individuals in support of public objectives - Typologies of policy instruments have been created⁵⁸ 	<p>For policies to be coherent:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Alignment of policy instruments is considered beneficial for policy coherence.
<p><i>1. Would / has putting the policy instruments into practice lead / led to results that are in accordance with 1) the policy's own objectives, 2) other policies' objectives, 3) the EGD (CrossGov specific) objectives</i></p>	
<p>... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 4</p>	
<p><i>2. To what extent are spatial and temporal scales aligned between instrument of the different policies?</i></p>	
<p>... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 5</p>	
<p><i>3. Do the instruments support the cross-fertilization of information and knowledge across policies with similar instruments?</i></p>	
<p>... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 6</p>	
<p><i>4. Do policies have shared implementation mechanisms (shared licensing, common indicators, shared monitoring frameworks)?</i></p>	
<p>... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 7</p>	
<p><i>5. Do the policy instruments provide mechanisms to deal with conflicting objectives, incentives, etc.?</i></p>	
<p>... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 8</p>	

After evaluating the two Coherence Attributes (policy objectives and instruments), you are now requested to explore the three sets of Explanatory Variables that help explaining why a certain level of policy coherence is observed. If you found explanations that do not fit into any of these three categories, please document the information in the additional box provided at the end.

Explanatory variable nr. 1: Governmental organizational structures	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structures (within/across local, regional and national authorities, EU and international organizations) that set the framework within which policies are formulated and implemented. - These structures include the involved and responsible governmental organizations, their roles and responsibilities, their ability to address broader issues than their own “silo” issues, as well as their coordination mechanisms 	<p>It plays a role in the level of coherence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizational behaviour and collaboration to overcome working in silos (e.g. coordination and collaboration within and across organizations⁵⁹) - Clear mandates aimed at overcoming barriers - Clear responsibilities to work towards EGD objectives, and clear means to do so
<p><i>1. Are the mandates and roles of governmental organizations governing a policy issue clearly defined (overlaps or redundancies)? How does this affect their involvement in policy formulation and implementation, and their collaboration with other organizations?</i></p>	
<p>... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 9</p>	

⁵⁸ Examples of typologies: Economic (taxes, charges, fees, fines, penalties, liability and compensation schemes, subsidies and incentives, deposit-refund systems, and tradable permit schemes); Information (state-of-the-environment reporting, impact assessments, labelling schemes, technical standards, education campaigns); Legal (licenses, permits, prescriptions, prohibitions, bans); Compliance procedures (including monitoring and reporting schemes); Enforcement procedures (litigation and access to justice).

⁵⁹ Formalized processes such as the creation of supra- or lead institutions, inter-ministerial committees, joint task forces and decision-making bodies; or ad-hoc and informal coordination mechanisms.

2. Which intra- and inter-organizational (formal and informal) coordination mechanisms are in place and how do they support coordination across policies?
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 10
3. Are spatial and temporal scales of governmental organizations well aligned and also fit-for-purpose for the relevant policy issues areas?
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 11
4. How does resource allocation within governmental organizations affect their ability to formulate and implement policies, and to collaborate with other organizations
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 12
5. How do political processes and power dynamics within and between governmental organizations affect their influence on policy formulation and implementation?
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 13

Explanatory variable nr. 2: Science-policy-society interface ⁶⁰	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social processes that describe the role of knowledge production, transfer, and use in decision-making processes. - It also refers to the actors involved as well as their roles within the different phases of the policy cycle. 	<p>It plays a role in the level of coherence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the use of best available science and knowledge, from across different policy areas and actors, as a base for informed and coherent decisions
1. Are data and knowledge integrated or fragmented and how does this affect policy coherence? Example: Is data available and accessible to all actors of the SPS system? Are data gaps and uncertainty accounted for? Are interlinkages across sectors or governance levels well understood? Is data integrated across disciplines and policies? Is data covering relevant spatial and temporal scales to understand a policy problem.	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 14	
2. How do assessments affect policy coherence? Example: Are the assessments transparent? Which actors were involved in developing the assessments, and are some key providers of data and knowledge missing? Were cross-sectoral effects considered, also reflecting on other policy areas or environmental problems?	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 15	
3. How do models of knowledge transfer affect policy coherence? Example: Is knowledge production separated from policy-making (=linear) or is it based on a collaborative process? How well is society integrated in the co-production of knowledge? What are the transfer mechanisms in place?	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 16	
4. What is the role of Permanent SPSI platforms on policy coherence? Example: Have formal or informal platforms been established? Are the relevant actors engaged and are the platforms covering cross-sectoral dimensions of policies and facilitating coordination across policy areas and governance arrangements?	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 17	
5. How does competence and understanding of the problem/subject-matter affect policy coherence? Example: Do actors in the SPS system have a shared understanding of the problem? Are training and capacity activities enhancing systemic understanding?	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 18	
5. How does funding and resources affect policy coherence? Example: Are funding and resources allocated in a way that supports the production and transfer of relevant knowledge across governance arrangements?	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 19	

⁶⁰ This explanatory variable of SPSI sheds light on how stakeholders influence the production and transfer of knowledge; the explanatory variable of Stakeholder Involvement explicitly focuses on how stakeholders shape policy alternatives both during the formulation and design of policies as well as their implementation.

Explanatory variable nr. 3: Stakeholder involvement⁶¹	
- Manner in which stakeholders influence policy framing, design and implementation through participatory processes and other avenues such as information campaigns and lobbying, and how this affects coherence across policies.	It plays a role in the level of coherence: - Inclusive, participatory mechanisms that enable active exchange across a broad set of actors and interests, are more likely to have a stronger contribution to coherence than processes involving few interests that may be typical “clients” for one sector only - Involvement of different stakeholders in policy making and implementation processes enables integration of different information, knowledge, values and ideas and fosters agreement and buy in across different interest groups
<i>1. To what extent does stakeholder involvement affect policy choices during design and implementation, and how does this impact coherence across policies?.</i>	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 20	
<i>2. In how far are formal and informal stakeholder involvement mechanisms at different stages of the policy cycle aligned across policies?</i>	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 21	
<i>3. In how far do participatory processes (e.g. stakeholder platforms) in the process support the involvement of stakeholders across different policy areas/sectors?</i>	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 22	
<i>4. Are the consultation/participatory processes inclusive, fair, and equitable ensuring contributions of all relevant stakeholders or do power imbalances mean that contributions are biased towards certain stakeholders?</i>	
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 23	

Additional explanatory information
<i>1. The additional explanatory information in 2-3 sentences.</i>
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex 24
<i>2 The additional explanatory information in 2-3 sentences</i>
...
<i>.. The additional explanatory information in 2-3 sentences</i>
... Supplementary information can be found in Annex n.

⁶¹ This explanatory variable of Stakeholder Involvement explicitly focuses on how stakeholders shape policy alternatives both during the formulation and design of policies as well as their implementation. The explanatory variable of SPSI sheds light on how stakeholders affect-influence the production and transfer of knowledge.

Annex 3: Step 3 report template

Step 3 answers WP3 and case-study specific research questions; summarises other findings (if any); draws conclusions from the cases including areas for improvement.

Case Study: _____

Instructions:

The number of pages of the STEP 3 report is limited to 10 to 15 pages.

All analyses must be scientifically argued following the coherence evaluation framework; they should build up on the basis of the information gathered in the tables of the Step 2 report.

*The key research questions that WP3 aims to address have been fine-tuned along the development of the project. **Table 22** presents the questions for WP3 as presented in the DoA (left column) and how these questions have been operationalized with a Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 lens (middle and right columns). Case studies have at the same time defined more specific questions. They have been documented in the Step 1 reports ([link to the folder here](#))*

The current document collects the answers to these case specific questions (section 1). We are also asking case study leaders to answer -from the particular problem/angle explored in each of the case studies, the Task 3.2 / Task 3.3 questions (section 2). Finally, any other finding of interest to CrossGov which has not been covered already in the previous two sections, can be documented in Section 3.

Table 22: Evolution of the WP3 questions through a Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 lens

Key research questions that WP3 aims to address (as stated in the DoA)	Explanations of the questions with a Task 3.2 lens	Explanations of the questions with a Task 3.3 lens
How do the plans and planning processes that implement marine related legal and policy frameworks support or impede progress towards the GD objectives?	Addresses both: Horizontal coherence (e.g., “how do the interlinkages between national and local plans developed under the WFD, MSFD, MSP provide an integrated approach to govern and protect the marine environment?”), and	Addresses both: Do policy instruments [delivery mechanisms] set for the implementation of sectoral policies adequately internalize key-requirements of EU policies established to deliver healthy marine ecosystems (MSFD/WFD/MSPD)? and
What explains the degree of vertical coherence towards the GD objectives?	Vertical coherence (e.g., “to what extent does the resulting interplay between these three Directives’ national and local plans assists the reaching of the key GD objectives ⁶² ?).	Do policy instruments set for the implementation of sectoral policies adequately internalize the GD objectives ⁶³ ?
What can be learnt from impediments and best practices, as reported in the first two questions, to facilitate the realisation of the key GD objectives?	Addressed by analysing the findings from the first two questions For example: What is the takeaway?, What needs to be done to facilitate the realisation of the key GD objectives? Which lessons can be distilled that can assist the coherence and cross-	What can be learnt from impediments and best practices to facilitate the internalization of the key GD objectives into sectoral policies?

⁶² The *three key GD objectives*: zero pollution, climate resilience, and the protection of marine biodiversity

⁶³ The *three key GD objectives*: zero pollution, climate resilience, and the protection of marine biodiversity

Key research questions that WP3 aims to address (as stated in the DoA)	Explanations of the questions with a Task 3.2 lens	Explanations of the questions with a Task 3.3 lens
	compliance of marine policies both for their own intended objectives, as well as for the three Key GD ones?	

1. Answering case study-specific research questions

*We kindly ask you to write **1 page max per research question**; we encourage you to use this space to **bring the key messages**. Additional and supporting information can be included in the form of annexes. We also expect to see cross-references to material already presented in the STEP 2 report.*

Case study-specific research question n°1

Your research question: XXXX

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages; supporting information in Annex x; cross-reference to material in the Step 2 report]

Case study-specific research question n°2

Your research question: XXXX

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages; supporting information in Annex x; cross-reference to material in the Step 2 report]

...

Case study-specific research question n°n

Your research question: XXXX

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages; supporting information in Annex x; cross-reference to material in the Step 2 report]

2. Answering the Task 3.2 research questions

We kindly ask you to write 1 page max per research question; we encourage you to use this space to bring the key messages.

Task 3.2 research question n°1

Which synergies and conflicts / challenges appear in the operational implementation of River basin management plans (WFD), Marine Strategies (MSFD), and Marine Spatial plans (MSP) with the goal of xxx?

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages]

Task 3.2 research question n°2

Whether and how the operational implementation of River basin management plans (WFD), Marine Strategies (MSFD), and Marine Spatial plans (MSFD) are coherently contributing / considering measures to the delivery of the GD objectives of xxx?

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages]

Task 3.2 research question n°3

Whether and how the operational implementation of River basin management plans (WFD), Marine Strategies (MSFD) and Marine Spatial Plans (MSFD) are coherently contributing / considering measures for the management of [sector]?

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages]

Task 3.2 research question n°4

What needs to be done to enhance horizontal coherence to xxx

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages]

Task 3.2 research question n°5

What needs to be done to enhance vertical coherence that would contribute to the delivery of the GD objectives for xxx.

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages]

3. Answering the Task 3.3 research questions

We kindly ask you to write 1 page max per research question; we encourage you to use this space to bring the key messages.

Task 3.3 research question n°1

Do policy instruments [delivery mechanisms] set for the implementation of sectoral policies adequately internalize key-requirements of EU policies established to deliver healthy marine ecosystems (MSFD/WFD/MSPD)?

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages]

Task 3.3 research question n°2

Do policy instruments set for the implementation of sectoral policies adequately internalize the GD objectives?

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages]

Task 3.3 research question n°3

What can be learnt from impediments and best practices to facilitate the internalization of the key GD objectives into sectoral policies?

Your answer: [1 page max; bring key messages]

4. Reporting other findings of interest for CrossGov

We kindly ask you to synthesise this section in max. 1 page per topic. Please indicate 3 key words that quickly explain the content of the topic. Additional and supporting information can be included in the form of annexes.

Title of the topic: xxxx

Three key words: XXXX

Elaboration of the topic: [1 page max; bring key messages]